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Editorial Notes

The Faculty of Security - Skopje has continuously developed its educational and research work, and it is based on the basic values of the quality of scientific and professional activities and applied principles of ethics, independence, impartiality, relevance and research excellence.

Scientific and professional activity is the driving force behind the development of scientific thoughts, with which man, as an intelligent being, realizes it as a creative activity, which is formed and continuously grows, thus enhancing human existence, development in a technical-technological sense and in general social supremacy over natural forces and adaptation to one's own needs and overall human development in societies, and it is reflected through the results of the activities. Therefore, scientific and research activity is a clear indicator of civilizational achievements of today's society, and its development indicates general civilizational growth and development. Current social goods and prosperity are a direct consequence of scientific and research activities and the great progress of scientific thought.

Faculty of Security - Skopje has security as a basic requirement, which is expressed through personal, collective and global security, in all spheres of social life, as the subject of its scientific activities.

The publication "Faculty of Security - Skopje" is already of legal age and has been published continuously for 20 years. It is an expression of the constant progress of scientific and professional thoughts of the teaching and collaborative staff of our institution, but also of very eminent researchers from other institutions whose subject is security research and related areas, who have recognized the value and significance of this publication.

The scientific journal "International Yearbook of the Faculty of Security - Skopje" contains scientific papers that deal with current, contemporary topics and issues in the social sciences, with a special focus on security, but also papers of an interdisciplinary nature, with the application of new methodological approaches and the development of critical thinking in scientific and professional practice. Works have been reviewed by local and international experts in this field.

I would like to express my gratitude to the employees of the Faculty of Security - Skopje for their dedication and contribution to the previous and current editions in order to maintain continuity and meet the criteria for an international scientific journal. Of course, thanks to everyone who has already published works in our publication.

In the hope of teaching the development of scientific and professional thoughts, I would like to motivate my colleagues from academic and professional fields to participate in future editions.

Sincerely,

Chief editor, prof. Dr. Zlate Dimovski

APPLICATION OF TERRORIST ORGANISATIONS' STRATEGIES – POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE TRENDS

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Abstract

In the post-Cold War era, terrorism has emerged as the foremost transnational security threat, replacing the nuclear confrontation and large-scale armed conflicts characteristic of the Cold War period. Although traditionally perceived as an isolated act of political violence directed against the constitutional order, state security, and individuals, the growing ideological and political radicalisation of terrorists, combined with the availability of modern weaponry and advances in science and technology, has transformed terrorism into a mass and increasingly destructive phenomenon. This evolution has elevated terrorism from a national security concern to a threat of international and global significance.

This paper analyses the application of terrorist strategies in contemporary conditions, with an emphasis on their objectives, tactics, financial models, and the operational effectiveness of terrorist organizations within the context of global security. The focus of the study is an assessment of the objectives of these strategies from political, ideological, and psychological perspectives, highlighting the tactics employed in advanced terrorist actions, such as suicide attacks, the targeting of civilians, the use of the media, cyberattacks, and the use of drones. Through a comparative analysis of successful and unsuccessful terrorist strategies, the study seeks to identify the underlying factors that lead to their effectiveness or failure.

Keywords: security, strategies, trends, terrorist organisations, tactics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary terrorism represents a serious global threat that affects national security, social stability, and international relations. Terrorism is not merely a military or security phenomenon, but also a deeply social and political issue that involves the dissemination of violent ideas, strategies, and techniques aimed at achieving various objectives. Modern terrorist organisations employ diverse strategies to carry out their attacks, ranging from political and religious goals, through ideological and psychological motivations, to the use of advanced technologies and the media (Lambert, 2013:23-38).

For a comprehensive understanding, it is necessary to analyse the operations of contemporary terrorist organisations, with a focus on the strategies and tactics they employ to achieve their objectives in terrorist acts. Terrorism¹, as a strategy in modern conflicts,

¹ Terrorism is a multidimensional social phenomenon, and its conceptual definition therefore requires a multidisciplinary approach (Beriša et al., 2018).

encompasses a broad spectrum of aims, including political, religious, and ideological dimensions, as well as a profound psychological component directed towards creating fear, panic, and insecurity among civilians. As Pellegrino notes, “*terrorism is not merely an act of violence, but also a form of political and ideological action that exerts a long-term influence on public consciousness and international relations.*” (Pellegrino, 2008:42-56).

Contemporary terrorist strategies encompass efforts to overthrow political systems and governments, as well as the dissemination of radical ideas related to religious, ideological, or national objectives. The political goals of terrorist groups often include separatism, as exemplified by the *Irish Republican Army (IRA)* and *ETA* in Spain, which sought to overthrow existing political systems and achieve independence for their respective communities (Taylor, 2015:6-15). Religious terrorism, as represented by organisations such as *ISIS* and *Al-Qaeda*, aims to establish a religious order, such as an Islamic caliphate, or to eliminate “infidels” who oppose their interpretation of faith (Benedict, 2010:54 -70).

The tactics employed by contemporary terrorist groups include targeting civilians and infrastructure, as well as exploiting the media and modern technologies as instruments for spreading ideology, recruiting new members, and intimidating the public. Attacks such as those on the Twin Towers in New York in 2001 and in Paris in 2015, as well as the targeting of infrastructure such as power plants, bridges, and communication systems, demonstrate how terrorists aim to inflict maximum damage and provoke global fear (Schwander, 2002:101-112).

In addition, modern terrorist groups increasingly rely on the media and propaganda, especially through social networks, to disseminate their ideology and attract new members. *ISIS* became well known for its sophisticated propaganda, which included videos, texts, and images designed to inspire and recruit individuals worldwide. Cyberterrorism has emerged as a growing concern, as terrorists use the Internet to conduct hacking attacks against governments, banks, and critical infrastructure in order to cause disruption and undermine the normal functioning of states (Roy, 2014:110-128).

Examples of successful and unsuccessful strategies employed by terrorist organisations are an important part of the analysis. In 2014, *ISIS*² successfully controlled large territories in Iraq and Syria through a combination of propaganda, military operations, and terror. Similarly, in 2001 *Al-Qaeda*³ carried out an attack on the Twin Towers as a symbolic strike against American power. In contrast, groups such as *ETA* and the *Red Brigades* ultimately failed due to a lack of support from the local population and effective state countermeasures (Lambert, 2013:23-38).

For a comprehensive understanding, it is necessary to identify the strategies that terrorist organisations employ in contemporary conflicts and to analyse the differences between successful and unsuccessful strategies, as well as their impact on global security and political processes.

² *ISIS* (The Islamic State of Iraq and Syria) is a radical terrorist organisation that emerged in 2013 and became known for its territorial conquests in Iraq and Syria. Its ideology is based on a destructive interpretation of Islam, and the organisation has employed terror, executions, and propaganda to advance its objectives. *ISIS* has also attracted global followers through social media and has become a symbol of extremist struggle. (Peter, N. 2016: 45-67).

³ *Al-Qaeda* is a radical Islamic terrorist organisation founded in 1988 by Osama bin Laden. It became known for orchestrating attacks against the United States of America, including the attacks on 11 September 2001. Its ideology is based on the concept of global jihad, aiming to overthrow Western governments and establish Islamic states. *Al-Qaeda* is active across several continents, employing terror, attacks, and propaganda to attract followers and achieve its objectives (Bruce H., *Inside Terrorism*, Columbia University Press, New York, 2006, pp. 115-130).

2. OBJECTIVES OF TERRORIST STRATEGIES

It cannot be overlooked that terrorism, as a global phenomenon, occupies a central place in contemporary security studies and international relations. The strategies employed by terrorist organisations aim not only at physical destruction but also at creating fear and uncertainty within society. Contemporary terrorist strategies, which are largely oriented towards generating psychological impact, utilise diverse forms of communication, symbolic actions, and messages with profound political and ideological implications.

Unlike *traditional* terrorist strategies, which primarily focused on physical attacks against state institutions and military facilities with the aim of exerting political pressure or achieving territorial gains, *modern* terrorist strategies target civilian populations and critical infrastructure in order to generate global fear and uncertainty. These strategies often rely on psychological effects and the dissemination of messages through the media. Overall, contemporary terrorism has broader ideological and global objectives, whereas traditional terrorism was often local or national in character (Benjamin & Sima, 2015:152-154).

To fully understand this phenomenon, it is important to examine not only the nature of terrorist actions themselves but also the strategies behind them, as well as the various objectives that terrorists seek to achieve. The goals of strategies employed by terrorist organisations frequently extend beyond immediate physical effects, aiming instead at political change at global, national, or local levels. Terrorists often use violence as a means of generating political pressure, combining violent actions with psychological effects such as the spread of fear and societal disruption. Additionally, some terrorist organisations target civilian structures as a means of attracting international attention and ensuring that their ideology is recognised on the global stage (Benjamin & Sima, 2015:134-136).

Examining how different terrorist groups shape their strategies reveals the objectives of contemporary terrorist strategies, which most commonly include political, religious, ideological and psychological aims (Hoffman, 2006:34). Modern terrorist strategies increasingly employ psychological and media tools in order to achieve global political and ideological objectives. This approach makes terrorism a more complex phenomenon, involving not only physical violence but also profound effects on social consciousness and the global political landscape.

Political goals of terrorist organisations are among the most common motives behind the use of violent actions and strategies. Terrorists pursuing political aims seek to alter or destabilise political systems, overthrow governments, and, in some cases, establish new political entities. These groups frequently strive for independence or autonomy for specific ethnic or national communities, as exemplified by the *Irish Republican Army (IRA)* in Northern Ireland and *ETA* in Spain.

The Irish Republican Army aimed to create an independent Catholic state in Northern Ireland, free from British rule. Its strategy included attacks on British security forces, civilian and military targets, as well as criminal acts such as bombings and kidnappings. The organisation believed that the use of terrorism could induce change in the political system and compel the government of Great Britain to withdraw from Northern Ireland. Similarly, *ETA* sought to establish an independent Basque state in Spain. The group used terrorism to garner support from the local population and to pressure the Spanish government into granting Basque independence. The political aims of these groups were not limited to the violent overthrow of authority but also included attempts to establish ethnically and politically separate states. (Lambert, 2013:154-168).

Religious aims – Religiously motivated terrorists pursue a different set of objectives, often including the establishment of a religious order, the elimination of hostile religious

groups, and the radical interpretation of religious doctrines. *ISIS*, as one of the most prominent examples of religious terrorism, aimed to establish an Islamic caliphate and create a theocratic state across the territories of Iraq and Syria. By utilising terror to compel the local population to accept a radical interpretation of Islam, *ISIS* targeted Christians and other religious minorities, as well as Sunni Muslims who opposed its interpretation of religion. Actions such as beheadings, terrorist attacks on civilian targets, and gruesome online campaigns were employed to instill fear and promote a radical ideology that legitimised violence as a religious obligation (Hamid, 2017:101-104).

Similarly, *Al-Qaeda* used terrorism to promote its goal of establishing an Islamic caliphate. The main objective of this organisation was to confront the West and its culture, as well as to fight against what it perceived as American imperialism. Attacks such as the 2001 assault on the Twin Towers were intended to deliver a symbolic blow to American power and to create a global confrontation between the West and the Muslim world (Bruce, 2006:124-126). Religiously motivated terrorists use violence not only as a military strategy but also as a means to mobilize believers, instill fear, and declare war on all who disagree with their interpretations of religion (Taylor, 2015:202-218).

Ideological goals – Some contemporary terrorist organisations promote various political and social ideas, such as leftist, right-wing, or anarchist ideologies, which constitute their ideological goals. These groups use terrorism as a means to achieve their ideological objectives, spreading anti-corporate, anti-capitalist, or anti-immigrant views, and often oppose democratic principles.

In recent decades, radical right-wing groups in the USA and Europe have demonstrated how ideologically motivated terrorism can be directed against different social groups, such as migrants, ethnic minorities, or political opponents. These groups often use violence to spread neo-Nazi and anti-Semitic ideas. Similarly, leftist terrorist groups, such as the *Red Brigades* in Italy, used violence as a means to overthrow the capitalist system and promote communist ideology. Historically, ideologically motivated groups have often posed a threat to democratic institutions, as they have attempted to bring about radical political change in society through violence (Roy, 2014:96-112).

Psychological aims – The actions of certain terrorist groups, which involve creating fear and panic among civilians, as well as weakening trust in governmental institutions, reflect their psychological objectives. Terrorists use violence not only as a means of physically destroying the opponents but also as a way of manipulating public opinion and inducing deep psychological stress within society. The 2001 attack on the Twin Towers had a significant psychological impact worldwide, causing lasting uncertainty regarding global security. The attack was more than a mere military strike – it was a blow to the very core of Western society, symbolising a rupture in the historical perception of security (Bruce, 2006:145-156).

The psychological aims of terrorism include creating societal insecurity and weakening trust in authorities. Attacks on civilians, such as those targeting public squares, stadiums, or public buildings, aim to undermine the sense of safety and make people aware of a constant threat. When terrorists successfully instill fear among civilians, they not only achieve their immediate tactical objectives but also profoundly influence social consciousness, making populations susceptible to panic reactions and sustained fear (Benedict, 2010:73-81).

It can be confidently concluded that contemporary terrorism is a global threat encompassing not only physical but also profound political, religious, ideological, and psychological aspects. (Beriša, 2024) Modern terrorist organisations employ diverse

strategies to achieve their goals, including attacks on civilians, military, and infrastructure targets, as well as the use of the media and modern technologies to disseminate their ideas. The political objectives of terrorists often involve striving for independence or changes in political systems, as was the case with the *Irish Republican Army* or *ETA*, while religious objectives, such as those pursued by *ISIS* and *Al-Qaeda*, aim at establishing theocratic states and eliminating “infidels” or other religious groups. Ideological goals, including left-wing and right-wing ideologies, use violence as a means of promoting radical political views. The psychological impact of terrorism also plays a significant role, as terrorists seek to instill fear and insecurity in society, thereby undermining trust in institutions and the general sense of safety. The strategies of terrorist groups often include the use of the media and online platforms to mobilise support and recruit new members. The success of terrorist actions depends not only on physical destruction, but also on the ability to attract global attention and influence international relations. By analysing various examples of terrorist attacks, it becomes evident that some groups have achieved significant successes, while others have failed due to a lack of popular support and effective counter-operations. Terrorism, as a global phenomenon, has a profound impact on international security and continues to pose a major challenge for states in protecting their citizens and maintaining stability.

3. TERRORISM TACTICS IN TERRORIST ACTS

In modern conflicts, terrorism has become one of the key factors shaping strategies and tactics of warfare. Today, terrorist groups employ various methods that differ significantly from traditional warfare. These groups often rely on asymmetric tactics, with the primary aim of instilling fear and instability in society, while simultaneously undermining the military and political power of their opponents. Terrorist acts, which use terrorism as a form of combat, demonstrate how terrorists employ diverse methods such as attacks on civilian targets, sabotages, kidnappings, and digital propaganda.

According to *Pamela Hets*, the tactics of terrorist groups increasingly involve suicide attacks (suicide bombers) and explosive devices designed to cause maximum destruction of civilian infrastructure, while also influencing the international community (Hets, 2019:104). Furthermore, terrorists are increasingly focused on using media and Internet technologies to spread their messages globally. As *Jonathan Bowen* emphasises, the use of social networks enables terrorists to mobilise support, recruit new members, and coordinate their actions in real time, thereby making contemporary counter-terrorism efforts far more complex (Bowen, 2015:213).

The tactics employed by terrorists in contemporary conflicts are no longer confined to direct attacks on military targets. Instead, they increasingly focus on assaults against civilian populations and on eliciting the broadest possible psychological and political responses. By analysing the tactics terrorists use today – including attack techniques, the use of media, and their impact on social and political stability – several key strategies can be identified: targeting civilians and infrastructure, use of media and propaganda, cyberterrorism, suicide attacks, and use of modern technologies. (Bowen, 2015:176-246). Modern terrorism in conflicts demonstrates an evolution of tactics far beyond traditional methods of warfare. Terrorists now employ asymmetric tactics that include attacks on civilians, sabotages, digital propaganda, and advanced technologies, thus further complicating counter-terrorism efforts and profoundly affecting global security and political stability.

3.1. Targeting Civilians and Infrastructure

Terrorist groups frequently attack civilians and critical infrastructure as core tactics in modern conflicts. The attack on the Twin Towers in New York in 2001 remains one of the most well-known examples, where civilian targets and symbolic buildings were deliberately chosen to provoke global fear and panic. Attacks on mass gatherings, such as concerts, theaters, and public events, aim not only to inflict physical damage but also to generate psychological trauma on the public. Additionally, the destruction of essential infrastructure, such as power plants and communication systems, can lead to long-term repercussions for economies and public safety. The 2015 Paris attacks carried out by Islamist terrorists exemplify how assaults on civilians and critical infrastructure can result in numerous casualties and cause deep political and social destabilization (Schwander, 2002:141-156).

3.2. Use of Media and Propaganda

In an era of rapid technological development, media and social networks play a central role in disseminating the ideology of terrorist organisations and recruiting new members. ISIS, for example, has effectively used social networks and video campaigns as primary tools to spread its radical interpretation of Islam and attracting new fighters. Videos of terrorist acts circulated online served not only as instruments of terror and intimidation but also as global propaganda promoting narratives of a “righteous struggle” against Western powers. This type of propaganda also acted as a call for other radical individuals and groups to join the fight. In modern terrorism, media has become crucial for maximising the reach and influence of terrorist strategies (Pellegrino, 2008:210-225).

3.3. Cyberterrorism

Cyberterrorism is a new and increasingly widespread form of terrorism used to carry out attacks on state systems, banking institutions, and key infrastructure. Attacks on Internet platforms, government websites, and critical communication channels constitute a means of paralysing a state or company without direct physical intervention. Hacker attacks on hospitals, as well as on industrial and banking systems, can also lead to significant economic disruption and chaos. The dissemination of misinformation via the Internet represents another method of undermining public safety and democratic processes. In this type of terrorism, individuals and groups often use advanced technological tools capable of causing major global consequences, such as attacks on key government databases or electronic platforms (Lambert, 2013:253-267).

3.4. Suicide Attacks

Suicide attacks are among the most horrific and well-known forms of modern terrorism. Terrorist groups that employ this method, such as the Taliban in Afghanistan, target political leaders, military installations, and civilian populations. Suicide attacks have become a symbol of ruthless violence and ideological commitment, in which terrorists often sacrifice their own lives for political or religious causes. In Afghanistan, for instance, the Taliban used suicide attacks in response to the interventions of Western powers, hoping that these attacks would cause instability and undermine the morale of allied forces. Suicide attacks also have a significant psychological impact, instilling fear and insecurity on a global scale (Bakker, Cohen, 2010:180-194).

3.5. Use of Modern Technologies

Modern technologies, such as drones and improvised explosive devices, play an increasingly important role in contemporary terrorist attacks. Drones enable terrorist groups to strike targets far from their bases, thereby reducing the risk of detection and elimination. Drone attacks also provide new tactical possibilities allowing for operations that are rapid and difficult to defend against. Additionally, the development of improvised explosive devices enables terrorists to manufacture weapons capable of causing significant damage with minimal resources and training. This technology facilitates attacks on public spaces, military bases, and civilian facilities without the need for extensive logistic capacities (Najpau, 2016:114 -132).

The analysis of the tactics employed by terrorist organisations leads to the conclusion that modern terrorism is characterised by a wide range of methods that transcend traditional forms of warfare. Terrorist groups use asymmetric methods to instill fear, cause instability, and promote political destabilisation. Targeting civilians and infrastructure, the use of media and propaganda, and cyberterrorism constitute fundamental components of contemporary terrorist strategies. The introduction of suicide attacks and the use of advanced technologies such as drones and improvised explosive devices further increase the complexity and danger of terrorist action. Furthermore, terrorist organisations often rely on criminal networks to finance their activities, thereby complicating the global fight against terrorism. This confirms that modern terrorism has become deeply embedded in various spheres of social life and is conducted on multiple fronts, both physical and virtual.

3.6. Sources of Financing

The financing of terrorist organisations constitutes one of the key aspects of their functioning and the sustainability of their activities. These organisations use a variety of methods to raise funds, both *legal* and *illegal*, enabling them to evade detection and sanctions imposed by governments and international institutions. Some of the most common legal sources of funding for modern terrorist organizations include:

- *Donations and humanitarian aid.* Many terrorist organisations receive significant support through ostensibly legal channels, such as donations from private individuals or humanitarian organisations. In certain instances, terrorists use “fundraising campaigns”⁴ that conceal their true objectives under the guise of humanitarian assistance. An example of such practice is Hezbollah, which has used donations from Lebanon and the diaspora to finance its operations.
- *Entrepreneurial activities and lawful business operations.* Terrorist organisations often invest in legal business to generate profit. These businesses may operate in sectors such as construction, manufacturing, transport, and trade. For instance, the Taliban in Afghanistan has used revenue from agriculture and natural resources as a legal means of financing its activities.
- *Laundered funds channeled through legitimate avenues.* In some cases, terrorist groups use money laundering to legalise illegally obtained income. This process involves concealing illicit activities and channeling funds into legitimate business

⁴ Fundraising campaigns consist of organised activities aimed at raising financial resources or other assets for the purpose of supporting a specific project, organisation, or objective. These campaigns may serve a variety of purposes, including funding humanitarian initiatives, supporting charitable organisations, and financing research, education, and arts, or political initiatives. While the primary goal of fundraising is to raise financial resources, it may also involve collecting donations in the form of goods, services, time, or other resources.

entities. A common example is the use of offshore accounts and seemingly legitimate investments across various sectors worldwide (Kovačević, 2020:215-222).

- Some of the most commonly used illegal sources for funding modern terrorist organisations include the following:
- *Drug trafficking.* One of the most prominent and widespread methods of financing terrorist organisations is drug trafficking. Groups such as the *Taliban* and *Al-Qaeda* exploit the narcotics trade, particularly opium production and distribution, as one of their main sources of income. Collaboration with criminal and local drug cartels enables terrorists to raise substantial funds for the purchase of weapons and the organization of terrorist attacks.
- *Human and arms trafficking.* Some terrorist organisations finance their activities through human and arms trafficking. This trade is usually carried out through complex networks involving multiple countries and criminal organisations. An example of such activities is *Hezbollah's network* in Latin America, which finances terrorist operations through human and arms trafficking (Roy, 2014:250-267).
- *Kidnappings for ransom.* Technological advancements and global mobility enable contemporary terrorist organisations to conduct kidnappings for ransom as a means of raising funds. These operations typically involve abducting individuals from higher social strata or representatives of international organisations. A notable example is the kidnapping of Western nationals by *Al-Qaeda* in Syria, which was exploited as a means of collecting substantial financial resources.
- *Robberies and thefts.* Some terrorist organisations finance their activities through robberies and thefts, targeting banks or other facilities capable of yielding large sums of money. These organisations often use weapons and violence to secure funds for purchasing military equipment and financing their networks.
- *State sponsorship and support.* It is not uncommon for certain terrorist organisations to receive direct or indirect support from specific states. Such states may provide financial, logistic, or military assistance in order to achieve political objectives at regional or global levels. An example of this practice is Iran's support of *Hezbollah* in Lebanon (Kovačević, 2020:222-230).

The financing of terrorist organisations represents a complex and multifaceted network encompassing both legal and illegal activities. These groups exploit all available channels to secure funds for their operations while simultaneously attempting to evade detection by international institutions and security services. Consequently, the fight against terrorism necessarily includes global efforts to counter the financing of terrorist organisations. This requires enhanced international cooperation, the development of effective economic sanctions, the monitoring of financial flows, and the implementation of legal measures against individuals and entities that support terrorism.

4. EXAMPLES OF SUCCESSFUL AND UNSUCCESSFUL STRATEGIES

Certain contemporary terrorist organisations have demonstrated a remarkable capacity to employ diverse strategies that enable them to achieve their objectives, whether in terms of temporary territorial control or the destabilization of global security. These organisations have implemented innovative and asymmetric methods that allow them to exert significant influence at the global level, often provoking profound political, economic, and social changes.

For example, *ISIS* based its strategy on establishing and maintaining territorial control, which significantly differs from traditional terrorism, which focused primarily *on isolated attacks*. As James Laffey highlights, one of *ISIS*'s key strategies was the *temporary control of territories* in Iraq and Syria, which allowed the group to gain legitimacy among its followers and advance its ideological goals (Laffey, 2016:92). *ISIS* exploited uncertainty and political instability in these countries to establish a self-proclaimed "*Islamic State*", thereby decisively influencing international security and the dynamics of modern warfare. In contrast, *Al-Qaeda* gained *international attention* within the field of terrorism through its attack on the World Trade Center in New York on 11 September 2001. As Stanley Cohen emphasises, the attack on the Twin Towers marked a pivotal moment that ensured *Al-Qaeda*'s global reach and influence. Unlike *ISIS*, *Al-Qaeda*'s strategic orientation was not based on territorial control but on actions designed to provoke global fear (Cohen, 2008:174). This strategy, centered on *coordinated and large-scale attacks* such as those carried out on 11 September, aimed not only at material destruction but also at generating profound psychological and political effects, thereby eliciting worldwide mobilisation and responses.

However, not all terrorist strategies can be considered successful. In many cases, terrorist groups adopt methods that ultimately prove ineffective or unsustainable. Unsuccessful strategies may result from various factors, including insufficient understanding of local contexts, unanticipated reactions from civilian populations, and a lack of international support.

As James Laffey notes, examples of unsuccessful strategies can be observed in the actions of terrorist groups that, in pursuing their objectives, employ excessively brutal methods that provoke public rejection rather than support (Laffey, 2017:105). Numerous terrorist organisations, including certain formations operating in Africa, have utilised radical actions that trigger counter-protests and strengthen state and international security responses. In such cases, terrorists often fail to achieve long-term objectives or mobilise mass support, leading to rapid suppression of their activities.

4.1. Successful Strategies of Terrorist Organisations

The strategies of terrorist organisations play a central role in shaping contemporary conflicts and global security. These strategies frequently combine military, psychological, and propaganda methods in order to achieve political and ideological objectives. For the purpose of better understanding the successful application of these strategies and gaining deeper insight into the techniques employed by terrorist groups, it is useful to examine *ISIS*'s *strategy of temporary territorial control* and *Al-Qaeda*'s *strategy of coordinated attacks*. *The Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS)* represents one of the most striking examples of contemporary terrorism, combining military operations, propaganda, and terror to accomplish its objectives. From 2014 onwards, *ISIS* managed to temporarily control large parts of Iraq and Syria, enabling the group to declare the establishment of a so-called "caliphate", a state governed by radical interpretations of Islam and Sharia law. *ISIS*'s

strategy was based on several key elements, including military assaults on strategic cities, the use of terror as a governing tool, and the extensive use of modern media and technology to mobilise new supporters and disseminate radical ideology.

Regarding military strategies, *ISIS* targeted major urban centers such as Mosul and Raqqa in order to seize control of oil fields and other natural resources, which represented a major source of revenue for the organisation. These attacks were frequently accompanied by assaults on civilian targets aimed at spreading fear and conveying the message that civilians were not safe from violence, thereby creating conditions for a prolonged state of terror on conquered territories. This strategy was also employed to achieve political destabilization of the region and to undermine the capacity of local authorities to operate effectively (Najpau, 2016:114-132).

Alongside military operations, *ISIS* actively conducted highly sophisticated propaganda campaigns through social media and video content depicting both violence and territorial “victories.” Videos of executions, territorial conquests, and the destruction of cultural and religious symbols were designed to spread psychological terror and attract new members willing to join the organisation. These propaganda efforts also sought to portray *ISIS* as the primary liberator of the Islamic world from Western influence. This approach enabled the organisation to garner considerable support from radicalised individuals across the globe (Lambert, 2013:154-168).

With regard to financing, *ISIS* relied not only on traditional methods such as kidnappings and ransom but also on its control of oil fields in Iraq and Syria, which constituted a primary source of revenue. *ISIS* funded its military operations through these resources, alongside a range of illegal activities, including drug trafficking, arms smuggling, and human trafficking. This financial base was crucial for sustaining prolonged warfare and territorial expansion. Additionally, *ISIS* employed emerging technologies such as drones, enabling it to conduct reconnaissance and targeted strikes while minimising risk to its fighters (Schwander, 2002:141-156).

Al-Qaeda, as one of the most prominent terrorist organisations, successfully applied a strategy of attacks on symbolic targets designed to provoke profound political and psychological effects on a global scale. The 2001 attack on the Twin Towers in New York stands as one of the most significant terrorist assaults in history, causing major consequences not only for the United States of America but also for global security. This attack did not aim at territorial conquest or resource acquisition but rather at symbolic and psychological objectives – striking at American power and demonstrating the vulnerability of Western powers in the face of radical Islamic movements. The attack sought to generate a sense of global instability and weakness, through which *Al-Qaeda* aimed to convey the message that Islamic groups could confront Western powers and attract new supporters to radical jihad (Taylor, 2015: 202-218).

Al-Qaeda's tactics included terrorist attacks on public infrastructure designed to cause the highest possible number of casualties and to attract extensive media attention. The organisation used the media as a key instrument for spreading its ideology and mobilizing radicalised individuals worldwide. In addition, acts of terror and symbolic violence were complemented by *Al-Qaeda*'s efforts to construct a narrative of war between the West and the Islamic world, with the aim of motivating religious extremists to join its struggle against Western powers (Roy, 2014: 96-112).

Although the analysed terrorist organisations adopted differing approaches to achieve their objectives, both examples demonstrate how the combination of violent action, propaganda, and financial resources can yield temporary success. By exploiting modern

technologies and social networks, *ISIS* succeeded in mobilizing large numbers of radicalised individuals globally and executing military operations that enabled its temporary control over substantial territories in Iraq and Syria. *Al-Qaeda*, by contrast, achieved strategic success through a symbolic attack on one of the most significant American institutions, triggering far-reaching political and security consequences worldwide. Both cases underscore the power of terrorism as a strategy that carries not only military and political implications but also profound psychological effects on target populations (Lambert, 2013:154-168).

4.2. Unsuccessful Strategies of Terrorist Organisations

Unsuccessful terrorist strategies often emerge when violent methods fail to produce the desired political change. While some terrorist groups initially achieved short-term successes, they encountered strong resistance and international isolation in the long term. Terrorist organisations such as *ETA* in the Basque Country and the *Red Brigades* in Italy exemplify groups that, despite decades of terrorist actions, failed to achieve their primary political objectives. Ultimately, both organisations renounced violence, highlighting the limitations of terrorist strategies in achieving lasting political changes.

ETA was armed radical organization operating in Spain with the objective of establishing an *independent Basque state*. From 1959 onwards, *ETA* carried out numerous attacks, including bombings, assassinations of political and military leaders, and assaults on civilian facilities. Its strategy was centered on violent resistance against Spanish governance and the pursuit of an independent Basque nation. However, despite years of violence, *ETA* did not succeed in achieving its political goals, partly due to strong resistance from Spanish authorities and extensive international isolation resulting from its terrorist actions. Eventually, in 2011, *ETA* announced a permanent cessation of violence, and in 2018 the organization formally dissolved. It is important to emphasise that, after decades of terror, *ETA* recognized that violent methods did not lead to the resolution of political and social issues, which ultimately prompted the abandonment of its armed campaign and the conclusion of a ceasefire with Spanish authorities (Schwander, 2002:194-201).

Similarly, Italy's *Red Brigades (Brigate Rosse)* illustrate a leftist terrorist organisation that was active during the 1970s and 1980s. The goal of the *Red Brigades* was to overthrow the capitalist system and establish a socialist state, and their strategy included kidnappings, assassinations of political figures and public officials, as well as bomb attacks. The organization regarded itself as a representative of the working class and sought to incite a revolution in Italy. However, like *ETA*, the *Red Brigades* failed to achieve their political aims. The response of the Italian authorities proved highly effective, and public support for the group remained limited, which led to its weakening and eventual collapse. After years of violence and failure to achieve its objective, the *Red Brigades* ceased their activities and were officially disbanded in 1988 (Schwander, 2002:202-212).

In both cases, *ETA* and the *Red Brigades* faced numerous challenges, including sustained military and police resistance and widespread international condemnation of their actions. Ultimately, both organisations were forced to acknowledge that terrorism as a strategy did not produce meaningful political change, but instead resulted in significant human casualties and widespread destruction. Despite their ideological motivations and belief that violence could advance their goals, the final outcome was failure, leading both groups to abandon terrorist methods.

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that terrorist organisations such as *ETA* and the *Red Brigades* demonstrate that terrorism, while capable of attracting attention

and producing short-term effects, is not a sustainable strategy for achieving long-term political objectives. Human casualties, property destruction, and social isolation are among the key factors contributing to the failure of such groups. Despite their ambitious goals, these organisations ultimately recognised that violent strategies do not lead to lasting or constructive solutions.

5. COMPARISON OF SUCCESSFUL AND UNSUCCESSFUL STRATEGIES

Terrorism as a strategy in contemporary conflicts is an exceptionally complex and multifaceted phenomenon, grounded in the diverse objectives and tactics employed by terrorist organisations. From political and religious goals to the dissemination of ideological and psychological impulses, terrorists employ a wide range of methods to pursue their ambitions. The success or failure of these strategies depends on multiple factors, ranging from an organisation's capacity to mobilise local populations and secure international support to its ability to acquire resources and direct its actions toward broader geopolitical objectives.

The case of *ISIS* illustrates how a terrorist organisation can employ a combination of propaganda, military operations, and terror as core tactics for the temporary conquest and governance of territories in Iraq and Syria. The success of this strategy was not solely the result of terrorist attacks but also stemmed from the organisations's ability to mobilize individuals on the ground and attract international support networks. Within this framework, *ISIS* used modern technologies, such as social media, to disseminate its ideology and recruit new followers. This approach exemplifies how terrorism can be integrated into a broad spectrum of military and propaganda tactics that extend beyond traditional forms of violent action (Taylor, 2015:281-285).

In contrast, the example of *Al-Qaeda* demonstrates that a successful terrorist strategy does not necessarily require territorial conquest. The 2001 attacks on the Twin Towers were symbolic yet highly effective in provoking a global psychological response. Such attacks were designed to instill fear and anti-government sentiment, producing profound political consequences worldwide. *Al-Qaeda*'s strategy also relies heavily on local cells and recruitment from conflict-affected regions, enabling the organisation to exert global influence without the need for physical territorial control (Taylor, 2015:286-295). Unsuccessful strategies, such as those employed by *ETA* in the Basque Country and the *Red Brigades* in Italy, demonstrate that a lack of local support and isolation from the general public can lead to the collapse of terrorist organisations. Although *ETA* remained active for an extended period, it ultimately abandoned violent methods after failing to secure sufficient support from its base and facing persistent government suppression. Similarly, the *Red Brigades* were unable to garner broader public support for their objectives and ceased their violence-based strategy following effective countermeasures. These examples underscore the critical importance of stable local support as a key determinant of the success of a terrorist strategy.

International support also plays a pivotal role in shaping the effectiveness of terrorist organisations. While *ISIS* and *Al-Qaeda* were able to leverage global support networks, *ETA* and the *Red Brigades* failed to develop comparable international resources. Resource mobilisation is equally essential, as organisations such as *ISIS* employ modern technologies, including sophisticated media campaigns and cyber-terrorism, to secure new resources and ideological backing. These strategies enable terrorist groups to maintain operational activity on a global scale, even when resources are limited or when they are subject to sustained state pressure.

The distinction between successful and unsuccessful terrorist strategies lies primarily in the organizations' ability to mobilise local populations and cultivate international support. Organisations such as *ISIS* and *Al-Qaeda* have successfully combined propaganda, military operations, and terror as instruments to achieve their objectives. Conversely, *ETA* and the *Red Brigades* faced insufficient support and failed to attain their political aims, ultimately leading to the abandonment of violence.

In conclusion, the success or failure of a terrorist strategy is not determined solely by the violent tactics employed but also by the organization's capacity to attract and sustain local and international support, as well as to mobilise resources effectively. The study of both successful and unsuccessful cases demonstrates that terrorism as a strategy in contemporary conflicts does not always aim at territorial conquest; rather, it may function as part of a broader geopolitical dynamic in which psychological impact and symbolic attacks can, at times, be more influential than direct physical control.

6. CONCLUSION

Contemporary terrorism represents one of the most complex security challenges faced by both individual states and the international community as a whole. As a phenomenon deeply rooted in political, economic, and social conditions, terrorism has evolved throughout history, taking on new forms in response to technological development and global political dynamics. Its multidimensional and transnational character stems from a range of interconnected causes – ideological, ethnic, religious, economic, and political – resulting in context-specific manifestations across different regional and historical settings. Analyses further indicate that modern terrorism is more technologically advanced, mobile, and flexible than ever before. Contemporary terrorist organisations, such as the *Islamic State* and *Al-Qaeda*, have combined classical methods of terrorist activity with new tools, including cyber attacks, drones, online propaganda, and cryptocurrencies used to finance their operations. Their strategies frequently involve symbolic and highly media-visible attacks designed to generate global resonance and attract new supporters. Nevertheless, while these organisations have exerted significant short-term influence, their long-term stability and public support have proven unsustainable.

In contrast, organisations such as *ETA* or the *Red Brigades* failed to achieve their objectives, primarily due to limited support, strong state responses, and the absence of a coherent political platform. This underscores that terrorism, as a strategy, rarely leads to long-term political success, although it can nonetheless cause significant destabilisation and human tragedy in the interim.

Successful strategies employed by terrorist organisations most often rest on three pillars: a clear ideological foundation, effective propaganda, and adaptability to global trends. When these elements are absent, organisations lose both legitimacy and operational capacity. The examples of *Al-Qaeda* and *ISIS* demonstrate that territorial control and media manipulation can create the appearance of strength, yet simultaneously render these organisations targets of intense international counteraction. In the absence of a long-term strategy and sustained support, such organisations face internal divisions and declining influence. Historical evidence further shows that violent action without public backing and clearly defined objectives leads to isolation and, ultimately, the disbandment of terrorist groups.

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GENERATION Z PROTESTS IN NEPAL COMPARED WITH THE ARAB SPRING: THE EVOLUTION OF THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract

This article compares the Arab Spring protests in Tunisia and Egypt (2011) with Generation Z protests in Nepal (2025) to examine how the shift from friend-centric networks (Facebook/Twitter) to algorithmically curated ecosystems (TikTok/Discord/Telegram) reshapes mobilisation thresholds, the pace of contention, organisational depth, and political outcomes. Methodologically, it employs a qualitative comparative design based on secondary sources using theoretical criteria: platforms/infrastructure, mobilisation threshold, tempo/volatility, organisational depth (the “signal vs. capacity” ratio), and outcome. The theoretical framework draws on Granovetter and Tufekci, as well as approaches to connective action and affective publics. Findings indicate that digital networks lower participation thresholds and barriers to entry into collective action, thereby accelerating diffusion. In Tunisia and Egypt, social media amplified coordination within existing trade-union and party structures; in Nepal, mobilisation emerged and was coordinated online through horizontal influencer–moderator networks without party backing. Large Discord communities functioned as deliberative hubs and heightened visibility, while viral short-form video produced rapid, affect-driven escalation; yet organisational capacity lagged behind the visible “signal”, and the protest cycle remained short and volatile. Conclusion: the shift to algorithmic feeds increases speed and scale but constrains institutionalisation; durable change still depends on organisational “bridges” that convert visibility into sustained capacity.

Keywords: Generation Z protests; Nepal 2025; Digital mobilisation; Mobilisation threshold; Social media.

1. INTRODUCTION

The 2025 unrest in Nepal, part of a broader wave across Africa and Asia and labelled in public discourse as Generation Z protests, bears multiple resemblances to events in Egypt and Tunisia during the 2011 Arab Spring, which culminated in regime change through mass demonstrations. Common features include youth as the principal protagonists; dissatisfaction with corruption and bleak economic prospects; demographic pressure (a youthful population and high youth unemployment); “leaderless”⁶ movement and

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⁶ The concept of “leaderless movements” refers to decentralised, horizontally organised forms of collective action in which the absence of formal leadership does not imply an absence of coordination; rather, coordination is reconfigured into networked, algorithmically mediated processes of decision-making and influence. Such movements operate through distributed authority, and their cohesion derives from shared moral and symbolic orientations rather than hierarchical structure (Bennett & Segerberg, 2012). Under contemporary socio-digital conditions, “leaderless” models represent a new paradigm of political mobilisation, in which

coordination; and the pivotal role of social media in mobilisation and organisation. The article compares Nepal with Egypt and Tunisia using criteria of volatility (Hale, 2020), mobilisation thresholds (Granovetter, 1978), and the signal-capacity ratio (Tufekci, 2017), alongside relevant theoretical concepts, to provide a synthesis of how protests evolved when digital platforms played a significant role.

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopts a comparative qualitative approach to examine three cases of mass protest: Tunisia and Egypt during the Arab Spring (2011) and Nepal (2025). The analysis is based on secondary sources: academic literature, reports by international organisations, media analyses, and statistics from relevant institutions (United Nations, World Bank, Transparency International).

This article employs a qualitative comparative case-study design, focusing on three cases (Tunisia, Egypt, and Nepal). The limited number of cases allows for in-depth, context-sensitive analysis of protest dynamics and the role of social media. In terms of case selection, the article follows a most-similar systems logic: Tunisia and Egypt are chosen as paradigmatic cases of the first “wave” of digitally mediated mass uprisings in authoritarian contexts during the Arab Spring, where Facebook and Twitter operated in tandem with trade-union and party infrastructures. Nepal (2025) is selected as a theoretically salient successor case: it exhibits comparable structural conditions, a pronounced youth bulge, high youth unemployment, and entrenched corruption, but takes place in a later communication ecology dominated by TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, and Discord and is largely devoid of organisational backing from parties or unions. Comparing these three cases, which all culminated in leadership change within a short time frame, allows the article to hold constant key socio-demographic and governance pressures while varying the configuration of digital platforms and organisational infrastructures that mediate mobilisation, protest dynamics, and outcomes.

The case studies encompass events in Egypt (2011), Tunisia (2011), and Nepal (2025), with an emphasis on the function and significance of social media in establishing durable foundations for social and political activism. The units of analysis are platforms and the broader digital infrastructure (Facebook/Twitter vs. TikTok/Discord). The criteria by which social media are analyzed across three distinct social and political contexts, hence their roles and modes of influence, are:

- Mobilization threshold (the speed and scale of the response to a trigger)
- Tempo and volatility (the dynamics of event development)
- Organizational depth (the relationship between signaling and capacity)
- Protest outcomes (institutional, political, and social effects)

The theoretical framework integrates both classical and contemporary concepts of mobilization to achieve a multilayered understanding of the key dimensions of digital protest.

collective action emerges from communication networks rather than institutional discipline (Gerbaudo, 2012; Tufekci, 2017).

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Generation Z is most commonly defined as those born between the mid-1990s and the early 2010s, with exact bounds varying by source but often taken as 1995–2010. This generation is frequently described as the first truly “digital generation”, having grown up in a world where the internet was already embedded in everyday life. Unlike previous generations, they have never experienced a reality without digital connectivity (Benítez-Márquez et al., 2022; Katz et al., 2021).

The mobilisation threshold refers to the point at which the number of individuals willing to participate in protest, or the intensity of their grievances, reaches a level sufficient to trigger mass action. Individuals decide to join when they perceive that the risks are outweighed by the benefits, often once they observe that they are “not alone” (Granovetter, 1978; Tufekci, 2017).

Volatility, in this context, refers to the degree of political and social unpredictability. Under high volatility, short-term events – such as spontaneously, digitally coordinated protests – can produce deep systemic consequences for the governing authorities and economic stability (Hale, 2020).

Tufekci draws a key distinction between signals of power and actual capacity. Signal denotes the visible display of strength – mass gatherings, viral content, protest marches – at which digital networks excel by rapidly assembling large crowds and generating striking visual and media effects. Capacity, by contrast, refers to the ability to convert that signal into durable political power: organisational infrastructure, clear demands, bargaining mechanisms, and the ability to sustain pressure over time. Capacity requires structure, leadership, hierarchy, and continuity – features that networked protests often lack because they rely on spontaneity and horizontality (Tufekci, 2017).

Bennett and Segerberg (2012) introduce the concept of “*connective action*” to explain individualised, network-mediated participation grounded in personalised narratives rather than stable organisations. Papacharissi (2015) theorises “*affective publics*”, highlighting the roles of emotion, humour, and anger in the circulation of political messages on platforms. These approaches complement Tufekci’s signal–capacity distinction: affective virality rapidly inflates the signal, while the absence of organisational infrastructure constrains capacity and the longevity of protest cycles.

4. KEY EVENTS

4.1. Tunisia (2011)

Mohamed Bouazizi’s self-immolation in Sidi Bouzid (17 December 2010) escalated within days into a wave of protests across Tunisia. Demonstrators’ demands – combating corruption, unemployment, and repression – were articulated and disseminated via social media. Facebook played a decisive role in transmitting information and connecting activists (Bruns, Highfield, & Burgess, 2013). The protests lasted several weeks and culminated on 14 January 2011, when President Zine el-Abidine Ben Ali, after 23 years in power, fled the country.

4.2. Egypt (2011)

The Egyptian protests began on 25 January 2011, Police Day, as an expression of opposition to corruption, police brutality, and economic stagnation (Howard & Hussain, 2011). Inspired by the success of the Tunisian demonstrations, Egyptian activists used the

internet and social media, most notably the Facebook page “We Are All Khaled Said”, to call citizens to mass mobilization (Eltantawy & Wiens, 2011).

The protests spread from Cairo to Alexandria, Suez, and other cities. The demands became more clearly articulated, evolving from calls for social reforms and justice to explicit demands for President Mubarak’s resignation. Over 18 days of contention, the authorities sought to suppress the movement through a mix of repression and concessions, including the shutdown of internet and mobile networks (Howard & Hussain, 2013). Despite violence and intimidation, on 11 February 2011 President Hosni Mubarak resigned after thirty years in power.

4.3. Nepal (2025)

The immediate catalyst for the protests was a nationwide ban on popular social media platforms, including Instagram and TikTok, which provoked outrage among youth who relied on these platforms for expression, organizing, and economic activity (The New Humanitarian, 2025). Although the ban was later lifted, it only further fueled pre-existing grievances.

A significant mobilizing factor, one that further intensified discontent among youth who felt overlooked and marginalized, was the heavily publicized “nepo kids/nepo babies” controversy (Reuters, 2025). Social media circulated numerous videos showcasing politicians’ children enjoying luxuries unattainable to ordinary citizens, in a country where the average annual income is roughly US\$1,500 (World Bank, 2024).

The protests began on 8 September 2025 and culminated on 9 September, when Prime Minister K. P. Sharma Oli resigned. Over the course of two days, demonstrators mounted mass protests that escalated into unrest, resulting in incursions into state institutions, including parliament and the presidential residence, the latter of which was subsequently set on fire. Having secured the prime minister’s resignation, new elections, and following the deployment of the army to the streets to restore order – with the military assuming a mediating role between the protesters and state institutions, chiefly the president – the protesters succeeded in securing the appointment of their preferred candidate as interim prime minister, bringing the protest to conclusion.

5. SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC AND ECONOMIC CONTEXT

The cases analyzed – Egypt and Tunisia during the Arab Spring (2011) and Nepal (2025) – share structural similarities that made youth mobilization likely and potent: pronounced youth demographic pressure (*youth bulge*⁷), high youth unemployment, and systemic corruption that erodes trust in institutions.

Egypt: According to the United Nations (2011), the 15–29 cohort constituted approximately 27% of the total population. World Bank data for 2010 record youth unemployment at 24.8%, with higher rates among university graduates. The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2010) gave Egypt a score of 3.1/10, indicating widespread public-sector corruption.

⁷ The term *youth bulge* denotes a demographic structure in which the share of young people – most commonly those aged 15-29 – significantly exceeds other age groups within the total population. This phenomenon arises when fertility remains high over an extended period while mortality declines, producing a large cohort entering the labor market and public life simultaneously (Urdal, 2006). In socio-political terms, the youth bulge is frequently associated with an elevated risk of political instability, protest, and violent conflict – especially where high youth unemployment, economic inequalities, and weak institutions are present (Cincotta et al., 2003).

Tunisia: The 15–29 cohort accounted for roughly 25% (United Nations, 2011), and youth unemployment stood at 30.7% (World Bank, 2012). The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2010) assigned a score of 4.3/10, reflecting broad discontent with corruption and the opacity of state institutions.

Nepal: In 2024–2025, the 15–29 cohort represented 27.9% (UNFPA Nepal, 2023); youth unemployment was 20.8%, with high informality (~55%) (World Bank, 2024). The Corruption Perceptions Index (Transparency International, 2024) is 35/100 (rank 108/180), indicating persistently high perceived corruption. Corruption and nepotism remain chronic (Mulmi, 2025). Since 2020, average GDP growth has remained below 5%; remittances account for ~33% of GDP; and about 1,700 people leave the country each day in search of work (Mulmi, 2025).

Table 1. Key sociodemographic and governance indicators

Indicator	Egypt (2010–2011)	Tunis (2010–2011)	Nepal (2024–2025)
Share of population aged 15–29	27% (UN, 2011)	25% (UN, 2011)	27.9% (UNFPA Nepal, 2023)
Youth unemployment (15–24)	24.8% (World Bank, 2010)	30.7% (World Bank, 2010)	20.8% (World Bank, 2024)
Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI)	3.1/10 (Transparency International, 2010)	4.3/10 (Transparency International, 2010)	35/100 (Transparency International, 2024)
CPI rank	98/178	59/178	108/180

6. THE ROLE OF SOCIALMEDIA IN THE SUPPORT STRUCTURE AND ORGANIZATION OF PROTESTS

6.1. Tunisia (2011): Trade-Union Infrastructure as the Backbone of Mobilization

In Tunisia, although the immediate trigger for the mass protests was Mohamed Bouazizi’s self-immolation, the General Union of Tunisian Workers (UGTT) played the key role in transforming spontaneous discontent into an organized movement. Deeply embedded in the country’s social fabric, it was the only institution with the logistical, communicative, and network capacities to mobilize citizens at the national level (Beinin, 2016). The UGTT organized general strikes, coordinated protest sites, and steered the narrative toward political reform, thereby effectively assuming the role of political organizer. Thus, while digital communication was important for disseminating information, the foundation of the Tunisian protests was institutional: mobilization was socially structured rather than purely networked (Alexander, 2011).

The Tunisian case thus illustrates a hybrid pattern: elements of connective action (networked diffusion and personalized narratives) were layered onto existing collective structures (the UGTT and student organizations), while affective impulses were channeled through union infrastructure. In this configuration, a strong social-media signal was translated into mobilizational capacity via institutional bridges.

6.2. Egypt (2011): The Digital Spark Harnessed by Political Actors

Unlike Tunisia, the Egyptian protests began as connective action around the Facebook page We Are All Khaled Said (Howard & Hussain, 2013), but quickly spilled into collective political structures: the April 6 Youth Movement and the Muslim Brotherhood assumed on-the-ground coordination, logistics, and media outreach (Lynch, 2012). Affective publics on social media supplied speed and scale, while organizations provided capacity and continuity. Egypt thus also represents a hybrid model: digitally initiated, politically co-opted. In both Tunisia and Egypt, social media simultaneously accelerated mobilization and heightened international visibility, yet the decisive weight still rested with offline structures (Bruns, Highfield, & Burgess, 2013).

6.3. Nepal (2025): Structureless Digital Self-Organization

The 2025 protests in Nepal exhibit a qualitative shift in the pattern of political mobilization. Unlike the Arab Spring protests, they had no institutional backing. No opposition party participated, and the largest parties – Nepali Congress, CPN-UML, and the Maoist Centre – publicly distanced themselves from the demonstrations (Suwal, 2025). The movement emerged exclusively online, coordinated across TikTok, Discord, and Telegram, where informal moderators and Gen-Z influencers disseminated messages and mobilized crowds. Reports by Amnesty International (2025) and Freedom Forum (2025) describe a “horizontal network of digital nodes,” which enabled viral diffusion while also accelerating the loss of cohesion.

In digital terms, synthesizing telecom and survey data, recent estimates suggest that by January 2025 there were about 16.5 million internet users in Nepal – roughly 55.8% of the population – and some 14.3 million social media user identities, equivalent to 48.1% of the population (DataReportal, 2025; Paudel, 2025). These figures are broadly consistent with World Bank and ITU series, which put internet use at around 55% of the population in 2023 (World Bank, 2024). A recent UNICEF–ChildSafeNet situation paper, drawing on Nepal Telecommunications Authority data, reports that in the first quarter of 2024 there were 42.34 million broadband mobile connections in a country of roughly 29 million inhabitants (about 145% of the population), underscoring the ubiquity of mobile access in everyday life (UNICEF & ChildSafeNet, 2024). Within this environment, Meta’s advertising tools indicate that Facebook⁸ and Instagram alone could reach approximately 14.3 million users – 48.1% of the total population and 72.8% of adults (18+) – while Instagram had around 3.9 million users, or 13.2% of the population, with a clear concentration in the 18–34 age cohort (DataReportal, 2025). In parallel, the Internet Service Providers’ Association of Nepal estimated that TikTok had around 2.2 million users before the November 2023 ban and that TikTok traffic alone accounted for nearly 40% of total internet bandwidth consumption (Prasain, 2023). Taken together, these figures indicate that for connected young Nepalis, social media use is close to universal, with platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and especially TikTok operating less as marginal entertainment apps and more as core

⁸ In order to clarify how the social media environment in Nepal differs from that of Egypt and Tunisia, it is important to note that in the contemporary digital landscape, Facebook and Instagram have largely moved away from their original friend-centred architecture and have progressively adopted TikTok-like recommendation logics. As a result, Facebook now operates much like TikTok or Instagram Reels – as an algorithmic, short-video-dominated discovery feed in which exposure is driven primarily by engagement signals and “interest clusters” rather than by pre-existing social ties (Narayanan, 2023; Gerbaudo, 2024).

infrastructures of everyday communication and identity. This helps explain why attempts to curtail social media access triggered such a strong and sustained Gen Z backlash. In practice, this viral diffusion was carried by highly visual, memetic content, anime-inspired protest flags, ironic placards and short TikTok clips that mixed humour with footage of police violence. These circulated faster than any formal call to protest and made the uprising instantly recognisable as a Gen Z event.

Nepal thus exemplifies a dominant connective action pattern: coordination via TikTok, Discord and Telegram channels, driven by influencers and moderators, without party anchoring. The dynamics were powered by affective publics – emotionally charged, visually forceful, and often ironic video clips –that produced rapid spikes of attention and low thresholds for participation. This mechanism helps explain both the strong initial signal and the brief duration of the cycle, as well as the difficulty of converting that energy into organizational depth. Consequently, the institutionalization of outcomes remains limited despite impressive visibility.

It is important to underscore the unprecedented method through which the candidate for interim prime minister was chosen, and the role of the social platform Discord. During the mass protests, youth movements – primarily students, programmers, and activists from Kathmandu – created the Discord server “Youth Against Corruption,” which quickly grew to more than 100,000 members. Initially, the server was used to coordinate protests, share logistics, document abuses, and raise funds. When a political vacuum emerged (the prime minister resigned and parliament was dissolved), organizers opened dedicated channels for “interim government candidate proposals.” Members anonymously nominated public figures with reputations for integrity, including journalists, judges, and activists. Former Supreme Court Justice Sushila Karki soon emerged as the leading option.

Activists then ran an in-platform poll on Discord; Karki received approximately 3,833 votes out of 7,700 participants, the highest by a wide margin (Mulmi, 2025). This result was relayed to the media and the armed forces. Within 48 hours, the president, under public and international pressure, formalized that choice by appointing Karki as interim prime minister. This episode set a precedent in contemporary political history: for the first time, the selection of the candidate for interim prime minister stemmed from a digital process of deliberation and collective decision-making on a platform originally designed for gaming and social interaction.

7. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The comparative analysis of the selected cases comprises, first, an examination of the platforms employed, with attention to their affordances, and, second, an inquiry guided by the adopted theoretical criteria (Tufekci, 2017): mobilization threshold, pace, organizational depth, degree of violence, and outcomes.

Platforms:

- Egypt & Tunisia (2011): Facebook and Twitter – **sharing premised on friend/follower networks;**
- Nepal (2025): TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, Discord – **operation premised on algorithmic feeds**⁹.

Key implications:

- Speed of diffusion: algorithmic feeds enable content to go viral within hours, whereas friend networks rely on chain sharing.
- Decentralization of authorship: content can originate from anyone; content performance matters more than author identity.
- Affective amplification: algorithms privilege emotionally charged, visually salient, and often polarizing content, spurring collective reactions and a sense of urgency.
- Weaker narrative control: states and legacy media struggle to manage virality because content flows are fragmented and driven by interactions rather than hierarchy.

In the Nepali case, the abstract properties of algorithmic virality were visible in a distinctive visual and memetic repertoire. One strand revolved around pop-cultural symbols, most notably the Straw Hat Pirates' Jolly Roger flag from the anime and manga *One Piece*. Initially circulating within anime fandom and social-media spaces, the flag quickly migrated to the streets: protesters carried it on black banners and, during the fire at Singha Durbar, hung it across the palace gates as a generational emblem of defiance against censorship and corruption (Ratcliffe, 2025). A second strand centered on emotionally charged close-ups, above all the now iconic image of a blood-soaked white sneaker left on the asphalt near the parliament building, which was shared millions of times and came to symbolize the bodily risk and precarity borne by young protesters (Shree et al., 2025.) Short-form TikTok and Instagram videos further combined irony and destruction: clips of teenagers dancing in front of burning government buildings or filming choreographed routines amid tear gas and sirens travelled quickly through recommendation feeds, were endlessly re-uploaded, and picked up by international media (Paul, 2025; NDTV, 2025). These image-meme hybrids circulated faster than any single organizational call, repeatedly resurfacing on "For You" pages, lowering the subjective threshold for participation while simultaneously blurring the line between political witnessing and performative clout-seeking.

⁹ During the first wave of digital activism, the Arab Spring (2011), social media such as Facebook and Twitter operated primarily on friend graphs: network structures formed by direct interpersonal ties (friend-friend or follower-followed). Information diffused horizontally within networks that were fundamentally social rather than algorithmically mediated. In this model, the content a user sees depends on personal ties and direct sharing, which fosters trust and organic diffusion but constrains the speed and scale of reach. By contrast, contemporary platforms such as TikTok, Instagram Reels, Telegram channels, and Discord communities are built around algorithmic feeds – systems in which AI-driven recommendation models determine what content a user sees, independent of personal contacts. These feeds analyze user behavior (watch time, interactions, topical interests) and dynamically push high-engagement content, enabling messages to spread vertically and exponentially, often far beyond the author's primary social graph.

Mobilization threshold: Compared to Egypt and Tunisia, where mass mobilization expanded over time as events unfolded and content was gradually shared (police brutality, regime violence), Nepal saw almost instantaneous mass mobilization; in other words, the mobilization threshold was very low. The visibility of injustice, repression, and corruption through algorithmically propelled short-form video (the so-called *story culture*¹⁰) provides what is perceived as continuous visual evidence for the crowd. This depresses the mobilization threshold and compresses the time from outrage to street-level protest.

Pace and volatility: Egypt and Tunisia – slower onset with prolonged momentum and duration; Nepal – a sharp onset with a short-lived trajectory. The $T_0 \rightarrow T_1$ interval (trigger \rightarrow first mass mobilization) is shorter than in 2011.

Organizational depth (signal and capacity): In Egypt and Tunisia, social media were employed for promotion and coordination, yet the principal anchors remained offline (trade unions and political parties). In Nepal, organizational structures were shallower: no parliamentary party participated in the protests, and coordination relied on Discord groups with promotion via other social platforms (TikTok, Instagram). The signal was stronger in Nepal, but capacity was weaker. This “signal vs. capacity” distinction underscores that a large, rapidly assembled crowd is not equivalent to organizational strength; as Tufekci shows, this is a structural limitation of networked movements, which is why contemporary outcomes more often take the form of policy concessions rather than deep regime change.

Outcome: Egypt and Tunisia – regime change; Nepal – the fall of the government and the announcement of parliamentary elections within six months, but no sweeping or deep structural transformation.

Table 2. Comparative dynamics of 2011 and 2025 protest waves

	Egypt & Tunisia (2011)	Nepal (2025)	Key implications
Platforms	Facebook, Twitter	TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, Discord	Paradigm shift in communication ecology.
Mobilization threshold	Gradual build-up via time and chain-sharing	Near-instant mobilization; low threshold	Lowered threshold: shortened time from anger to street.
Pace & volatility	Slower onset; longer momentum and duration	Sharp onset; short-lived trajectory; high volatility	Faster cycles increase tactical speed but reduce staying power.
Organizational depth	Social media for promotion/coordination, anchored by robust offline structures (unions, parties)	Coordination via digital groups; no parliamentary parties involved; promotion on TikTok/Instagram	Greater signal , lower capacity : mass turnout \neq organizational strength.

¹⁰ *Story culture* denotes a digital mode of communication through short-lived, ephemeral narratives (“stories”) that operate as visual and emotional micro-events in real time. In contrast to the static *post culture*, where posts are durable and reflective, *story culture* fosters immediacy, spontaneity, and shared participation. In the context of contemporary social movements, this expressive model enables the rapid diffusion of emotions, moral messages, and micro-narratives that serve as triggers for collective action. (Leaver, Highfield, & Abidin, 2020; Tufekci, 2017).

	Egypt & Tunisia (2011)	Nepal (2025)	Key implications
Outcome	Regime change	Government collapse and parliamentary elections called (without deep systemic transformation)	Contemporary movements more often yield policy concessions than deep political restructurings.

8. CONCLUSION

The case studies support the conclusion that the causes of protest onset are structural in nature –unemployment, corruption, and poverty – accompanied by implicit trigger factors. Of particular importance is that the dynamics of events in 2011 and 2025 differ considerably. An analysis of the structural patterns of social-movement organization in Tunisia (2011) and Egypt (2011), on the one hand, and Nepal (2025), on the other, reveals significant shifts in how political discontent is transformed into collective action. Whereas the Arab Spring protests were anchored in social and political structures – trade unions, opposition parties, and civil-society networks –the 2025 Gen Z protests in Nepal exemplify a mode of near-total digital self-organization, largely without traditional institutional intermediaries. The shift in technological infrastructure from friend-centric networks to algorithmic feeds directly shaped the tempo, scale, and volatility of the protests, enabling faster but also more superficial mobilization.

Put differently, the protests in Tunisia and Egypt belong to an era in which social media served as instruments for organizing pre-existing opposition structures, whereas Nepal exemplifies a period in which social media themselves become a relatively self-sufficient oppositional infrastructure. While, during the Arab Spring, trade unions and opposition parties functioned as bridges between the digital and the street, the Gen Z protests display a fully digitized mode of political mobilization, driven by visibility algorithms, viral formats, and a collective sense of injustice, yet lacking substantive political articulation. One can argue that the protests of 2025 constitute the first wave of “post-organized” contention, in which the network takes on the role of the party and virality substitutes for leadership. Nevertheless, this form of post-organized resistance, though highly visible and affectively intense, often lacks sufficient institutional depth to produce durable political transformations, rendering it effective in the short term but weak over longer horizons.

Looking ahead, the very features that make post-organized contention fragile in institutional terms are also likely to shape future political processes. The Nepali case suggests that generationally concentrated, digitally native cohorts can rapidly alter the tempo and visibility of politics without relying on parties or unions. Over time, this may reinforce a durable generational divide in which Gen Z and younger Millennials experience politics primarily through short-form, algorithmically curated content rather than through programmatic party competition. Electoral campaigns, candidate branding, and issue framing are therefore increasingly likely to follow the logic of personalised, meme-based signalling that Bennett and Segerberg (2012) describe as “connective action,” rather than the organisation-centred repertoires that structured the Arab Spring.

Ultimately, the comparison between the Arab Spring and Nepal’s Gen Z uprising highlights a broader strategic dilemma for digitally mediated contention: how to translate rapid, spectacular visibility into the slow work of building durable organisations and policy

influence. Future research on digital protest will therefore need to focus not only on platforms and protest waves, but also on the intermediate organisational forms – from issue-based collectives to hybrid party–movement structures – that might bridge this gap and avoid what Tufekci (2017) terms “signal-rich, capacity-poor” mobilisation.

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SECURITY GOVERNANCE IN AN ERA OF MANAGED CHAOS: SELECTIVE INTERESTS AND THE RUSSO- UKRAINIAN CONFLICT IN DEGLOBALIZING INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract

In an era of global instability, erosion of universal values and the reconfiguration of international relations around selective interests, the concept of “normality” is increasingly perceived as a dynamic instrument of geopolitical and economic rationality rather than a static, value-based framework. This paper examines the transition from globally recognized norms toward fragmented, interest-driven structures within an emerging bi-multipolar international order. Through cases such as the expansion of economic sanctions, the US–Ukraine critical minerals agreements, and the retreat from eco-social commitments, it argues that contemporary normality reflects a system of managed chaos characterized by selective norm application and context-dependent legitimization of power. The analysis uses the Russo-Ukrainian conflict as a focal case to illustrate how managed chaos and selective interests reconfigure security governance.

Theoretically, the study draws on the critical school of international relations, post-structuralist thought and Bauman’s notion of liquid modernity. Methodologically, it combines comparative analysis, case studies and political-discursive interpretation of primary sources and recent data from reputable agencies. Empirical evidence includes quantitative data on sanctions, trade fragmentation, and global perceptions of democracy.

The findings indicate that normality now operates as a legitimizing mechanism for rationalized instability – a strategic tool that reconciles conflicting interests within an unpredictable geopolitical landscape. This reconceptualization challenges traditional notions of stability and exposes the paradox of order built on managed disorder. The study concludes by raising key questions: How is normality constructed and maintained at the regional level? What social and cultural mechanisms support its endurance? And can new ethical frameworks emerge within an increasingly pragmatic global environment?

Keywords: Security governance, deglobalization, managed chaos, selective interests, Russo-Ukrainian conflict.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary international relations are witnessing a profound structural transition. The long-dominant paradigms of globalization, stability and universal norms are being replaced by selective interests, fluid rationalities and regionally differentiated spheres of influence. The emergence of a bi-multipolar order does not merely redefine the balance of power among great powers; it fundamentally reshapes the very notion of “normality” in international relations.

In this context, the concept of *policing* is understood in a broader sense –not limited to institutional law enforcement, but as a form of security governance and normative control exercised by states and international actors within a deglobalizing, interest-driven international order. This perspective allows the paper to examine how mechanisms of control, regulation and legitimacy – traditionally associated with policing – now operate across multiple levels of global governance.

Traditionally, normality has been understood as a condition of stability, institutional order and predictable cooperation. However, since the turn of the 21st century, this concept has steadily eroded under the weight of crises, hybrid conflicts and competing normative frameworks. The once-dominant paradigms of realism and liberal institutionalism are increasingly unable to provide comprehensive explanations, while post-structuralist and critical approaches have gained prominence in capturing the fluid and contingent character of the contemporary order (Acharya, 2014; Bauman, 2000).

This research examines how normality today functions less as a shared value-based condition and more as a dynamic construct leveraged by actors with asymmetric power. Rather than a universal moral consensus, the international system is characterized by selective norm adherence, pragmatic interests and functional adaptation.

The paper is structured into five thematic chapters. Chapter 1 analyzes the transition from globalization to deglobalization. Chapter 2 explores the bi-multipolar structure and the fragmentation of norms. Chapter 3 examines the normalization of selective interests through cases such as economic sanctions and critical minerals agreements. Chapter 4 discusses the transformation of political rationality. Chapter 5 addresses whether today’s managed chaos has itself become new normality.

A globally accepted definition of ‘managed chaos’ describes a situation in which disorder is not only present but actively overseen or strategically directed. It implies the absence or erosion of traditional structures, combined with efforts to impose a level of organization or direction within that disorder. Accordingly, the toolkit of “managed chaos” operates across different social spheres: economic, political, military, aiming to disrupt collective memory, weaken national-cultural continuity, reduce societal resistance and undermine the ability to self-organize and develop. One of the principle reasons for “managed chaos” is the decline in international law dominance.

The conclusion offers a synthesis and critical reflection on the implications of this transition for the concepts of stability and international order.

FROM GLOBALIZATION TO DEGLOBALIZATION

In the late 20th century, globalization emerged as the dominant paradigm for development, international cooperation, and the diffusion of liberal-democratic values. Institutions such as the WTO, IMF, World Bank, and the United Nations embodied the narrative of a rules-based global order founded on market openness, legal universality, and human rights (Rodrik, 2020). This framework facilitated cross-border market integration, transnational mobility and even humanitarian interventions. Over time, however,

globalization also produced deepening inequalities and structural asymmetries, eroding the very system it constructed (Stiglitz, 2017). Rather than uniform stability, it generated a hierarchical network of power and influence in which “global rules” often served the interests of those who shaped them.

Deglobalization has not occurred abruptly; it has unfolded through concrete economic, political, and technological measures. Tariffs introduced by the Trump administration on Chinese goods, the abandonment of multilateral agreements like the TPP, and the UK’s exit from the EU (Brexit) exemplify this trend (Zielonka, 2018). The post-pandemic period and the war in Ukraine have further accelerated this shift.

The Russo-Ukrainian conflict exemplifies how contemporary crises redefine global security governance within a deglobalizing world. It demonstrates the transition from collective norms to selective interests, in which sanctions, energy politics, and strategic communication become instruments of managed instability. The conflict functions not merely as a regional war but as a mechanism for restructuring power relations and legitimizing control through the normalization of chaos. In this sense, the Russo-Ukrainian case provides a critical lens for understanding broader transformations in international relations in the 21st century.

The scientific concept of “managed chaos” has been developed and employed in the context of hybrid war. Russian narratives erroneously attribute this strategy to US actors, their legitimising subversive activities against states in which the Russian Federation conducts or plans military operations. President Putin’s public discourse reflects extensive engagement with the “managed chaos” concept; content analysis identifies at least 50 references to “chaos” in three main contexts:

- 1) As a difficult legacy of the 1990s that he skillfully overcame;
- 2) To characterize countries in the world where the culprits of chaos are allegedly created and supported by the USA or NATO;
- 3) The conceptualization of chaos as a global phenomenon and an instrument of hybrid warfare.

Analysis of Russian sources indicates that the “managed chaos” tactic is understood as a policy of deep interference in the internal affairs of sovereign states, subversive operations, economic and diplomatic pressure, interference in the electoral process, political corruption, information manipulation, the formation of the “fifth columns”, and other destabilising measures. Drawing on the experience of the 2014 events of the so-called “Russian Spring” in Ukraine, operations of “managed chaos” unfolded in three directions:

- 1) chaos of mass consciousness,
- 2) obstruction of state institutions,
- 3) organization of street protests and riots.

The chaos of large systems represents a specific element of social dynamics and social changes, shaped by the selection of future models of systemic existence (Rushchenko and Zubar, 2021).

These dynamics explain why the Russo-Ukrainian conflict was selected as a suitable example for analysing the theory and practice of “managed chaos”.

Security discourses, calls for national self-sufficiency and efforts to secure critical mineral resources have led to the re-nationalization of strategic industries and the reframing of global interconnectedness as a vulnerability rather than a value. A key indicator of deglobalization is the weakening of universal institutions: the UN Security Council has been paralyzed by competing vetoes; the WTO’s arbitration mechanisms are in crisis; and the WHO came under scrutiny during the COVID-19 pandemic. Multilateral diplomacy is

increasingly replaced by ad hoc coalitions and bilateral agreements, producing a fragmented and competing architecture of global governance (Flockhart, 2016).

Rather than a single global system, regional centers of power are now emerging, including China's Belt and Road Initiative, Russia's Eurasian Economic Union and BRICS, and the EU's Green Deal and digital regulation strategies. This raises a fundamental question: is the world moving towards a new global order or towards multiple competing normative orders?

Deglobalization is profound and multifaceted and has military implications. As global interconnectedness weakens, states are recalibrating security policies and forming new alliances. The fragmentation of the international order contributes to a more unpredictable and potentially hostile environment, in which regional players and traditional alliances increasingly depend on dominant European states and coalitions. In this new era, military power is increasingly defined by the ability to adapt in changing geopolitical conditions, where the old certainties of globalization no longer apply.

Advances in military technology, the era of permanent information, and accelerated technological development have moved far beyond traditional conventional warfare, global security and the future of international alliances. As the world moves further into this era of technological development, the risks of conflict and instability are likely to increase, reinforcing the need for new mechanisms of conflict management and cooperation. These risks associated with deglobalization have intensified significantly since the invasion of Ukraine (Bucăța and Tudorache, 2024). Following the pandemic, debates on strengthening of supply-chain resilience and reducing dependence on imports for critical public health supplies further reinforced the deglobalization trajectory.

BI-MULTIPOLARITY AND THE FRAGMENTATION OF NORMS

With the end of the unipolar moment and the rise of China as a global economic actor, the system of international relations has shifted from the dominance of a single power to a bi-multipolar structure. In this system, two global cores (the US and China) operate alongside regional actors and organizations (Kaldor, 2013). Russia positions itself as a "third center" through security, energy and cultural narratives. Bi-multipolarity does not spell the end of globalization, but rather its reconfiguration into complex, competing spheres of influence and fragmented orders.

With the weakening of Western universalism, new actors like Turkey, India, Brazil, and Iran position themselves as "hybrid" normative actors. They blend economic pragmatism with regional security strategies (Kirkova, 2023). Through initiatives like BRICS+ and regional mediation efforts, these states contribute to a differentiated global normality. The growing autonomy of regional powers challenges the notion of a single, global consensus.

In this fragmented context, the US seeks to maintain its economic and military leadership but faces growing challenges in imposing its normative frameworks (Levitsky & Ziblatt, 2018). China, by contrast, pursues infrastructural diplomacy and economic expansion without promoting liberal values. Russia defends its "normality" through military presence, resource leverage, and nationalist narratives. The EU attempts to uphold liberal norms through green and digital policies but struggles with internal divisions and external pressures.

Whether bi-multipolarity leads to cooperation or conflict will depend on the strategic choices of the world's most powerful states and their ability to adapt to weaker and dependent states within their spheres of influence. Retaining relevance in a bi-multipolar

system will require moving away from paradigms of unilateral dominance toward strategies that emphasize partnership, flexibility and economic stability. Understanding polarity transitions can guide policymakers toward a more secure and predictable global future in today's uncertain era. Embracing the realities of bi-multipolarity, rather than resisting them, offers the best chance to foster a stable and cooperative international order. As the emerging global order becomes increasingly decentralized, the West's ability to maintain a leading role depends on its willingness to embrace necessary reforms and to share strategic leadership with other global powers (Ivanov, 2025).

NORMALIZATION OF SELECTIVE INTERESTS

Economic sanctions have become an increasingly common tool of political pressure in the 21st century. The US, EU and their allies use sanctions not only in response to aggression (as in the case of Russia) but also as a means of reshaping global economic relations (Naumovska, 2023).

Reuters (2023) data show that from 2014 to 2024, the number of sanctioned entities linked to Russia grew by over 150%, from approximately 400 to more than 1,000 companies, banks and individuals. Sanctions are no longer merely a punitive tool; they have become a new form of global governance, transitioning from economic interconnectivity to selective exclusion. In this context, "normality" no longer implies fair market rules but the pragmatic containment of competitors.

One of the most significant examples is the critical minerals agreement between the US and Ukraine, signed in 2025. This agreement enables Ukraine to access American markets and technology, while the US gains priority access to key minerals such as lithium, titanium and rare earth elements (Reuters, 2025). Ukraine possesses deposits of 22 of the 34 minerals that the EU classifies as critical, including lithium, titanium and graphite (Al Jazeera, 2025). However, a significant portion of these deposits is in areas under Russian control, complicating their exploitation (CIRSD, 2025).

In recent years, under the banner of national security and economic resilience, the US has imposed new tariffs (25% on steel and aluminum and 25% on automotive products), (Reuters, 2025). This shift moves the logic of global trade from free competition towards protectionist arrangements. Russia and China respond with similar policies, creating competing normative blocs of. For example, the US withdrawal from environmental standards on plastics and waste (Reuters, 2025) illustrates how sustainability principles are selectively applied in line with national interests.

World politics, as a process of normalization, enables powerful states to exercise power at the lowest possible cost and with minimal resistance. Such compliance is seen as the ultimate form of satisfying both domestic and international requirements for peace and development. Multilateral forums require states to compare themselves with others, exposing themselves to peer pressure and potential embarrassment. States are encouraged – and at times coerced – to become peaceful, redirect their power away from war and conflict and focus on economic development. Thus, they are seen as acting in compliance with international norms, rules and laws governing interstate relations.

Normalization in world politics involves the projection and anticipation of social behaviors and attitudes. The repeatability aspect of normality concerns expectation regarding how states and societies should act and perform their roles. Despite the cosmopolitan appeal of normalizing interventions intended to promote peace, development and international order, Western values and modes of engagement may be readily accepted in some regions while being restricted or denied in others (Lemay and Visoka 2022).

POLITICAL INSTABILITY AND SECURITY MANAGEMENT

Contemporary crises have weakened institutional mechanisms and concentrated power in individual leaders. Examples include Ukraine's strengthened executive power during wartime, Trump's "presidential diplomacy," and Putin's "personalized stability" (Schedler, 2013). Instead of a formalized order, a form of "exceptional normality" emerges – the acceptance of charismatic leaders who promise efficiency over institutional legitimacy (Levitsky & Ziblatt, 2018).

This transition highlights the concept of "rationalizing the exception" (Habermas, 2012; Kirkova, 2023) – the idea that governance no longer rests on norms but on permanent crisis management. Values become secondary tools rather than foundational principles and political processes are increasingly justified by "efficiency" rather than democratic norms.

Unstable governments often lead to military takeovers, which suppress civilian participation in decision-making. Turbulent changes in leadership disrupt policy continuity and the overall development of states (UNHCR, 2021). Countries in the Middle East have so far witnessed significant migrant crises due to prolonged instability (Dzacka, 2024)

The ongoing Russo-Ukrainian conflict has fundamentally reshaped Europe's security paradigm, compelling European nations to urgently reassess and enhance their security management frameworks. This conflict serves as a stark reminder of traditional state-on-state aggression and hybrid threats, demanding a multifaceted response across defense, intelligence, energy, cyber and economic domains. It has catalyzed significant increases in defense spending across Europe, with nations moving towards or exceeding the NATO 2% GDP guideline (NATO, 2023). These investments focus on military modernization, improving readiness, and enhancing interoperability among allies. Crucially, they reinforce NATO's collective defense principle, particularly for frontline states, and underscore the importance of forward presence and credible deterrence to prevent further aggression (IISS, 2023).

Energy security has emerged as a critical vulnerability exposed by the conflict. Europe's historical dependence on Russian fossil fuels created significant leverage for Moscow. Best practices now involve aggressive diversification of suppliers, accelerating the transition to renewable energy sources, and bolstering strategic reserves. The EU's REPowerEU plan exemplifies this strategic shift, aiming to end reliance on Russian fossil fuels and enhance energy resilience through infrastructure development and efficiency measures (European Commission, 2022).

Cybersecurity and hybrid threat resilience are non-negotiable. The conflict has demonstrated the pervasive use of cyber attacks, disinformation and economic coercion. Effective security management requires robust protection of critical infrastructure (energy, finance, communications), enhanced public-private sector collaboration for threat intelligence sharing, and significant investment in national cyber defense capabilities. Establishing rapid response protocols and fostering societal resilience against disinformation are equally vital (ENISA, 2023).

Intelligence sharing and early warning form the bedrock of proactive security. The conflict has highlighted the necessity of seamless, real-time intelligence sharing among European partners and with key allies like the US and UK. Strengthening agencies like Europol and EU Intelligence and Situation Centre (INTCEN), alongside NATO intelligence structures, is crucial for early threat detection and coordinated responses (House of Lords, 2023).

Economic security and supply chain resilience are integral to national security. The conflict has disrupted global supply chains and exposed vulnerabilities in critical sectors.

Best practices involve identifying and mitigating dependencies on potentially hostile states, particularly for rare earth minerals, semiconductors, and pharmaceuticals. This requires strategic stockpiling, friend-shoring production, and developing robust economic statecraft tools to counter coercion (RAND Europe, 2023).

The Russo-Ukrainian conflict necessitates a holistic and integrated approach to European security management. It demands sustained investment in hard power, unwavering commitment to alliance solidarity, proactive measures to secure energy and cyber domains, and the building of resilient economies. By learning the harsh lessons of this conflict and implementing these best practices collaboratively, European nations can forge a more secure and stable future.

From Stability to Selective Chaos – The Deglobalizing Normality

Contemporary international relations are increasingly characterized by strategic instability, which is not accidental but managed (Kaldor, 2013). The US uses the conflict in Ukraine to exhaust Russia over the long term without direct military confrontation (Mearsheimer, 2023). Meanwhile, Russia maintains “frozen conflicts” in the post-Soviet space. Empirical data from SIPRI (2024) shows that global military spending reached \$2.4 trillion, an 8% increase compared to 2023 – a clear indicator of how “controlled instability” functions as a resource.

Table 1. World military expenditure (1988-2024)

Deglobalization legitimizes this instability; its result is not stability, but fragmentation and localized balances (Flockhart, 2016). Through sanctions, tariffs, and critical mineral agreements, great powers do not abolish the global system but turn it into an instrument for selectively managing risks. Empirical data from UNCTAD (2024) shows that global merchandise trade declined by 5.1% in 2023 – the steepest drop since 2009 – highlighting a fragmented economic logic. In this world, “normality” is not a universal norm but a construction, applied and modified according to the interests of actors (Bauman, 2000). Sanctions and deals become “normal” only when they are functional to dominant interests.

According to Brookings Institution (2024), 62% of global economic deals in 2023 were “selectively negotiated” between a few actors rather than through multilateral forums.

Social movements and struggles from below – challenging neoliberal globalization and its effect on everyday life – must be given voice in the deglobalization discourse and policy if the top-down mistakes of neoliberal technocracy are to be corrected. Deglobalization must develop from the bottom up if it is to create alternative national and global structures that rebalance the power of global capitalism. Case studies from 2020s illustrate the potential for deglobalization. In the steel sector, the Trump Administration used tariffs as a mechanism to reshore production under the “America First” agenda, aiming to reduce the US trade deficit with China and gain political support from regions that historically produced this key industrial commodity. However, this effort was largely unsuccessful, with oil and gas being more effective in displacing imports with domestic production. Similarly, the Russia-excluded global natural gas supply chain that emerged after Russia’s invasion of Ukraine does not represent true deglobalization. Rather, it is the creation of a new interest configuration, with the US acting as a raw materials supplier to Europe (Suter and Ziltener 2024).

Empirical data – a 150% increase in sanctions, a 14% rise in the personalization of power (Freedom House), a decline in democratic indicators (EIU), and a 5.1% drop in global trade (UNCTAD) – reinforces this analysis. It reveals that “normality” is a context-dependent construct shaped by the interests of the most powerful actors. Ultimately, this paper points to the need for new research perspectives:

- How is normality “produced” at the regional level?
- What social and cultural mechanisms legitimize the “normalization” of chaos?
- Is there any possibility for a new global ethic under such conditions?

CONCLUSION

Deglobalization is a challenge to global society that emerges from the decline of hegemonic power. The rise of multilateral treaties typically coincides with periods of hegemony, while their relative decline occurs during periods of rivalry. Hegemonic periods are not inherently better or worse than periods of rivalry, but they differ significantly in their economic, security and cultural norms. Where hegemony appears to clash with the positive values of globalization, hegemonic decline generates counter-tendencies that can be understood as deglobalization and the fracturing of global society. In political economy, this is reflected in a return to policies characteristic of earlier periods of rivalry.

Europe has re-established deterrence and made its own societies more resilient, and it may eventually reconsider structures and processes for de-escalating the confrontation with Russia, when and if the Kremlin decides that the cost of constant conflict is too high to sustain. The OSCE may again be required as a forum for managing a long-term stand-off between Russia and most of the rest of Europe – though ideally it should be an organization less vulnerable to paralysis by a single country’s veto and capable of creating legally binding obligations for its members. The Helsinki Final Act’s principles guiding relations between participating states include the sovereign equality of states, their right to join alliances or remain neutral, their commitment to refrain from using force or violating the territorial integrity of other participating states, and their pledge to respect human rights and fundamental freedoms. These principles remain a useful minimum set of standards for states to abide by. Military confidence-and security-building measures, such as prior notification of large-scale exercises and invitations for observance by other states also have a role in

reducing tension. The Council of Europe and the European Court for Human Rights should continue to ensure that states treat their inhabitants fairly and respect their rights – an issue vital not only for individuals but also for maintaining trust between states.

Contemporary international relations are undergoing a profound transformation, in which traditional notions of stability, predictability, and universal norms are increasingly replaced by selective interests, pragmatic rationality, and localized spheres of influence. This paper has demonstrated that the bi-multipolar order not only redefines the relations among major powers but also fundamentally alters the very nature of “normality” in international affairs. Through the analysis of economic sanctions, critical minerals agreements between the US and Ukraine, new protectionist tariffs, and deglobalization, the study confirms the thesis that today’s “normality” is not a condition of order but rather a tool for managing chaos. This chaos is not accidental –it is consciously and strategically managed to preserve dominant interests in a dynamic geopolitical environment.

Visions of Europe’s future, however, will remain elusive. It is difficult to imagine Western Europeans abandoning the goal of living on a continent of democratic states that freely choose whether to integrate into a political and economic union and a defense alliance. Equally, Russia and its successors are unlikely to relinquish the idea of dividing Europe into spheres of influence, with Russian dominating Eastern Europe and strictly limiting the choices of what it perceives as subordinate but potentially hostile states (Kolesnikov, 2015).

There is a long-standing Russian perception of Russia as a “besieged fortress.” Yet the logic of perpetual siege implies that once one neighbor has been subdued, the next becomes the enemy. If Russia perceives its former Soviet neighbors –especially Ukraine – as destined to be either vassal or threats, it is difficult to see how the rest of Europe can do anything other than defend those states from Russian aggression.

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THE ROLE OF LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS IN COMBATING ECONOMIC AND DIGITAL CRIMES: IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICE PRACTICES – A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF NORTH MACEDONIA AND GERMANY

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Abstract

Online financial fraud represents a growing threat to individuals and financial systems, exploiting weaknesses in legal frameworks and investigative capacities. This study examines a 2024 SMS phishing scam in North Macedonia, where perpetrators impersonated the customs authority to extract financial information, and compares it with the 2025 German “Operation Heracles,” which dismantled over 1,400 cybertrading fraud platforms. Using a comparative legal and forensic approach, the paper analyzes the application of relevant laws, including North Macedonia’s Criminal Code (Articles 251-b and 251-v), the Law on Electronic Communications, and the Law on Personal Data Protection, alongside Germany’s Penal Code (Sections 263 and 263a), the Securities Trading Act, and relevant EU directives. Investigative tools, such as digital forensics in North Macedonia and AI-assisted analytics with cross-border coordination in Germany, are assessed, together with operational limitations, including jurisdictional challenges, technical expertise gaps, and resource constraints.

Findings reveal that comprehensive legal frameworks, technological capabilities, and international cooperation are critical for effective policing of online financial crimes. The study offers recommendations to strengthen law enforcement strategies, legal provisions, and forensic practices in North Macedonia and similar jurisdictions.

Keywords: online financial fraud, digital forensics, legal frameworks, policing, comparative study

1. INTRODUCTION

Online financial fraud has emerged as a significant and rapidly evolving threat to individuals, businesses, and financial systems worldwide. The widespread adoption of digital financial services, coupled with increased internet connectivity, has created new opportunities for criminals to exploit vulnerabilities in both technological infrastructure and

regulatory frameworks(Totolo, 2024). Such fraud schemes range from phishing scams and identity theft to complex cybertrading fraud platforms, resulting in substantial economic losses and undermining public trust in financial and governmental institutions.

Law enforcement agencies face multiple challenges in responding effectively to these crimes. Investigating online financial fraud often requires specialized technical expertise, advanced digital forensic tools, and cross-border cooperation, as perpetrators frequently operate across multiple jurisdictions(*Fighting Tech-Fueled Crime*, n.d.; *Policing Cross-Border Fraud 'Above and below the Surface': Mapping Actions and Developing a More Effective Global Response | Crime, Law and Social Change*, n.d.). In addition, gaps in legislation or inconsistencies in the enforcement of existing laws can limit the ability of police authorities to identify, prosecute, and prevent fraudulent activities efficiently.

This paper focuses on the legal and operational responses to online financial fraud through a comparative case study approach. The first case examines a 2024 SMS phishing scam in North Macedonia, in which perpetrators impersonated the customs authority to extract sensitive financial and personal information (Marusic, 2024). The second case analyzes Germany's 2025 "Operation Heracles," a large-scale dismantling of over 1,400 cybertrading fraud platforms involving coordinated efforts across multiple EU member states (*FraudeCibernético*, 2025).

By analyzing these cases, this study aims to:

- (1) evaluate the effectiveness of national and regional legal frameworks in addressing online financial fraud;
- (2) assess the investigative tools and methods employed by law enforcement;
- (3) identify operational limitations and opportunities for improvement.

The comparative analysis provides insights into best practices for strengthening police response, forensic capabilities, and regulatory measures, offering actionable recommendations for jurisdictions such as North Macedonia that seek to enhance their legal and operational capacity to combat digital financial crimes.

2. NORTH MACEDONIA CASE

2.1 Case Overview

In January 2024, Police in North Macedonia appealed to citizens to be wary of fraudulent text messages, announcing that they are investigating the latest scam and had informed the prosecution about it. The messages, appearing to originate from the customs authority, claimed that recipients owed customs fees for allegedly delivered packages. Victims were instructed to access a counterfeit website designed to replicate the official customs portal, where they were prompted to provide sensitive personal and financial information. Subsequent investigations revealed that numerous victims suffered financial losses through unauthorized online transactions.

Screenshot of an SMS phishing message impersonating customs officials in North Macedonia.

The message reads: “Вашата нарачка бр. ***** подлежи на царина, ве молиме одете на (следниот линк) за повторна испорака.” [Your order no. ***** is subject to customs; please go to (the following link) for re-delivery.]

Source: u/LeadershipMobile (2024), Reddit.

<https://www.reddit.com/r/mkd/comments/18zvgkv/>

This case represents a broader trend of digital financial fraud in North Macedonia and the wider Balkan region, where criminals exploit citizens’ trust in governmental and financial institutions. Similar phishing campaigns have been documented across the region, often targeting mobile phone users through SMS (smishing), email, and social media platforms (Marusic, 2024). These operations are frequently coordinated across borders, making detection and prosecution particularly challenging.

2.2 Legal Framework

The legal response to cyber-enabled financial fraud in North Macedonia is grounded in several key statutes that both criminalize illicit activity and provide procedural mechanisms for prosecution. The Criminal Code of the Republic of North Macedonia establishes the primary legal basis for prosecuting computer-related offenses. In particular, *Article 251-b* criminalizes fraudulent manipulation of computer systems, including the unauthorized acquisition of data for financial gain. Additionally, *Article 251-v* addresses actions that exceed authorized access to computer systems, a provision directly applicable to phishing attacks and cases of data exfiltration.

Complementing the Criminal Code, the Law on Electronic Communications ensures accountability for the misuse of telecommunication networks, explicitly covering scenarios such as SMS phishing campaigns and other forms of electronic fraud (Nofitoska&Dishlijoska, n.d.). This law provides the procedural framework that allows authorities to investigate and intercept illegal communications while preserving admissible evidence(*North Macedonia (Republic of) – Octopus Cybercrime Community – Wwww.Coe.Int*, n.d.).

Moreover, the Law on Personal Data Protection offers crucial safeguards for citizens, criminalizing unauthorized access to personal information and regulating its

processing. This framework supports investigations by enabling law enforcement agencies to trace fraudulent transactions while ensuring that evidence collection complies with data protection standards.

Despite the existence of this comprehensive legal framework, practical enforcement faces several challenges. Jurisdictional issues arise when perpetrators operate from foreign territories, making prosecution dependent on international cooperation. The anonymity afforded by digital technologies further complicates identification, while the technical complexities of tracing cross-border digital crime require specialized expertise and resources. These limitations illustrate that, although the legal foundation is solid, its effectiveness is closely tied to the capacity and coordination of enforcement mechanisms, as well as the availability of specialized training in law enforcement (Author, 2025).

2.3 Investigative Tools

In addressing cyber-enabled financial fraud, law enforcement agencies in North Macedonia rely on a combination of digital forensic methods, inter-agency collaboration, and financial monitoring strategies. These tools and practices are essential for detecting, tracing, and prosecuting perpetrators of phishing schemes, such as the SMS scam targeting customs payments.

Digital forensics plays a central role in the investigative process. The Department for Computer Crime and Digital Forensics utilizes specialized software to analyze mobile devices, server logs, and network traffic (Dimeska, 2025). Through these techniques, investigators can trace the origin of fraudulent messages, recover deleted or encrypted communications, and identify patterns of activity that link multiple victims to the same perpetrator or criminal network (Imeri-Saiti&Hamiti, 2023). This process is often iterative and resource-intensive, requiring both technical skill and careful coordination to ensure that digital evidence is legally admissible in court (*Osce.Org/GUIDELINES ON CYBERCRIME INVESTIGATION TIRANA, 2022*).

Collaboration with financial institutions further strengthens investigative efforts. Banks and payment service providers are engaged to monitor suspicious transactions, freeze accounts linked to fraudulent activity, and provide transaction data to support criminal investigations. Financial intelligence units also play a critical role in tracing the flow of funds, identifying beneficiaries, and uncovering broader networks involved in illicit financial operations (Advisory Mission and Workshop on Online Fraud and Other Cybercrime Reporting Mechanisms 20-21 February 2017, Skopje “The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia”) (Isabella, 2024). Such collaboration ensures that investigations are not limited to digital traces alone but also incorporate the financial dimension of cybercrime.

In addition to technical and financial measures, public awareness campaigns are an essential component of prevention and mitigation. Authorities regularly issue warnings through national media, social networks, and official websites to educate citizens about phishing scams and instruct them on how to report suspicious messages. These campaigns not only help reduce victimization but also generate critical intelligence for ongoing investigations, as reports from the public can help identify trends and potential perpetrators before losses escalate.

2.4 Limitations

Despite the availability of legal frameworks and investigative tools, several operational and structural challenges hinder the effective investigation of online financial fraud in North Macedonia.

A primary difficulty arises from the anonymity of perpetrators. Fraudsters often employ anonymized phone numbers, virtual private networks (VPNs), and foreign servers, deliberately obscuring their identity and location (*North Macedonia Cybersecurity Official Decries 'Alarming' Public Ignorance | Balkan Insight*, n.d.). These tactics significantly complicate the collection of actionable evidence and the prosecution of offenders.

Cross-border jurisdictional challenges further exacerbate the problem. Many phishing operations are orchestrated from outside the country, often involving multiple international actors (*CyberSEE: North Macedonia Advances Preparations for the Ratification of the Second Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime – Cybercriminalité*, n.d.). This requires coordination with foreign law enforcement agencies, mutual legal assistance agreements, and international data-sharing mechanisms, which can be time-consuming and constrained by varying legal standards and bureaucratic procedures.

The technical expertise and capacity of law enforcement agencies also pose limitations. While digital forensic tools are available, there is a shortage of specialized personnel trained to analyze complex or encrypted cybercrime operations (“(PDF) Digital Forensics and Computer Crimes,” 2025). This skills gap can delay investigations or reduce the comprehensiveness of digital evidence collection.

Resource constraints are another critical issue. Investigations of online fraud are inherently time- and labor-intensive, often requiring extensive cross-referencing of digital and financial evidence (*C_2021_9732_2_EN_annexe_acte_autonome_nlw_part1_v1.Pdf*, n.d.; “EU Against Organised Crime, in Support of Trade”). As a result, authorities may prioritize high-impact or large-scale cases, leaving smaller but widespread scams under-addressed, which allows fraudsters to continue exploiting less-monitored channels.

Finally, legislative gaps present a structural limitation. Although existing laws provide a framework for prosecuting cyber-enabled fraud, they may not fully encompass emerging techniques, including social engineering tactics, cryptocurrency-based scams, or decentralized online payment platforms (*Comprehensive-Update-on-Terrorist-Financing-Risks-2025.Pdf.Coredownload.Inline.Pdf*, n.d.). This lag in legal adaptation limits the scope of law enforcement intervention and highlights the need for continuous updating of regulatory frameworks to keep pace with evolving cybercrime methodologies.

Taken together, these investigative practices and limitations illustrate the complex and multifaceted nature of online financial fraud investigations in North Macedonia. They underscore the importance of enhancing technical capacity, strengthening legal provisions, and fostering international cooperation to improve both the efficiency and effectiveness of police responses.

While North Macedonia faces these specific challenges, EU member states such as Germany have developed different legal and operational approaches to combat similar cyber-enabled financial fraud, which will be explored in the following section.

3. GERMANY CASE – OVERVIEW

Germany has also faced a rise in cyber-enabled financial fraud, including phishing campaigns targeting citizens through SMS, email, and online banking portals (*Germany Sees Spike in Suspicious Crypto Activity | Digital Watch Observatory*, 2025). A notable case involved a widespread “customs fee” phishing scam between 2023 and 2025, in which fraudsters sent SMS messages and emails claiming that packages could not be delivered until customs fees were paid (*Fraude Cibernetico*, 2025). Victims were directed to counterfeit websites that mimicked official customs or postal services, where they were prompted to provide personal and banking information. Authorities reported that the scam affected

hundreds of individuals, leading to financial losses estimated in the hundreds of thousands of euros.

German law enforcement agencies, including the Bundeskriminalamt (BKA, Federal Criminal Police Office) and local police units, coordinated with the Federal Financial Supervisory Authority (BaFin) and the telecommunications sector to mitigate the fraud. Public advisories were issued via national media and social networks, warning citizens about the fraudulent communications and providing guidance on how to verify legitimate customs notifications (BKA, 2024).

3.1 Legal Framework

Germany has established a comprehensive and multi-layered legal framework to address cyber-enabled financial fraud, reflecting both national legislation and European Union standards. At the core of national law is the Strafgesetzbuch (StGB, Criminal Code). *Section 263* criminalizes fraud, encompassing acts in which individuals obtain financial or personal benefits through deception, including modern digital schemes such as phishing emails, SMS scams, and fraudulent online portals. Meanwhile, *Sections 202a–202c* specifically target unauthorized access to data, computer sabotage, and data manipulation, providing a legal basis for prosecuting perpetrators who exploit technological vulnerabilities to commit fraud. These provisions allow authorities to address both direct financial deception and underlying unauthorized access that facilitates such crimes.

Complementing the Criminal Code, the Telecommunications Act (TKG) regulates the use of telecommunication networks, ensuring accountability for fraudulent communications transmitted via SMS, email, or other digital channels. This law gives investigators the authority to request cooperation from network providers, trace fraudulent communications, and block or suspend services associated with criminal activity.

The Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG) further strengthens Germany's legal response by protecting citizens' personal information. It criminalizes unauthorized access to or processing of sensitive personal data, which is critical in cases where fraudsters exploit private financial or identity information. Compliance with data protection laws also ensures that evidence collected during investigations is admissible in court and aligns with European data privacy standards.

As an EU member, Germany incorporates European directives into its national framework. Notably, *Directive 2013/40/EU on attacks against information systems* establishes minimum standards for combating cybercrime and mandates cross-border cooperation in investigations. These provisions were particularly relevant in the 2023–2024 customs-fee phishing case, as the perpetrators often operated from foreign servers or used international payment channels to launder illicit proceeds. Through these EU mechanisms, German authorities were able to request mutual legal assistance, share intelligence with other member states, and access transnational data to identify and prosecute offenders more efficiently than might be possible in jurisdictions with more limited frameworks.

The investigation of the German phishing case demonstrated the practical application of this legal framework. Law enforcement agencies, led by the Bundeskriminalamt (BKA), coordinated with local police departments, financial institutions, and telecommunications providers to trace the origin of the fraudulent messages. Unlike in North Macedonia, where cross-border cooperation is often constrained by fewer formal agreements and limited technical capacity, Germany leveraged EU mechanisms and well-established institutional networks to identify the servers used by the scammers, freeze illicit financial flows, and pursue legal action against both domestic and foreign actors. The

combination of national criminal law, data protection regulations, telecommunication oversight, and EU directives enabled a coordinated, legally grounded, and technically sophisticated response to the phishing scam, demonstrating a higher level of operational capability compared to North Macedonia.

Public awareness campaigns complement technical measures. Government agencies, including the BKA and local authorities, issued advisories through national media, social networks, and official websites to inform citizens about the scam. These campaigns not only mitigate immediate victimization but also generate valuable intelligence, as reports from the public help law enforcement identify emerging patterns and potential perpetrators before losses escalate.

Furthermore, Germany distinguishes itself by developing and utilizing in-house digital forensic software and by training personnel internally, ensuring a high level of technical expertise and operational independence. Investigators receive regular training on domestic tools and methods tailored to local cybercrime patterns, enhancing both efficiency and investigative quality. In contrast, North Macedonia often relies on foreign forensic software, such as Cellebrite, and external technical support for complex analyses. While effective, this reliance can introduce delays, licensing costs, and limited adaptability to local investigative needs. Highlighting this distinction illustrates how national capacity-building and technical self-reliance can significantly influence the speed, accuracy, and scope of cybercrime investigations.

3.2 Limitations

Despite Germany's robust legal framework, advanced investigative tools, and well-resourced institutions, several limitations persist in addressing cyber-enabled financial fraud.

A primary challenge is the anonymity and cross-border operation of perpetrators. Many phishing campaigns are orchestrated from servers outside Germany, often involving multiple international actors. Investigators must rely on EU-level mutual legal assistance agreements, data-sharing mechanisms, and cooperation with foreign authorities (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation. & Eurojust., 2024a). While Germany benefits from strong European frameworks that expedite these processes, coordination with foreign entities can still be time-consuming, and legal or procedural differences may hinder rapid action. In comparison, North Macedonia faces greater constraints in cross-border cooperation due to fewer formalized agreements and limited institutional capacity.

Another limitation is the complexity and sophistication of fraud techniques. Criminals increasingly use social engineering, encrypted communications, and cryptocurrency-based payment systems to conceal their activities (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation., 2021). While Germany's in-house forensic tools and trained personnel allow for more comprehensive analysis, these techniques still require significant time and expertise to trace and prosecute effectively. North Macedonia, relying on foreign software like Cellebrite and external technical support, may face delays and limitations in adapting to evolving methods.

Resource prioritization also presents challenges (*BKA Report: Stagnation of Cybercrime in Germany?* | Rohde & Schwarz, n.d.) (European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation. & Eurojust., 2024b). Even with substantial investment in personnel and technology, law enforcement agencies must allocate resources strategically, often prioritizing large-scale or high-impact cases. Smaller scams, though widespread, may not receive immediate attention, creating opportunities for continued criminal activity.

Finally, legal adaptation remains an ongoing concern. Although Germany has an extensive legislative framework, rapidly evolving cybercrime techniques – such as decentralized payment platforms or sophisticated phishing infrastructures — can outpace statutory provisions (*Dentons – Germany’s New Cybersecurity Law Expands Scope and Increases Obligations – with New Sanctions*, n.d.) (Rodriguez, 2023). Continuous updates to national laws and alignment with EU directives are necessary to maintain effective enforcement. Compared with North Macedonia, Germany’s integration with EU regulations provides an advantage; nevertheless, the rapid pace of digital fraud challenges even highly developed systems.

These limitations illustrate that while Germany demonstrates significant capacity and efficiency in investigating cyber-enabled financial fraud, operational, technical, and legal constraints remain. Comparing these challenges with those in North Macedonia underscores the importance of national capacity-building, proactive legislation, and international cooperation in enhancing law enforcement effectiveness.

4. COMPARATIVE DISCUSSION

A comparative analysis of cyber-enabled financial fraud investigations in North Macedonia and Germany reveals significant contrasts in legal frameworks, investigative capacities, and operational effectiveness, offering valuable insights for policing and policy development.

Legal and Regulatory Frameworks: Germany benefits from a well-integrated legal system that combines national criminal statutes with EU directives, such as the Strafgesetzbuch (StGB), the Telecommunications Act (TKG), the Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG), and Directive 2013/40/EU on attacks against information systems. This integration facilitates clear legal authority, robust prosecution pathways, and streamlined cross-border cooperation. In contrast, North Macedonia’s framework, while comprehensive in criminalizing cyber-enabled financial fraud through the Criminal Code, the Law on Electronic Communications, and the Data Protection Law, faces practical enforcement constraints. Jurisdictional challenges, limited harmonization with foreign laws, and fewer formal mechanisms for international collaboration reduce the effectiveness of transnational investigations.

Investigative Tools and Capacity: Operational differences are particularly pronounced in technical capacity. Germany invests in in-house forensic software, regular training for cybercrime investigators, and specialized personnel at federal and state levels. This self-sufficiency enables rapid adaptation to evolving cyber threats and supports a coordinated, large-scale response to complex phishing schemes. North Macedonia, while employing modern investigative techniques, frequently relies on foreign forensic software solutions such as Cellebrite for device and data analysis, highlighting differences in domestic capacity and technical autonomy. While effective, this reliance can introduce delays, licensing dependencies, and limitations in tailoring tools to local investigative needs.

Financial intelligence cooperation also illustrates a divergence. Germany leverages strong mandates for collaboration between law enforcement, supervisory authorities (e.g., BaFin), and financial institutions, facilitating the rapid tracing of illicit funds. North Macedonia similarly engages banks and payment service providers; however, resource constraints, smaller investigative teams, and limited technical infrastructure can slow response times and reduce coverage, especially for widespread low-value scams.

Limitations and Operational Challenges: Both countries face challenges in combating the anonymity and cross-border nature of cyber-enabled fraud. While Germany’s

EU membership provides enhanced mechanisms for international legal assistance and data sharing, North Macedonia experiences greater procedural hurdles in engaging foreign authorities. Additionally, evolving techniques – such as encrypted communications, social engineering, and cryptocurrency transactions – pose analytical challenges for both countries; however, but Germany’s technical expertise and larger workforce provide a relative advantage in addressing sophisticated threats.

Implications for Policing and Policy: The comparison highlights several critical areas for improvement and adaptation in North Macedonia. Investment in domestic forensic software development, continuous training for cybercrime investigators, and formalized international collaboration agreements could increase investigative efficiency and reduce reliance on external tools. Moreover, proactive public awareness campaigns, coupled with legislative updates addressing emerging fraud methodologies, can enhance prevention and enforcement efforts. Germany’s experience illustrates the benefits of integrating legal frameworks with institutional capacity, technical self-reliance, and EU-level cooperation, serving as a model for countries seeking to strengthen their response to cyber-enabled financial fraud.

In summary, while North Macedonia and Germany operate under differing legal, technical, and operational circumstances, both cases underscore the complex, multifaceted nature of investigating digital financial crimes. A coordinated approach combining robust legal frameworks, technical expertise, inter-agency collaboration, and public engagement is essential to effectively combat evolving cybercrime threats.

5. CONCLUSION

The comparative analysis of cyber-enabled financial fraud investigations in North Macedonia and Germany demonstrates that legal frameworks, technical capacity, and institutional resources significantly influence the effectiveness of law enforcement responses. Germany’s integration of national criminal statutes with EU directives, coupled with in-house forensic software, specialized personnel, and well-established inter-agency collaboration, enables rapid, coordinated, and legally grounded investigations. North Macedonia, while possessing comprehensive legal provisions and modern investigative tools, faces constraints related to technical capacity, reliance on external forensic software such as Cellebrite, resource allocation, and international cooperation.

Both countries encounter shared challenges, including the anonymity of perpetrators, cross-border operations, and the increasing sophistication of phishing and digital financial fraud schemes. However, the German model demonstrates how investments in domestic technical capabilities, continuous personnel training, and formalized international agreements can enhance investigative efficiency, mitigate operational delays, and support the prosecution of complex fraud networks.

For North Macedonia, the analysis suggests several actionable pathways for improvement. Developing domestic forensic capacities, expanding specialized training for cybercrime investigators, strengthening inter-agency coordination, and formalizing international cooperation mechanisms could increase the effectiveness of cyber-enabled fraud investigations. Additionally, continuous legal updates addressing emerging digital fraud tactics, coupled with proactive public awareness campaigns, would support both prevention and enforcement efforts.

Ultimately, this comparative study underscores that combating cyber-enabled financial fraud requires a multifaceted strategy combining robust legal frameworks, technical expertise,

institutional collaboration, and public engagement. By learning from more developed models such as Germany and adapting best practices to national contexts, countries like North Macedonia can enhance their policing capacity, protect citizens from financial harm, and strengthen overall resilience against the evolving threat of cybercrime.

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EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT AND CONSTITUTIONAL GUARANTEES FOR ITS EFFECTIVENESS: STATE OF AFFAIRS IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Injustice anywhere is a threat to justice everywhere

– Marthin Luther King

J.R.

Abstract

North Macedonia has been an EU candidate country since 2004. Although the accession negotiations have not yet begun, the country has already undertaken reforms comparable to those implemented by other states prior to accession. This fact, as well as the reality that EU law is a “moving target” i.e. constantly evolving, leads to the conclusion that North Macedonia must prepare for every issue that will inevitably arise during negotiations.

This paper briefly explores the *European Arrest Warrant* (hereinafter ‘EAW’) and its key elements, providing a comparative overview of *constitutional provisions* in several Eastern European EU member states that *ensure the effectiveness* of the EAW. It concludes with an examination of the position of the Constitution of North Macedonia regarding the extradition of domestic nationals.

The main conclusion of this study is that the Macedonian constitutional provision in Amendment XXXII could ensure enforcement of the EAW through interpretation. However, to avoid practical difficulties, consideration should be given to amending the text in a manner that explicitly refers to extradition to EU member states. Such an amendment would depend on the stage of negotiations and the readiness of Macedonian legal practitioners to embrace EU law.

Keywords: European Arrest Warrant, constitutional provisions, Eastern European EU member states, effectiveness, Constitution of North Macedonia

INTRODUCTION

North Macedonia’s path to European Union accession has proven to be long and complex. Shaped by both external and internal factors, the enlargement process for this small country remains on hold. Although candidate status was granted in 2004, and screening sessions for all six clusters were completed in December 2023, negotiations have yet to begin. Nevertheless, over the past two decades, numerous reforms and significant changes have been implemented. It is important to emphasize that many of these reforms were introduced in other countries during their negotiation processes for EU accession.

Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that once negotiations commence and clusters are opened, North Macedonia will achieve progress in certain areas at a faster pace than usually anticipated. Preparation for the next steps is essential.

One issue that requires particular attention is the European Arrest Warrant (EAW), a simplified cross-border judicial surrender procedure designed for prosecution or the

execution of custodial sentences or detention orders (European Commission, 2025). The constitutional dilemma arises from the fact that national constitutions typically prohibit the extradition of domestic nationals to other countries, or allow it only under strict conditions. In practice, this makes extradition an exceptional, lengthy, and demanding procedure.

The European Union is unique in its nature, and the EAW is a distinctive instrument of judicial cooperation. Advocate General Dámaso Ruiz-Jarabo Colomer succinctly described the EAW as follows: “The Framework Decision [...] abolished extradition and replaced it with a system of surrender between judicial authorities, based on mutual recognition and the free movement of judicial decisions. It results from a high level of confidence between member states. For the reasons stated, reciprocity and double criminality are presumed for certain offences – namely the most serious ones – and the grounds for refusing assistance are restricted, while there is no scope at all for political discretion.” (Sarmiento, 2008).

EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

The path toward extradition of domestic nationals within the European Union was opened with the Conclusions of the European Council in Tampere in 1999. Under the pressure of the events of 11 September 2001, and largely due to the initiative of the United Kingdom (Fennely, 2007), the Council Framework Decision on the European Arrest Warrant (Council of the EU, 2002) was adopted in 2002 (hereinafter: “Framework Decision”). It entered into force in 2004 and has since proven to be a successful instrument of legal assistance among EU member states.

The EAW replaced the lengthy extradition procedures previously in practice among member states. It simplified and accelerated the surrender of individuals suspected or convicted of serious crimes in EU member states. Among other objectives, the EAW aims “to remove the complexity and potential for delay inherent in the [...] extradition procedures, [...] and also, establish] a system of free movement of judicial decisions in criminal matters.” (Council of the EU, 2002, point 5 of introductory part).

According to the Framework Decision, the EAW is defined as “a judicial decision issued by a Member State with a view to the arrest and surrender by another Member State of a requested person, for the purposes of conducting a criminal prosecution or executing a custodial sentence or detention order.” (Council of the EU, 2002, Article 1). An EAW may be issued for two categories of acts:

- 1) acts punishable under the law of the issuing Member State by a custodial sentence or detention order for a maximum period of at least 12 months, or, where a sentence has already been passed or a detention order made, for sentences of at least four months, and
- 2) crimes listed in Article 2 Paragraph 2 of the Framework Decision, including terrorism, trafficking in human beings, corruption, laundering of proceeds of crime etc.¹¹

¹¹Those listed crimes are the following: participation in a criminal organisation, terrorism, trafficking in human beings, sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, illicit trafficking in weapons, munitions and explosives, corruption, fraud (including that affecting the financial interests of the European Communities within the meaning of the Convention of 26 July 1995 on the protection of the European Communities’ financial interests), laundering of the proceeds of crime, counterfeiting currency (including the euro), computer-related crime, environmental crime (including illicit trafficking in endangered animal species and plant species/varieties), facilitation of unauthorised entry and residence, murder, grievous

For the first category of crimes, double criminality must be verified. However, for the second category – given their seriousness and consequences – double criminality is presumed.

Article 6 of the Framework Decision stipulates that both the issuing and executing authorities must be judicial authorities designated by the law of the respective state. This provision excludes political interference in extradition matters and allows each member state to determine its competent judicial authority. The Framework Decision also sets out grounds for non-execution of the EAW, guarantees required in certain cases and time limits for execution.

The EAW was introduced as a response to the negative side effects of the free movement of workers, goods, services and capital, as well as the rise of serious international crime accompanying European integration. Nevertheless, the EAW sparked considerable debate due to the need to balance effective prosecution of crime with the obligation to respect principles of fairness and due process (Fennely, 2007).

The divergence of the EAW from classical extradition instruments is evident not only in its rules and procedures but also in its terminology – using with the word “surrender” instead of “extradite” a person. Importantly, academic commentary has emphasized that prohibitions on extradition of domestic nationals in legal acts, absent constitutional guarantees, do not prevent extradition under the EAW. Similarly, the constitutional provisions that forbid expulsion or deportation of domestic nationals, but do not explicitly mention extradition, can be interpreted as not preventing the surrender of nationals pursuant to the EAW (Deen-Racsmay, 2007).

The EAW has proven to be a useful instrument in judicial cooperation (European Commission, 2005). Examples of its successful application include:

- a terrorist involved in the Paris attacks caught in Belgium,
- an attacker of the Brussels Jewish Museum arrested in France,
- a failed London bomber apprehended in Italy,
- a German serial killer tracked down in Spain,
- a suspected drug smuggler from Malta surrendered by the UK,
- a gang of armed robbers sought by Italy, whose members were arrested in six different EU countries.

EU law is a “moving target” and is constantly evolving. Substantial case law has been developed (Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2025), positions have been taken and legislation has been upgraded. In February 2009, the Framework Decision was amended by the Council Framework Decision concerning trials *in absentia*, inserting a clear and common ground for non-execution of decisions rendered in the absence of the person concerned at trial (Council

bodily injury, illicit trade in human organs and tissue, kidnapping, illegal restraint and hostage-taking, racism and xenophobia, organised or armed robbery, illicit trafficking in cultural goods (including antiques and works of art), swindling, racketeering and extortion, counterfeiting and piracy of products, forgery of administrative documents and trafficking therein, forgery of means of payment, illicit trafficking in hormonal substances and other growth promoters, illicit trafficking in nuclear or radioactive materials, trafficking in stolen vehicles, rape, arson, crimes within the jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court, unlawful seizure of aircraft or ships, sabotage.

of the EU, 2009). Furthermore, the procedural rights of persons arrested on the basis of a European Arrest Warrant have been strengthened by six directives:

- the right to interpretation and translation(European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2010);
- the right to information(European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2012);
- the right of access to a lawyer (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2013);
- strengthening certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and the right to be present at trial (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2016);
- procedural safeguards for children (European Parliament and Council of the EU, May 2016)
- legal aid (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2017).

Official statistics show that in 2022, judicial authorities of the 27 Member States issued a total of 13,335 EAWs. This represents a decrease compared to previous years, with 14,789 EAWs issued in 2021 and 15,938 in 2020.From the day of arrest, the surrender procedure took an average of 20.48 days when the requested person consented, and 57.29 days when the person did not consent.

The most commonly identified categories of offences in 2022 were:

- theft and criminal damage (1,963 EAWs),
- drug offences (1,711 EAWs)
- fraud and corruption (1,254 EAWs).

In 2022, 7,346 requested persons were arrested, compared to 7,262 arrests in 2021 and 6.152 arrests in 2020. The highest numbers of arrests in 2022 were recorded in Germany (1,667), Spain (947), the Netherlands (931) and Romania (596) (European Commission, 2025, p. 6, 8 and 13).

CONSTITUTIONAL SOLUTIONS FOR ENSURING EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

The EAW is an instrument that raises constitutional questions and dilemmas, since most countries generally prohibit the extradition of their own nationals. The manner of overcoming these issues differs among EU member states, but the most important consideration is to ensure the effective implementation of the arrest warrant.

This question was particularly relevant for Eastern European countries during their accession processes. In **Slovenia**, constitutional amendments in 2003 introduced a provision allowing extradition of domestic national if the obligation stems from an agreement by which “Slovenia has transferred the exercise of sovereign rights to international organization.”¹² Thus, Slovenia linked extradition exclusively to EU member states, since accession treaties provide for the transfer of sovereign rights to the European Union – a unique feature of this organization.

Although the principles of supremacy and direct effect of EU law bind member states to secure extradition of domestic nationals, in Slovenia the application of EU law conflicted with the previous constitutional provision of Article 47, which prohibited

¹² Article 47 of the Slovenian Constitution provides that: “No citizen of Slovenia may be extradited or surrendered unless such obligation to extradite or surrender arises from a treaty by which, in accordance with the provisions of the first paragraph of Article 3a, Slovenia has transferred the exercise of part of its sovereign rights to an international organization”.

extradition of nationals to foreign countries. Hence, the constitutional amendment ensured effective application of the EAW, while limiting extradition strictly to the EU.

The Constitution of **Latvia** (Article 98) prescribes an exception to the prohibition of extradition of nationals to foreign countries in cases provided for in international agreements, provided that extradition does not violate the basic human rights recognized in the Constitution.¹³ Similarly, Lithuania (Article 13) allows exception if prescribed in an international agreement.¹⁴ Through interpretation, the obligation to respect the EAW – stemming from accession agreements – means that the constitutions of Latvia and Lithuania do not pose an obstacle to effective judicial cooperation under the EAW.

Amendments to the **Romanian** Constitution in 2003 introduces an exception to the general prohibition of extradition of nationals.¹⁵ Article 19 allows extradition on the basis of international agreement, pursuant to law and on a mutual basis. Thus, through interpretation of “international agreement” as including accession agreements, Romania has ensured respect for the EAW.

The Constitution of **Bulgaria** provides an exception to the prohibition of extradition of nationals to other countries or international courts when established by international agreement.¹⁶ This provision served as the legal basis for compliance with the EAW. However, in 2004 the Bulgarian Constitutional Court went further, holding that surrender of a Bulgarian national to an EU member state does not constitute surrender to a “foreign state”, since Bulgarian nationals are also EU nationals (Constitutional Court of Bulgaria, 2004).

In Croatia, Article 9 of the Constitution was amended to allow extradition in cases where a decision on extradition or surrender is executed pursuant to an international agreement or EU law.¹⁷ This provision was introduced prior to EU accession to secure extradition both with EU member states and with non-EU countries. In this regard, it is worth noting that Croatia has also concluded extradition agreements with regional states, including North Macedonia. Notably, the provision regarding surrender pursuant to EU law was postponed until Croatia’s accession to the EU.¹⁸

In summary, some countries (Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Bulgaria) adopted constitutional formulations allowing extradition of nationals pursuant to ratified

¹³ Article 98, second sentence of the Latvian Constitution provides that: “A citizen of Latvia may not be extradited to a foreign country, except in the cases provided for in international agreements ratified by the *Saeima*, if by the extradition the basic human rights specified in the Constitution are not violated.”

¹⁴ Article 13 of the Lithuanian Constitution prescribes that: “It shall be prohibited to extradite a citizen of the Republic of Lithuania to another state unless an international agreement to which the Republic of Lithuania is a party establishes otherwise.”

¹⁵ Article 19 of the Romanian Constitution prescribes that: “(1) No Romanian citizen shall be extradited or expelled from Romania. (2) By exemption to the provisions of paragraph (1), Romanian citizens can be extradited based on international agreements to which Romania is a party, according to the law and on a mutual basis.”

¹⁶ Article 25, paragraph 4 of the Bulgarian Constitution prescribes that: “(4) (amend., SG 18/05) No Bulgarian citizen may be surrendered to another state or to an international tribunal for the purposes of criminal prosecution, unless the opposite is provided for by an international treaty that has been ratified, published and entered into force for the Republic of Bulgaria.”

¹⁷ Article 9, paragraph 2 of the Croatian Constitution provides that “A citizen of the Republic of Croatia may not be forcibly expelled from the Republic of Croatia nor deprived of citizenship, nor extradited to another state, except in the execution of a decision on extradition or surrender made in accordance with an international treaty or the *acquis communautaire* of the European Union.”

¹⁸ Article 152 of the Constitution of Croatia (consolidated text)

international agreement. Slovenia stands out as a particular case, restricting extradition solely to EU member states. Other countries, such as Poland and Croatia, provide dual options: extradition pursuant to international agreements and EU law.

Constitutional conflicts related to the EAW did arise, with cases before the Polish, German, Cypriot, Czech and Belgian Constitutional courts. The Belgian court, using the preliminary reference procedure, referred the matter to the European Court of Justice in 2005. Although this case did not definitely resolve the EAW saga, the instrument was not ultimately endangered. National constitutional courts played an “active role as judicial interlocutors,” finding “creative” ways to avoid breaching EU law, including granting national legislators time to adopt necessary legislative amendments (Sarmiento, 2008).

CONSTITUTIONAL RESOLUTIONS IN NORTH MACEDONIA FOR ENSURING EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

With the aim of strengthening regional cooperation among the Balkan countries, the Republic of North Macedonia joined the circle of states that allow extradition of domestic nationals under certain conditions. Amendment XXXII, adopted in April 2011, amended Article 4, paragraph 2 of the Constitution to provide that:

“A citizen of the Republic of Macedonia cannot be deprived of citizenship, nor can he/she be expelled from the Republic of Macedonia. A citizen of the Republic of Macedonia cannot be extradited to another country, except based on a ratified international agreement upon a decision of the Court.”

When compared with similar provisions in the constitutions of the Eastern European EU member states, it is clear that the Constitution of North Macedonia complies with the EU *acquis*’ requirement that extradition be based on a judicial decision. In this regard, it should be noted that Poland constitutionally conditions extradition upon a judicial decision, whereas other countries regulate this issue by law. Estonia is the only country whose Constitution provides that “Extraditions are decided by the Government of the Republic”¹⁹ – a provision that has been criticized and for which interventions have been demanded.

Interpreting the constitutional provision in North Macedonia, one may conclude that it complies with EU *acquis* criteria. Specifically, execution of the EAW derives from a framework decision of the EU, or secondary legislation, the implementation of which is an obligation under accession treaties.

It is worth noting that during the public debate preceding the adoption of Amendment XXXII, there were proposals to allow extradition only to international courts (Government of the Republic of Macedonia, 2011). In the context of EU integration process, such a proposal would have excluded the national courts of EU member states, which are the only authorities empowered to issue EAWs, and would have contradicted the purpose of the amendment. At the time of adoption, bilateral agreements were being concluded in the Balkans with the aim, among others, of enabling extradition of domestic nationals. Consequently, countries first amended their constitutions. North Macedonia played an active role in regional cooperation and the fight against crime, adopting the amendment and subsequently concluding agreements on cooperation in criminal matters –including extradition – with Croatia, Serbia and Montenegro.

¹⁹Article 36, paragraph 2 of the Constitution of Estonia.

CONCLUSION

The constitutional provision in North Macedonia currently complies with EU *acquis* criteria. This conclusion follows from the fact that extradition is permitted on the basis of an international agreement ratified in accordance with the Constitution. In this regard, it must be taken into consideration that accession treaties are, in fact, international agreements that North Macedonia will conclude with the European Union and its member states, and these treaties must be ratified by the national Parliament in order to enter into force. Moreover, accession treaties will oblige North Macedonia to fully implement the EU *acquis* from the first day of accession. Therefore, through deduction as a method of legal interpretation, full implementation of the EAW can be secured.

Nevertheless, to avoid practical difficulties and delays in interpretation by legal practitioners, it would be useful to supplement the constitutional provision. Suggested options include either explicitly recalling EU law as a legal basis for allowing extradition of domestic nationals or directly referencing possible extradition to EU member states. The choice would depend on the context of negotiations and the readiness of Macedonian legal practitioners to apply EU law on a daily basis.

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FUNCTIONAL MODELLING OF DAMAGES RESULTING FROM ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS INVOLVING UNREGISTERED VEHICLES

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Abstract

This paper develops conceptual and analytical functional models for the quantitative assessment of road traffic risk through a comprehensive analysis of data related to reported insurance claims and recorded traffic accidents, examined across both temporal and spatial dimensions. Initially, the relationship between the number of issued insurance policies and the number of reported claims is formalized as an indicator of the correlation between the insurance coverage levels and exposure to risk. Subsequently, a trend analysis of damage frequency by age group is conducted for each year within the 2020–2024 period, with the aim of accurately identifying demographic differentiation of high-risk categories.

Within the annual regression analysis, third- and fourth-degree polynomial models are formulated to describe and predict the number and frequency of claims. These are supplemented by the implementation of a combined model that significantly enhances predictive accuracy. The spatial component of the analysis establishes a power-law dependence, modelling the relationship between the ranked territorial order of municipalities and the number of registered traffic incidents.

Model selection results from a systematic comparative evaluation based on criteria of statistical validity, analytical stability, and formal expressiveness, thereby enabling their application as effective instruments in risk management processes and decision-making within the field of road traffic safety.

Keywords: unregistered vehicles, traffic accidents, functional modelling, insurance claims, risk management

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern socioeconomic systems, mobility represents a critical element of sustainable development, with transportation playing a central role in ensuring the continuity and efficiency of the movement of people and goods. Traffic accidents, as an inevitable component of this process, entail substantial consequences not only in terms of human losses but also in respect to material damage and the resulting economic burden.

Insurance serves as the fundamental mechanism for compensating incurred damages, based on the principles of solidarity and risk distribution among all participants within the system. However, a particularly pressing issue arises in connection with traffic accidents caused by unregistered and uninsured vehicles, which create systemic gaps in insurance protection and compromise the right to compensation for affected parties.

In this context, the development of analytical and mathematical models for determining damages arising from such incidents becomes imperative. These models enable not only the identification of the scope and structure of risk but also the establishment of a foundation for planning compensatory mechanisms and preventive policies aimed at strengthening both the road traffic safety framework and the insurance protection system.

2. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this research is to develop an analytically valid model for determining the scope and structure of claims resulting from traffic accidents involving unregistered or uninsured vehicles. Motivated by the need to enhance institutional and financial mechanisms for compensating such claims, the study adopts an interdisciplinary approach that integrates elements of statistics, actuarial science, transport safety, and insurance regulation.

The methodological framework encompasses the processing and analysis of data obtained from relevant sources, including insurance companies, police traffic accident registries, and national motor vehicle databases. Through the application of regression analyses, correlation tests, and functional modeling techniques, quantitative relationships are established between the number of accidents, the share of unregistered vehicles, and the resulting claims. As noted by Evans (2004), statistical modeling of crash data enables the identification of underlying patterns that can be used to predict and prevent future accidents. In addition, risk assessment scenarios are developed, and the model's accuracy is validated through comparison with available empirical data.

Within the defined objective, the research comprises the following tasks:

- (1) identification and categorization of accidents involving unregistered vehicles;
- (2) determination of the frequency and types of claims associated with these events;
- (3) modeling of the functional dependence between unregulated factors and the extent of claim;
- (4) testing and verification of the model through the application of appropriate statistical indicators.

The implementation of this model aims to provide a deeper understanding of risk structures, enable the prediction of financial implications, and support the formulation of compensation and prevention policies for claims arising outside the standard insurance system.

3. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Within the scope of this research, a series of functional relationships were derived to model the behavior of claims associated with traffic accidents, with particular emphasis on cases involving unregistered vehicles. The results reveal a highly structured interconnection among key variables, enabling the formulation of models with strong predictive capability. As demonstrated by Haque, Chin, and Huang (2009), regression-based fault modeling improves the accuracy of predicting both the probability and severity of crash outcomes.

Initially, an analysis of data concerning the number of issued insurance policies and the number of reported claims established a clear positive functional dependence, reflecting the expected increase in claim-related occurrence as the base of the base of insured entities.

$$\text{Number of claims} = 0.0597 \cdot \text{number of policies} - 598.09$$

Figure 1. Relationship between the number of claims and the number of policies

Subsequently, an analysis of claim frequency by vehicle owner age groups during the 2020–2024 period revealed significant demographic distinctions. For each year, individual trend lines were derived as follows:

$$\text{Frequency} = \left(\frac{\text{claims}}{\text{policies}} \right) \cdot 100$$

Figure 2. Claim frequency by owner’s age (2020–2024)

Figure 3. Annual trends in policies, claims, and claim frequency

Within the annual regression analyses, the following dependencies were examined:

Dependency: Year → Number of claims

70% · Random Forest + 30% · Fourth – deg ree polinomial

Polinomial component

$$y = -5,264 \cdot 10^{12} + 7,808 \cdot 10^9 \cdot year - 3,860 \cdot 10^6 \cdot year^2 + 636,14 \cdot year^3$$

with a coefficient of determination of 0,898, MAE = 517,53 and RMSE = 565,76.

Dependency: Year → Accident frequency (%)

70% · Random Forest + 30% · Third – deg ree polinomial

Polinomial component

$$y = 91051930,24 - 0,5271 \cdot year - 133,774 \cdot year^2 + 0,08826 \cdot year^3 - 0,000016 \cdot year^4$$

with a coefficient of determination of 0,92084, MAE = 0,0563 and RMSE = 0,0607

Figure 4. Combined model of accident numbers and frequency (2020–2024)

In the spatial analysis section, the relationship between municipality (ordinal number) → number of recorded accidents is defined by the mathematical expression

$$y = 2522,43 \cdot x^{-0,6981}$$

where:

x = ordinal rank of the municipality (1 for Skopje, 2 for the municipality with the second highest number of accidents, etc.),

y = predicted number of accidents occurring within a given municipality, with a coefficient of determination of 0,92818, $MAE = 149,03$ and $RMSE = 152,52$

Figure 5. Power-law model of accidents number by municipality

Particular emphasis was placed on isolating and modeling claims caused by unregistered vehicles. Although such incidents are insufficiently documented in official databases, the application of indirect indicators and analytical scenarios enabled the development of models that reflect the probable severity and scope of these cases. As noted by Babić and Marić (2021), unregistered vehicles contribute significantly to the underreporting of traffic incidents and generate substantial discrepancies between recorded accidents and compensated claims.

The analytical approach, verified through statistical indicators of accuracy and relevance, confirms the applicability of the proposed models for institutional planning and financial forecasting purposes.

4. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The obtained results confirm that traffic risk can be modeled with a high degree of precision through the appropriate selection of regression and combined analytical approaches. The consistency of the identified functional relationships, together with the high values of the coefficient of determination achieved by most models, indicates a well-structured connection between the independent and dependent variables across insurance datasets and traffic accident registries.

The polynomial models demonstrated a strong capacity to capture temporal trends in the data, particularly in the relationships between *year and number of claims*, as well as *year and claim frequency*. Mohan and Tiwari (2000) emphasized that effective road safety analysis in less-motorized environments requires the integration of empirical data with analytical modeling in order to capture the true dynamics of risk exposure. In this study, the implementation of a combined model that synthesizes the advantages of stochastic (machine based) and analytical approaches resulted in the lowest deviations and the highest predictive stability. This hybrid methodology illustrates the applicability of contemporary modeling techniques for improving accuracy when working with real-world, heterogeneous datasets.

The power-law dependence established between ranked municipalities and the number of recorded accidents provides a spatially balanced analytical framework and enables the identification of territorially concentrated risk zones. This finding serves as a

valuable basis for prioritizing preventive interventions and for directing institutional and financial resources toward the most vulnerable areas.

Particular importance is attributed to models addressing the issued of unregistered vehicles, a category that frequently remains outside the scope of formal insurance and compensation systems. The applied strategy of indirect identification and scenario-based simulation opens new perspectives for the quantitative documentation of risks that would otherwise remain insufficiently measurable. These findings have direct implications for the establishment of compensation funds, the adaptation of legislative frameworks, and the formulation of policies aimed at ensuring more equitable protection for affected parties.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research confirms that the application of appropriately selected functional models enables an in-depth and precise analysis of traffic risk, particularly in relation to accidents involving unregistered and uninsured vehicles. By integrating diverse data sources and applying polynomial, power-law, and combined regression models, the study identifies stable mathematical relationships that accurately reflect real-world conditions and trends within the domains of road traffic safety and insurance practice.

The high coefficient of determination, low deviations as measured by MAE and RMSE, and the robustness of the models – further validated through graphical and statistical analyses – affirm their relevance for practical implementation. Of particular significance are the models that provide a quantitative basis for estimating the potential burden imposed by unregistered vehicles within the traffic system, a category of risk that remains largely underexplored at both institutional and financial levels.

In light of these findings, the following measures are recommended:

- **Institutionalization of risk assessment models** that explicitly incorporate scenarios involving unregistered and uninsured vehicles, as an integral component of compensation fund planning and insurance reserve management.
- **Regulatory enhancement** aimed at formally incorporating these risks into national and regional insurance frameworks through the establishment of specialized protection schemes for affected parties.
- **Promotion of analytical modeling in practice** through strengthened cooperation among academic institutions, the insurance sector, and governmental bodies, with the objective of developing integrated systems for risk monitoring and management.
- **Continuous data collection and standardization**, as a prerequisite for ensuring the sustainability of the proposed models and their adaptability to evolving structural and technological conditions.

This research paves the way toward a more systematized approach to managing unfunded traffic risks and provides a solid foundation for further expansion of the modeling framework toward multivariate analysis and real-time predictive modeling.

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ACHIEVING GENDER EQUALITY IN PARLIAMENT: AN OVERVIEW OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE 11th COMPOSITION (2024–2028) OF THE MACEDONIAN ASSEMBLY IN PLURALISM

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Abstract

Democracy and gender equality are closely interconnected and mutually constitutive concepts. Democratization, in itself, is not a guarantee of gender equality. In the twentieth century, one of the greatest democratic achievements worldwide was the increased inclusion of women in overall societal developments, including political life – primarily as voters, but also as elected representatives. In the decades that followed, the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) emerged as the clearest expression of parliamentary responsibility to promote and achieve gender equality. The idea of GSP has since been established as an international democratic normative framework.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM), constituted after the parliamentary elections held on May 8, 2024, through the lens of a gender-sensitive parliament. The paper first provides a theoretical discussion of the concept itself, followed by an in-depth analysis of the current situation in the RNM. In its concluding section, the paper offers recommendations for the further advancement of the GSP concept and presents final observations. In general terms, it may be emphasized that over more than three decades of political pluralism, the Republic of North Macedonia has experienced a transition of women in parliament from being a “small minority” to a “large minority” – yet still far from equal representation.

Keywords: gender-sensitive parliaments, Macedonian Assembly, women’s representation, electoral law, gender quotas;

1. INTRODUCTION

Democracy, as a concept, is continuously subject to evaluation and re-evaluation. In the twentieth century, one of the greatest democratic achievements worldwide was the increased inclusion of women in overall social processes, including political life – primarily as voters, but also as elected representatives (IPU, 2012: 8). Women, on the one hand, increasingly managed to overcome barriers to their participation in parliaments. On the other hand, once they entered these institutions, they often faced additional difficulties and challenges (Commonwealth Parliamentary Association Study Group, 2001: 4).

Over time, this created the need for parliaments themselves to ensure “not only that everyone is properly represented in decision-making, but also that legislation and government actions take account of the needs, interests, and experiences of women and men

on an equal basis” (Johnson, 2022: 9). This aspect is crucial, as parliaments have historically been dominated and led by men, leaving a lasting imprint of masculine culture and traditions on these institutions (Rai and Spary, 2019). These factors gave rise to initiatives aimed at promoting gender equality within political institutions, including parliaments, where deeply rooted models of rules, norms, and everyday practices have made them particularly resistant to change (Erikson and Freidenvall, 2023).

Hence, individual actions and political “goodwill,” accumulated over time through numerous efforts to embed changes within the rules, practices, and “organizational memory” of these institutions (ibid.), resulted in a greater number of women entering parliaments as “a legitimate aspiration of the citizenry in order to obtain a larger measure of justice and advancement in the democratization of political power” (Bernabeuand Rodríguez Gustá, 2013:4).

Over the past quarter-century, in response to these challenges, international organizations, practitioners, and academics have developed and advocated the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 7). In the decades that followed, “the concept of ‘gender-sensitive parliaments’ (GSP) has become the clearest expression of parliaments’ responsibility to promote and achieve gender equality” (ibid., 14).

The aim of this paper is to analyze the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM), constituted after the parliamentary elections held on May 8, 2024, through the lens of a gender-sensitive parliament. The paper is structured as follows: it first presents a theoretical discussion of the concept itself, followed by an analysis of the current situation in the RNM, and concludes with specific recommendations for further advancement and key findings.

2. GENDER-SENSITIVE PARLIAMENT – DEFINING THE CONCEPT

As noted in the introductory section, the concept of Gender-Sensitive Parliaments (GSP) increasingly appears as an emerging international norm that, according to Palmieri and Baker (2022), nevertheless requires “localization”. Its origins “can be traced to the 2001 report by the Commonwealth Parliamentary Associations’ study group, entitled *Gender Sensitizing Commonwealth Parliaments*” (Ahrens, Erzeel and Fieremans, 2024:3).

The most basic definition of a gender-sensitive parliament describes it as an institution that “actively respects and delivers on gender equality” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 3). However, one of the most frequently cited and widely used definitions of GSP was provided by the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU), which defines a GSP as “parliaments whose organization, operations, methods, and work resemble the needs and interests of men and women, which remove obstacles (material, structural, and/or cultural) to the equal participation of women, ensure resources for promoting gender equality, and offer a positive example and model to the society in general” (Kvinna, 2020: 3).

The same definition emphasizes that a GSP is a modern parliament because it “deals and reflects the demands of contemporary society for equality and non-discrimination, is aware that internal regulations and norms are not gender neutral, and makes efforts to achieve gender equality both internally and externally, through the adoption and promotion of gender sensitive policies” (ibid.).

Over time, the need has arisen for a revised and updated definition of GSP– one that is comprehensive yet more concrete, concise, and focused than the original IPU definition, which at first glance appears somewhat lengthy and extensive. In this context, the definition proposed by Childs and Palmieri (2023: 177) has gained prominence. They define GSP as a parliament that “values and prioritizes gender equality as a social, economic, and political

objective, and reorients and transforms their institutional culture, practice, and outputs towards those objectives”.

The following section therefore offers an overview of the actions that parliaments should undertake to strengthen the GSP concept, highlighting internal cultural, structural, and procedural – both formal and informal – aspects aimed at advancing gender sensitivity and achieving gender equality (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 15).

3. GENDER POLICIES IN PARLIAMENTS

For decades, women’s rights and gender equality have represented essential global, democratic, and social norms. They have been promoted through a series of international agreements, among which the most significant are: the 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW); the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (1995); United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security; and Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) adopted in 2015 (see: Inter Pares, 2024: 30).

In 2022, the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU), in its report *Women in Parliament*, marked a historic milestone by declaring that “not a single functioning parliament in the world is male-only” (IPU, 2023: 1–2).

This success can be attributed to the clearly defined gender policies implemented across numerous parliaments worldwide through strategic visions and action plans that enabled the achievement of concrete objectives. However, such measures alone would have remained insufficient without the establishment of self-assessment mechanisms capable of identifying existing gaps, emerging challenges, and providing adequate solutions for overcoming them (OECD, 2023: 96).

At their core, parliaments are complex institutions, and many aspects of their work directly influence gender sensitivity. Scholarly literature on this topic emphasizes that such sensitivity is particularly visible in what is often referred to as the “sacred parliamentary trinity” – *representation*, *legislation*, and *oversight* (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 7).

Regarding *representation*, also known in the literature as *descriptive representation*,²⁰ the focus is placed on ensuring gender balance in leadership positions across all parliamentary committees and delegations (OSCE/ODIHR 2021: 8). When it comes to *legislation*, gender-sensitive practices remain limited. The existence of international mechanisms and national legal frameworks that affirm equality before the law, prohibit discrimination, and encourage inclusivity are, by themselves, insufficient. Far greater significance lies in a legislative process that anticipates gender equality concerns, ensuring that existing governance rules and social structures do not perpetuate gender discrimination (OSCE/ODIHR, 2022: 8). As for *gender-sensitive oversight*, it encompasses a wide range of dimensions but can be concretized through monitoring progress; placing gender issues on the political agenda; and exploring the actual impact of government policies, programmes and actions (Inter Pares, 2024: 107).

Based on these principles, the following section presents an analysis of the current parliamentary composition of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia (2024–2028) through the lens of gender sensitivity.

²⁰ The research in this area has focused not only on the *descriptive* representation of women in parliaments (their numerical representation) but also on *substantive* representation (how women’s interests are addressed) and *symbolic* representation, such as how they appear in the media and other forms of communication (Pàrlamaid na h-Alba, 2023: 7).

4. THE CURRENT 11TH PARLIAMENTARY COMPOSITION IN PLURALISM: A GENDER-SENSITIVE ANALYSIS

On the occasion of the 30th anniversary of ODIHR (the primary institution of the OSCE), marked in 2021, its study *Realizing Gender Equality in Parliament: A Guide for Parliaments in the OSCE Region* demonstrated that parliaments in OSCE participating states, including North Macedonia, can generally boast strong female representation, “ranging from near parity to a little less than 15%. In fact, the OSCE regional average (29.6%) is higher than the global average (25%)” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 16).

In the current Assembly (2024–2028), there are 47 women MPs out of 120, representing 39.1% of the total membership. It should be noted that this constitutes an increase from the initial composition following the May 8, 2024 elections, which included 41 women MPs (34.1%). This growth is a logical outcome of the appointment of MPs to the new government, as well as subsequent resignations of members who assumed other posts and functions. From the governing coalitions of VMRO-DPMNE and VLEN, an additional 7 and 3 women MPs, respectively, entered the Assembly. Of the 10 VMRO-DPMNE MPs who joined the executive branch, 2 were women. Their parliamentary seats were filled by the next 2 female candidates from the same party list, in accordance with Article 153-a of the Electoral Code, which stipulates that: “if the Member of Parliament whose term of office has been terminated on one of the grounds prescribed in Article 152 of this Code is female, then the next female candidate on the list shall become a Member of Parliament for the remaining duration of the term of office”. This legal provision “ensures stability in the number of women in the Assembly” (Donev, 2023:5). In cases where MPs resigned, their replacements were determined according to the party and electoral district list order.

When analyzing the Assembly from a gender-sensitive perspective, particular attention should be paid to key parliamentary leadership positions, such as the Speaker and the Secretary General (the head of parliamentary administration). Regarding the Speaker’s position, the trend of exclusively male officeholders has continued. Since the introduction of the pluralist system, only once – during 1984–1985 – has a woman served as Speaker. In the current composition, there is one female Deputy Speaker out of 3, which represents an improvement, considering that in the 1990s none of the three parliamentary convocations had a female Deputy Speaker. The same situation was observed in the previous parliamentary composition (2020–2024), as well as in the 5th composition in pluralism (2006–2008). Conversely, a positive development is the reappointment of a woman as Secretary General of the Assembly, as was also the case in the previous term. Over more three decades of political pluralism, a total of 3 women have held this position. These figures are consistent with global trends within OSCE member states, where “in both cases, men were more likely to hold the positions of speaker (65%) and secretary general (64%)” (OSCE/ODIHR, 2021: 25).

A gender-sensitive parliament has always attached great significance to the selection of MPs as chairs, members, and deputy members of various parliamentary structures, such as committees and delegations. In these cases it is important “that women are present in a more diverse range” (ibid., 28). In the current parliamentary composition (2024–2028), there are 10 active parliamentary delegations. In two of them, gender parity is observed; in five, women are in the majority; in two, men dominate; and in one, there are no women at all. It

is noteworthy, however, that women outnumber men in delegation leadership positions by a ratio of 6 to 4.²¹

Table 1. Gender Representation in the Parliamentary Delegations

Beyond delegations, many parliaments worldwide have committees that function as “gendered institutional spaces”, which are manifested through their leadership and membership” (Inter Pares, 2024: 93). In this regard, the situation in the Assembly of North Macedonia differs somewhat from that of delegations. Of the 24 committees, men dominate in 15, while women lead in 7; 2 committees exhibit gender parity. Only 6 committees are chaired by women, compared to 16 chaired by men, and women serve as deputy chairs in 8 committees. In 7 committees, women represent less than 25% of members, whereas in 3 committees they form an overwhelming majority (around 80%).

The Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men, established in 2006 under the Law on Equality of Women and Men,²² traditionally shows the highest female representation. In this parliamentary term, the Verification Committee also follows this trend, as do “committees that encompass the sphere of the everyday life of women” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 15) – Education, Science and Sport (78%), Culture and Tourism (62%), and Social Policy, Demography and Youth (56%), among others. With 52% female representation, the Committee on European Affairs likewise continues its tradition of female predominance.

Conversely, in the 11th parliamentary term, committees in which women are traditionally underrepresented have once again come to the fore. These include those overseeing the Implementation of the Measures for Interception of Communications (100% men); the Work of the National Security Agency and the Intelligence Agency (78%); Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Resources Management (77%); and Defense and Security (72%) (ibid., 13-14).

²¹ All data presented in this paper are current as of October 1, 2025, and are taken from the official website of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia; they reflect the presentation provided there.

²² “Since its establishment, the average representation of women in this committee has been over 65%, and so far, all chairpersons and deputy chairpersons of this committee have been women” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 15).

This demonstrates the persistent absence of women in committees stereotypically perceived as “male”, where they effectively hold “a reduced capacity to act within these domains, meaning that decisions are made by their male colleagues” (ibid.,4).

Table 2. Gender Representation in the Working Bodies of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia

Working Bodies of the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia	mb.²³	f	%	m	%	ch.
Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men	22	18	82%	4	18%	f
Committee on Oversight of the Implementation of the Measures for Interception of Communications	8	0	0%	8	100%	m
Committee on Election and Appointment Issues	26	12	46%	14	54%	m
Committee on Rules of Procedure, and Mandatory-Immunity Issues	18	2	11%	16	89%	m
Committee on Oversight of the Work of the National Security Agency and the Intelligence Agency	18	4	22%	14	78%	m
Committee on European Affairs	29	15	52%	14	48%	m
Finance and Budget Committee	29	10	34%	19	66%	f
Committee on Economic Affairs, Labor and Energy Policy	22	6	27%	16	73%	m
Committee on Monitoring the Appropriate and Fair Representation of Citizens Belonging to All Communities	25	6	24%	19	76%	m
Committee on Agriculture, Forestry and Water Resources Management	22	5	23%	17	77%	m
Inter-Community Relations Committee	18	7	39%	11	61%	/
Committee on Transport, Digital Transformation, Environment and Spatial Planning	22	3	14%	19	86%	m
Committee on Social Policy, Demography and Youth	25	14	56%	11	44%	/
Standing Inquiry Committee for Protection of Civil Rights and Freedoms	29	9	31%	20	69%	m
Committee on Culture and Tourism	21	13	62%	8	38%	f
Verification Committee	5	4	80%	1	20%	f
Committee on Local Self-Government	26	5	19%	21	81%	m
Committee on Health Care	22	11	50%	11	50%	f
Committee on Foreign Policy and Foreign Trade	26	14	54%	12	46%	m
Committee on Education, Science and Sport	28	22	78%	6	22%	f

²³The regular members, as well as their deputies, have also been taken into consideration.

Committee on Constitutional Issues	34	16	47%	18	53%	m
Legislative Committee	28	14	50%	14	50%	m
Committee on Defense and Security	25	7	28%	18	72%	m
Committee on the Political System and Inter-Ethnic Relations	30	12	40%	18	60%	m

These data from North Macedonia’s 11th parliamentary composition reinforce the broader global observation that the number and proportion of women across party groups are automatically reflected in the composition of parliament’s committees (Inter Pares, 2024: 94). To overcome such a situation, authors such as Erikson and Josefson (2023) advocate for additional efforts aimed at achieving equal representation of both genders. This can be accomplished even through informal procedures that strive for fair representation of women. However, the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia, in its previous composition, adopted a more formalized approach: with the 2023 amendments to Article 114(3) of its Rules of Procedure, it decided that, during the selection of the Assembly’s working bodies, permanent delegations, and parliamentary cooperation groups, a gender-balanced composition should be ensured (in accordance with the current percentage of female MPs in the ongoing mandate).

Moreover, as Donev (2023: 7) notes, “apart from their participation in committees, the presence of female MPs in other structures of the Assembly as decision-makers is also crucial. For this reason, it is essential that women more frequently assume the role of parliamentary group coordinators and take part in coordination meetings where the Assembly’s agenda is determined”. In the 2024–2028 term, the Assembly comprises 6 parliamentary groups, corresponding to the number of political formations represented. According to parliamentary rules, a group must consist of at least 5 MPs. No parliamentary group is currently coordinated by a woman. However, except for the political movement ZNAM and the political party Levica, the remaining 4 groups each have both a male and a female deputy coordinator, and VMRO-DPMNE includes one male and two female deputy coordinators.

Most parliaments promote the concept of gender equality and women’s empowerment not only through formal bodies (such as the Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men in the Macedonian case) but also through informal groups, such as the Women’s Parliamentary Club (see: Sawer 2020, 2023). The Women’s Parliamentary Club has a long tradition in Macedonian parliamentarism, having been established in 2003, three years prior to the founding of the Committee on Equal Opportunities. Both bodies are crucial for achieving the aims outlined in the previous chapter – namely, to play a central role in gender-sensitive lawmaking and oversight. In the case of North Macedonia, “The Club, supported by the civil sector and the international community, made the most significant contribution to improving the normative framework regulating the nomination and election of Members of Parliament in the Assembly” (Jovevska Ćorĝevik and Janeska, 2020: 16) and “played a significant role in the fight for gender equality and the participation of women in politics” (Donev, 2023: 8).

The gender-sensitive dimension of each parliamentary composition is largely determined by the manner in which the candidate lists are submitted. In the respective elections, a total of 17 electoral lists were submitted – by 16 political parties and coalitions, as well as one group of voters. Of these, only 6 entered the 11th parliamentary composition in pluralism. The analysis therefore focuses on the structure of their electoral lists from a gender perspective. It should be emphasized that since 2015, the Electoral Code has

stipulated that political parties are obliged to submit candidate lists with at least 40% female representation. Among the parliamentary parties in this composition, the coalition led by SDSM offered the highest female representation (49%), while the Levica party, across all 6 electoral districts, opted for the legal minimum of 40% women – 8 female candidates per list. The VMRO-DPMNE-led coalition adopted the same strategy in 5 out of 6 electoral districts, as did the Albanian coalitions VLEN and the one led by DUI in 4 out of 6 electoral districts.

Table 3. The Percentage of Women on the Electoral Lists of the Parliamentary Represented Parties in the Current Parliamentary Composition (2024-2028)

Political party	ED ₁ ²⁴	ED ₂	ED ₃	ED ₄	ED ₅	ED ₆	Total %
VMRO DPMNE	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	60%	43%
SDSM	55%	45%	50%	55%	40%	50%	49%
ZNAM	40%	40%	40%	50%	45%	50%	44%
Levica	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
VLEN	40%	50%	40%	40%	50%	40%	43%
DUI	40%	40%	45%	45%	40%	40%	41%

However, a higher percentage of women on candidate lists does not automatically translate into greater female parliamentary representation, since women are often placed in non-electable positions merely to fulfill the legal quota. Consequently, we cannot expect substantial change as long as parties formally comply with legal provisions without improving women’s placement on the lists (Donev, 2023: 13). This can be illustrated with a concrete example: On the lists of VMRO-DPMNE, Levica, and ZNAM, there was only one female lead candidate. In contrast, the two Albanian coalitions that entered the Assembly did not have a single woman in the first position. The SDSM coalition was the most innovative, introducing the concept of a lead and co-lead candidate by positioning the male candidate in the first position on the list in the 1st, 4th, and 5th electoral districts, and the female candidate in the 3rd and 6th. All of these lead candidates were accompanied by a co-leader of the opposite gender, placed in the second position on the list.

Thus, it can be concluded that with nearly 40% women in the current parliamentary composition (precisely 39.1%), the Republic of North Macedonia is a regional leader in women’s parliamentary participation. This case reaffirms the argument that a proportional electoral system combined with a well-calibrated gender quota can significantly improve female representation in the legislature. The proportional model is often seen as “more responsive to societal gender norms for equality and demands for various reasons” (Inter Pares, 2024: 52). However, not every proportional system is equally favorable – only those operating with large multi-member districts, which allow the election of multiple candidates, tend to be effective. This is precisely the case in North Macedonia, which is divided into 6 constituencies with 20 seats each. In contrast, single-member districts typical of majoritarian systems allow for only one winner (Matland, 2005). This model can be particularly unfavorable for women, as shown by Macedonia’s early 1990s experience, when the two-round majoritarian system produced only 4% women MPs in 1990 and 3% in 1994, partly due to the low nomination rates of 6% and 8% women, respectively (Jovevska ĆorĆevik and Janeska, 2020: 9-10). However, this runoff model (*ballotage*), historically associated with

²⁴ Electoral district.

France as the most paradigmatic example, produces 39.5% female representation in the French National Assembly, since the model there is combined with a gender quota (Inter Pares, 2024: 53).

The effects of gender quotas are well studied in literature – they are most effective when they “are binding, use a quota percentage close to 50%, apply rank-order rules specifying the distribution of men and women on candidate lists or in winnable constituencies, and demand strict sanctions that do not rely solely on financial penalties” (Dahlerup 2016; Krook 2009 quoted in Inter Pares, 2024: 57). The Electoral Code of North Macedonia anticipates many of these provisions, setting the quota at 40% and stipulating that “at least one out of every three places shall be reserved for the underrepresented sex, with at least one additional place out of every ten places” (Art. 64 (5) Electoral Law of the R. of N. Macedonia).

5. CONCLUSION

Through the introduction of proportional representation in 2002 and the continued and permanent interventions in electoral legislation aimed at improving the gender quota,²⁵ the Republic of North Macedonia has dramatically enhanced women’s representation in its legislative body. Over more than three decades of political pluralism, the observation made by Dahlerup (2016: 64) also applies to North Macedonia – that “women in parliaments have moved from being a ‘small minority’ to a ‘large minority’”.

The proposed *Action Plan for the Advancement of Equality between Women and Men in the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia 2025–2027*, adopted by the Committee on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men in its current composition (2024–2028), reaffirms several commitments included in the previous two plans (2020–21; 2022–24), many of which remain unfulfilled. Nonetheless, the report notes certain achievements compared to previous periods. The Assembly has incorporated several aspects of gender equality strengthening into its Rules of Procedure. To raise awareness about promoting gender equality, an annual plenary session dedicated to this topic has been institutionalized. Multiple trainings and workshops have been conducted to strengthen capacities for recognizing and preventing violence against women in politics. Additionally, within the Office of the Secretary General, a Gender Equality Advisor position has been established (see: Assembly of RNM, 2025: 3, 18).

This third and current Action Plan reaffirms the commitment to lobby for amendments to the Electoral Code introducing a 50% gender quota through a “zipper system”, ensuring equality between women and men on candidate lists for both parliamentary and local council elections. The report concludes that no changes have yet been made to the legal framework and that intra-party dialogue regarding the promotion of women in executive and local government positions (i.e., the introduction of quotas) remains difficult. It also notes the absence of developed and implemented guidelines for the use of gender-sensitive language in parliamentary work.

Nevertheless, hope remains that the current parliamentary composition will address these challenges and continue advancing the concept of the Gender-Sensitive Parliament (GSP) within the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia.

²⁵ The initial quota was set at 30%, and with the amendments to the Electoral Code in 2015, it was raised to 40%. In 2006, the quota was further specified to ensure that for every three positions, one must be allocated to the less represented gender.

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STRATEGIC AMBIGUITY AND HYBRID THREATS IN THE TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY

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Abstract

This article investigates the strategic logic and historical evolution of hybrid threats in the twenty-first century, with particular emphasis on the role of strategic ambiguity in shaping contemporary conflict. It examines how hybrid threats – characterized by the fusion of military, informational, economic, and legal instruments – have emerged as central tools in the projection of influence by both state and non-state actors. The study draws on a qualitative methodology combining comparative case analysis and interpretive discourse analysis, focusing on Russian strategic thought as articulated through the doctrines associated with Yevgeny Primakov and Valery Gerasimov. While Primakov’s vision of multipolarity and strategic balancing laid the groundwork for indirect influence and normative contestation, Gerasimov’s articulation of hybrid warfare reflects a more operationalized and tactical approach to ambiguity in conflict.

The article addresses a critical academic gap: although hybrid threats are widely acknowledged in policy discourse, their intellectual genealogy and doctrinal foundations remain underexplored in scholarly literature. By tracing the conceptual lineage and strategic applications of hybrid threats, the article contributes to a deeper understanding of modern hostilities and offers insights for adaptive security governance.

Key words: hybrid threats, strategic ambiguity, influence operations

1. INTRODUCTION

“The role of non-military means of achieving political and strategic goals has grown, and in many cases, they have exceeded the power of force of weapons in their effectiveness.”

Gerasimov, V. (2013)

Hybrid threats – unconventional threats that fall below the threshold of military force – have become a pervasive feature of today’s security environment. The rise of hybrid threats represents a profoundly subversive challenge to national security and the international order. Due to their diversified and subtle forms of operation, there is no consensus on their definition. Essentially, the term refers to a range of activities that are strategically planned and coordinated under the cover of states or other actors, as a tactic to exert influence with the aim of altering or damaging the existing order.

The “victim” may be any individual or institution with decision-making power at the local, regional, national, or institutional level. These actions are deliberately directed at any sphere that is potentially vulnerable or represents a field for the abuse of civil rights and freedoms. Although present in every context – and likely no state is immune – their effects are most pronounced in new democracies or states in transition and institutional development. Unfortunately, they are often used as tools to build spheres of influence.

Much of what is treated as “hybrid threat” is not new, but rather a strategy and tactic applied in a new way, since “war has a changing nature but a permanent character” (Clausewitz, n.d.). Hybrid threats take on new forms and dimensions in each context, especially due to increased digitalization and growing dependence on internet-based services.

In the narrowest sense, hybrid threats refer to a mix of non-military activities through which strategic goals are achieved. They counter conventional threats, i.e., threats involving the use of military force. While states are the most common actors, hybrid threats may also originate from other entities such as terrorist groups, criminal organizations, or hacktivists (Hactivist, n.d.).

In a broader context, hybrid threats encompass multimodal, low-intensity, kinetic and non-kinetic threats involving various tactics, including cyberwarfare, asymmetric conflict scenarios, global terrorism, piracy, transnational organized crime, etc. Recognized in NATO’s 2010 Strategic Concept, hybrid threats are defined as those posed by adversaries capable of simultaneously employing adaptive conventional and unconventional means to achieve their objectives (NATO, 2010). The term “hybrid threats” serves as an umbrella for a wide spectrum of security threats that may originate from states or other actors, with attribution and accountability often difficult to establish.

In the 2016 Joint Communication of the European Commission, European Parliament, and Council on the European Agenda for Security and Defence, hybrid threats are defined as a mix of coercive and subversive activity using conventional and unconventional methods (i.e., diplomatic, military, economic, and technological), coordinated by states or other actors to achieve specific objectives while remaining below the threshold of formally declared warfare (European Commission, 2016).

In practice, hybrid threats encompass a wide range of influence operations through which various malign actors – often, but not exclusively, foreign – achieve strategic objectives under the guise of democracy and liberal openness (Gregg, 2024; Hybrid CoE, n.d.). These operations are deliberately designed to exploit systemic vulnerabilities in democratic societies, often using coordinated and synchronized actions that remain below the threshold of formal warfare.

Hybrid threats are always directed toward achieving strategic goals and are inherently synchronized. In this context, trouble rarely comes alone; rather, these are orchestrated actions that may pursue specific objectives, such as regime change in a targeted country, or broader goals like generating public panic and undermining trust in institutions (Olech, 2025).

At different stages of implementation, hybrid threats may take various forms – such as violent protests, cyber attacks, false bomb threats or disinformation – and be carried out by different actors, including political parties, NGOs, or religious organizations. Hybrid threats aim to shape public opinion to support the desired effects for the sponsor or power center behind them, and their effects are often cascading and not immediately visible. Therefore, building personal and societal resilience, and fostering a society of aware, informed, and free individuals and media, is of critical importance.

2. STRATEGIC AMBIGUITY AS A TOOL OF FOREIGN POLICY

Strategic ambiguity is defined as the deliberate use of unclear or non-specific communication by states to create uncertainty about their intentions, capabilities, or responses. This approach is particularly effective in sensitive geopolitical contexts such as territorial disputes, nuclear policy, and alliance commitments. For example, Israel's policy of neither confirming nor denying its nuclear capabilities exemplifies strategic ambiguity, deterring adversaries while avoiding diplomatic fallout (Youvan, 2024).

Eisenberg (1984) originally conceptualized strategic ambiguity in organizational communication, but its application in international relations has grown significantly. It is used to preserve deterrence without escalation, as seen in the U.S. policy toward Taiwan, where ambiguity discourages both Chinese aggression and Taiwanese independence declarations (Wang et al., 2024).

Hybrid threats thrive in environments where actors can exploit ambiguity to mask intentions, obscure attribution, and manipulate perceptions. Strategic ambiguity, therefore, becomes both a tool and a condition that enables hybrid operations.

Ambiguity is not merely a feature but the essence of hybrid warfare. Analysis of the 2014 war in eastern Ukraine and China's actions in the South China Sea demonstrate how kinetic and non-kinetic means were deployed in ambiguous ways to achieve political goals without crossing clear thresholds that would provoke conventional military responses. This strategic use of ambiguity allows hybrid actors to:

1. Avoid direct attribution, making retaliation difficult;
2. Exploit legal and normative grey zones, especially in cyberspace and information domains;
3. Maintain plausible deniability, which is crucial for influencing public opinion and international legitimacy (Mumford and Carlucci, 2023).

3. THE GERASIMOV DOCTRINE AND STRATEGIC INFLUENCE OPERATIONS

Hybrid threats – defined as the coordinated use of military, political, economic, informational, and cyber tools – have become central to Russia's strategic posture. While often attributed to General Valery Gerasimov, the roots of Russia's hybrid warfare doctrine lie in the foreign policy vision of Yevgeny Primakov, who reshaped Russian intelligence and diplomacy in the post-Soviet era.

The "Gerasimov Doctrine" refers primarily as influence operations conducted through informational, cultural, humanitarian, diplomatic, and economic activities. This includes the use of fake news to shape public opinion, and in this context, even the false bomb threats experienced in parts of Europe in 2023 can be interpreted as attempts to instill fear and erode trust in institutions. Although the "Gerasimov Doctrine" is more commonly used as a Western construct, the term originates from an article by Russian General Valery Gerasimov, published during a period of heightened tension in Russian-Ukrainian relations, shortly before the annexation of Crimea.

It would be unfair, however, to attribute the entire burden of hybrid warfare solely to General Gerasimov. This doctrine has deeper historical roots in Russian foreign policy and the evolution of its intelligence services. Many scholars consider it an advanced version of the "Primakov Doctrine," named after former Russian Foreign Minister and Prime Minister Yevgeny Primakov, who argued that a unipolar world dominated by the United

States was unacceptable for Russia. He proposed the following principles for Russian foreign policy:

- Russia should strive for a multipolar world to counterbalance U.S. unilateral power;
- Russia should assert its primacy in the post-Soviet space and lead regional integration;
- Russia should oppose NATO expansion.

The Primakov Doctrine, crystallized during his tenure as Foreign Minister beginning in 1996, was a direct rejection of a unipolar world order dominated by the United States (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2019). The doctrine insisted on Russia's primacy in the post-Soviet space and vehemently opposed NATO expansion, thereby setting long-term revisionist geopolitical goals. Critically, because Russia lacked the conventional military and economic resources to openly challenge the West, this strategic vision required new asymmetrical means to constrain U.S. power and reassert Russian status. While Primakov himself did not invent cyberattacks or disinformation, his doctrine created the demand for tools capable of destabilizing adversaries and challenging the status quo below the threshold of formal kinetic war.

In subsequent years, the perception emerged that the threat from Russia was based solely on soft power exercised through hybrid threats. However, the war in Ukraine demonstrated that this was not the only danger emanating from the East. The scope and scale of Russian hybrid operations expanded alongside the growth of its hard power capabilities – namely, armament and the direct use of force.

Russia has a long history of propaganda and disinformation operations, often classified by their effects into information-technical and information-psychological categories (U.S. Department of State, 2020; Horvath, 2022). A major turning point occurred in 2008, when pro-Russian cyberattacks coincided with Russian military operations in Georgia. These attacks were part of a synchronized campaign that included distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks and website defacements, targeting government and media infrastructure (Deibert, Rohozinski, & Crete-Nishihata, 2012; White, 2018).

Both sides competed to control the flow of information to the international community. From today's perspective, many experts agree that Georgia won the information war through an aggressive campaign involving disinformation and media manipulation –an alarming precedent for democratic norms and liberal values (Korns & Kastenberg, 2009).

4. CONTEMPORARY CASE STUDIES

Russia's operationalization of hybrid threats aligned closely with the strategic objectives laid out by Primakov. The so-called "Gerasimov Doctrine" (2013), often cited as the operational template, effectively fused hard and soft power across diplomatic, informational, and military domains (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2019). The critical lever for executing this strategy is strategic ambiguity – the purposeful obfuscation of an actor's identity, intent, or the military nature of its actions. This ambiguity serves two primary functions: it paralyzes the target state's decision-making process by keeping actions below the formal threshold of war, and it enables plausible deniability, thereby preventing escalation and avoiding punitive responses such as invocation of NATO's Article 5.

This approach was evident in several significant operations, including Georgia (2008), where Russia's military intervention was preceded by coordinated, large-scale cyberattacks against Georgian government websites and a sustained disinformation campaign, demonstrating an early integration of digital and conventional force (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2019).

The next chapter unfolded in Crimea and Eastern Ukraine (2014). This episode cemented the modern understanding of hybrid warfare. Russia deployed unmarked military personnel ("little green men"), organized local proxy groups, employed extensive social media propaganda, and applied economic pressure to annex Crimea and destabilize the Donbas region, all while maintaining plausible deniability – a textbook execution of sub-threshold conflict (Rahim, 2025).

Estonia, as one of the most digitally advanced and geopolitically exposed nations in the Baltic region, has long been a focal point for Russian hybrid threat activities. These threats, which blend conventional and non-conventional tactics, aim to exploit systemic vulnerabilities in democratic societies through disinformation, cyberattacks, sabotage, and influence operations (Praks, 2024).

One of the earliest and most emblematic cases of Russian hybrid aggression against Estonia occurred during the 2007 *Bronze Soldier* crisis, which involved coordinated cyberattacks and information warfare targeting Estonian institutions and public sentiment (Praks, 2023). This incident marked a turning point in the regional understanding of hybrid threats, highlighting the Kremlin's capacity to weaponize ambiguity and non-military means to achieve strategic objectives.

In recent years, Russia has intensified its hybrid tactics, particularly in response to Estonia's vocal support for Ukraine and its alignment with Western institutions. These tactics include GPS jamming, airspace violations, and suspected sabotage of critical infrastructure such as undersea cables and energy networks (Hybrid CoE, 2024). The Estlink-2 power cable incident – where a Russian-linked vessel severed the connection between Estonia and Finland – exemplifies the covert nature of such operations and their potential to disrupt national security without crossing the threshold of open conflict.

Disinformation campaigns remain a cornerstone of Russia's hybrid strategy. These efforts often target Estonia's Russian-speaking minority, aiming to foster division and undermine trust in democratic institutions (Radin, 2017). The Kremlin's narrative architecture, amplified through state-linked media and digital platforms, seeks to portray Estonia as hostile to Russian culture and values, thereby legitimizing interference under the guise of protecting ethnic Russians abroad.

Estonia's response has been multifaceted, involving both defensive and normative strategies. The government has invested heavily in cyber resilience, strategic communications, and legal reforms to counter malign influence. Moreover, Estonia has advocated for stronger EU and NATO coordination in addressing hybrid threats, emphasizing the need for shared situational awareness and attribution capabilities (Praks, 2025).

Ultimately, Estonia's experience underscores the evolving nature of hybrid warfare, where ambiguity is not merely a tactic but a strategic condition. As hybrid threats continue to challenge conventional deterrence models, Estonia's case offers valuable insights into resilience-building and the recalibration of security doctrines in the twenty-first century. Beyond the battlefield, influence operations targeting democratic processes have become increasingly visible. Notable examples include Russia's interference in U.S. and French elections, where coordinated disinformation campaigns aimed to manipulate public opinion,

polarize societies, and undermine trust in democratic institutions (Office of the Director of National Intelligence, 2017; RAND Corporation, 2020; McMasters, 2020).

Disinformation campaigns – and more broadly, foreign information manipulation and interference (FIMI) – are often used by threat actors as part of wider hybrid campaigns or as standalone instruments (Council of the European Union, 2025).

In the immediate region, Montenegro experienced significant political turbulence in the period leading up to its NATO accession, with tensions persisting afterward. These disturbances were often framed as societal issues, with religious controversies playing a particularly prominent role. The demoralization phase included widespread dissemination of fake news, hate speech, disinformation, and calls to defend against an imagined enemy. A local online portal played a central role in spreading disinformation despite not being registered in the official media registry. It presented itself as a legitimate news outlet and produced emotionally charged content, including historical distortions linking Montenegro's president to fascist regimes from World War II. Similar tactics were employed by the pro-Kremlin outlet *Sputnik*. These cases were documented by the Digital Forensic Center in Podgorica (Center for Democratic Transition, 2024; EUvsDisinfo, 2018).

The 2021 local elections in Nikšić marked a turning point, particularly due to Serbia's active involvement in the campaign. Individuals affiliated with or close to the ruling Serbian Progressive Party (SNS) were present in Montenegro, raising concerns about foreign interference. Some were detained, while others were denied entry due to suspicions of transporting funds to buy votes. Following the elections, the City of Belgrade donated €2 million to the municipality of Nikšić, further intensifying suspicions of electoral integrities and foreign influence (Regional Academy for Democratic Development, 2024).

In Romania's presidential elections held on November 24, 2024, ultranationalist and pro-Russian candidate Călin Georgescu led the first round with 22.94% of the vote, defying pre-election polls that predicted only 5–10% support. Georgescu, a vocal critic of NATO and the EU, surpassed Prime Minister Marcel Ciolacu, marking the first time a Social Democrat failed to reach the second round in post-communist Romania. His campaign was characterized by a suspicious surge in social media activity, especially on TikTok and Telegram, driven by paid influencers and coordinated networks. Romanian intelligence services confirmed that actors linked to Russia played a key role in amplifying pro-Russian and anti-Western narratives. TikTok subsequently removed millions of fake accounts promoting Georgescu's messages, although significant damage had already been done. Intelligence assessments confirmed that many of these accounts were tied to Russian-affiliated entities, indicating direct involvement by Moscow in manipulating public opinion. On December 6, Romania's Constitutional Court annulled the election results due to widespread irregularities and credible evidence of foreign interference. This unprecedented decision underscored the severity of hybrid threats targeting democratic institutions in Eastern Europe. (OpenMinds, 2025; *Politico*, 2024).

5. CONCLUSION

In an era marked by blurred boundaries between war and peace, state and non-state actors, and truth and disinformation, strategic ambiguity has emerged as both a tactic and a condition of modern geopolitics. Hybrid threats exploit this ambiguity, operating in the grey zones of international law, diplomacy, and security frameworks. This paper has examined how strategic ambiguity functions not only as a deliberate policy tool but also as a systemic feature of contemporary conflict environments.

The rise of hybrid threats – from cyber operations and disinformation campaigns to proxy warfare and economic coercion – demands a recalibration of traditional security doctrines. Strategic ambiguity, while offering flexibility and deterrence, also risks undermining transparency, accountability, and normative stability. As such, states must strike a balance between ambiguity and clarity, especially when navigating alliances, deterrence strategies, and legal obligations.

Ultimately, understanding the interplay between strategic ambiguity and hybrid threats is essential for crafting resilient institutions, adaptive policies, and cooperative international responses. The twenty-first century will continue to challenge conventional notions of conflict and strategy, and it is within this evolving landscape that ambiguity must be critically assessed –not only as a tool of power, but also as a potential vulnerability.

The trajectory of hybrid threats from strategic ambition to practical execution is deeply rooted in the post-Soviet geopolitical landscape shaped by the Primakov Doctrine. Primakov’s call for multipolarity necessitated an asymmetrical challenge to Western power, which successive Russian leaders operationalized through hybrid means. This evolution is characterized by the increasing sophistication and integration of non-military instruments – cyber operations, disinformation, and economic coercion –ultimately backed by hard military power. Central to this approach is strategic ambiguity, which ensures deniability and prevents a collective, escalatory response. Today, hybrid threats constitute a pervasive reality of international competition, requiring target nations to develop “whole-of-society” resilience that extends well beyond traditional military preparedness.

The future trajectory of hybrid conflict points toward increasing complexity across new technological domains. Actors are rapidly adopting artificial intelligence (AI) to scale operations, particularly through the creation of highly convincing “deepfake” disinformation campaigns that accelerate societal polarization. Furthermore, the reliance of modern states on digital technologies has rendered critical infrastructure a prime target for ambiguous, non-kinetic attacks, constituting a new gray zone of strategic competition. This constant technological advancement ensures that the threat remains dynamic and sophisticated, continually focused on maximizing impact while minimizing the risk of overt retaliation.

Finally, the ambiguity inherent in hybrid threats poses profound challenges to international security governance. By operating below the formal threshold of “armed attack” as defined by bodies such as the United Nations, hybrid actions exploit gaps in customary international law (*jus ad bellum*). This evasion necessitates a fundamental reevaluation of deterrence frameworks, shifting focus from traditional military response towards proactive measures such as regulatory harmonization, improved attribution capabilities, and coordinated diplomatic sanctions. Successfully countering this threat requires an international consensus that acts of strategic ambiguity, regardless of their lethality, must carry consequences in order to preserve the stability of the global system.

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STATUS, CHALLENGES AND CONCEPTUALIZATION OF THE FUTURE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINISTRY OF TRANSPORT – STATE TRANSPORT INSPECTORATE IN THE SEGMENT OF SAFE TRANSPORT OF PASSENGERS AND GOODS IN ROAD TRAFFIC

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Abstract

This paper presents a theoretical and research-based overview and a synthesis of perspectives aimed at portraying the current state and conceptualizing the future development of an important institutional actor—the State Transport Inspectorate—in ensuring enhanced safety in the transport of passengers and goods in road traffic. Through data analysis and content analysis methods, the paper examines the existing operational and technical challenges faced by the Inspectorate. Furthermore, it proposes a conceptual framework for a future operational model within the Ministry of Transport in the domestic context, while positioning the Inspectorate as a modern European inspection service in a broader comparative perspective.

Keywords: *road traffic; passengers; goods; safety; State Transport Inspectorate.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The safety and security of passenger and goods transport in road traffic represent one of the most important components of the transport system. Their proper functioning and development have a significant impact on public safety, economic activity, environmental protection, and the overall efficiency of road traffic. Achieving a higher level of road traffic safety is a pressing issue and a strategic objective; however, empirical data and field observations often point to persistent shortcomings. The path toward improved safety is neither linear nor free of obstacles, but rather dynamic and complex, shaped by a multitude of institutional, legislative, personnel, and technical prerequisites, as well as—most importantly—by human behavior, awareness, and responsibility.

Synchronized inter-institutional cooperation and continuous inspection activities constitute essential prerequisites for prevention, the reduction of accidents and violations,

and the achievement of a higher overall level of road traffic safety. The network of actors responsible for ensuring road traffic safety and security is broad and interconnected. In addition to the State Transport Inspectorate, operating as a body within the Ministry of Transport, this network includes the Ministry of Transport itself—primarily through the Sector for Road Transport and Infrastructure—the Ministry of Internal Affairs, through the Department for Border Affairs and Migration and the Bureau for Public Safety (Traffic Sector), the National Border Management Center, the Customs Administration, the Public Enterprise for State Roads, and the Public Enterprise for the Maintenance of Main and Regional Roads.

Further contributors include educational institutions responsible for the training of technical personnel and the conduct of professional examinations, technical inspection stations and workshops performing analyses and checks across various segments of the road transport sector, national transport and carriers' associations, as well as driver training centers. Each of these entities, to varying degrees, contributes to ensuring safety, smooth traffic flow, and compliance with national legislation and internationally ratified legal instruments.

Within this framework, the State Transport Inspectorate occupies a particularly significant position. Through its supervisory, preventive, and repressive functions, the Inspectorate plays a crucial role in raising awareness among stakeholders, educating sector participants, identifying and addressing irregularities, and preventing future violations. These activities directly contribute to reducing the number of infringements, enhancing safety in the transport of passengers and goods, and improving overall road transport conditions at both national and international levels.

The impact of passenger and goods transport in road traffic is multidimensional, affecting safety, road infrastructure integrity, environmental sustainability, and economic flows. Minimizing or eliminating negative effects requires sustained investment in human resources and technical-operational capacities. This includes the recruitment of highly qualified professional staff, the deployment of advanced information systems and technological equipment for the detection and identification of violations, and the implementation of appropriate safety measures within the road traffic system.

2. THE STATE TRANSPORT INSPECTORATE THROUGH THE LENS OF MODERN DIGITAL REALITY

2.1. Legal Framework and Territorial Dispersion

Pursuant to Article 87-b of the Law on Road Transport²⁶, the State Transport Inspectorate is established as a body within the Ministry of Transport. Recent legislative interventions—namely the adoption and entry into force of the Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 272/24²⁷), the Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 22/25²⁸)

²⁶ “Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 68/04, 127/06, 114/09, 83/10, 140/10, 17/11, 53/11, 6/12, 23/13, 120/13, 163/13, 187/13, 42/14, 112/14, 166/14, 44/15, 97/15, 124/15, 129/15, 193/15, 37/16, 71/16, 64/18, 140/18 and 163/18 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 275/19, 67/22, 170/24, 3/25, 17/25 and 101/25.

²⁷ The Law entered into force on 27 December 2024.

²⁸ The Law entered into force on 3 February 2025.

and the Law on Amending the Law on Road Transport (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 3/25²⁹) – have brought significant institutional changes.

As a result of these amendments, the State Transport Inspectorate remains an integral part of the Ministry of Transport but has lost its previous status as a legal entity with an independent budget account as a first-line budget user. Furthermore, the new Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 135/25³⁰) which entered into force on 12 July 2025 and will apply from 1 January 2026, stipulates that state inspectorates may not be granted legal entity status by separate legislation. Instead, they independently manage the budget approved by the Ministry to which they belong, upon authorization by the Minister, and conduct employment procedures for inspectors in accordance with applicable law.

The headquarters of the State Transport Inspectorate is located in Skopje, with regional offices distributed across the municipalities of Tetovo, Gostivar, Kičevo, Gevgelija, Ohrid, Kočani, Sveti Nikole, Struga, Bitola, Kriva Palanka, Radoviš, Prilep, Kavadarci, Veles, and Berovo.

2.2. Organizational and Staffing Structure

The State Transport Inspectorate is headed by a Director appointed and dismissed by the Government. Internally, as a body within the Ministry of Transport, it is structured into two (2) sectors, each comprising two (2) departments, as illustrated in the organizational chart below.

Figure 1. Organizational Units of the State Transport Inspectorate

²⁹ The Law entered into force on 3 January 2025.

³⁰ The Law entered into force on 12 July 2025, but shall be applicable from 1 January 2026.

Source: Ministry of Transport, Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate, p. 1.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport> (Accessed on 12 March 2025).

As of 1 March 2025, out of a total of 64 systematized job positions within the Inspectorate, 39 positions are filled, representing a staffing level of 60.94%. Of the 49 inspector positions, only 28 are filled (57.14%), while 11 of the 15 administrative (non-inspector) positions are filled (73.33%).

Figure 2. Quantitative Overview of Systematized and Filled Positions in the State Transport Inspectorate

Source: Ministry of Transport, Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate, p. 2.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport> (Accessed on 12 March 2025).

Excluding the Director—who is appointed by the Government and is not classified as an administrative civil servant—the Inspectorate is clearly understaffed relative to the scope of its mandate. The inspector corps consists of only 28 inspectors, approximately half of whom are over 51 years of age, responsible for supervising road transport activities throughout the entire territory of the country. The 11 administrative employees display heterogeneous educational backgrounds and age profiles.

The Department for Road Traffic Inspection Supervision employs twenty (20) inspectors, including one (1) Head of Department (senior inspector), twelve (12) senior advisor-inspectors, one (1) independent inspector, two (2) assistant inspectors, and four (4)

junior inspectors. These inspectors are tasked with enforcing road transport legislation. The majority of violations are detected during field inspections conducted while transport operations are ongoing, although inspections are also carried out at company headquarters, other business premises, customs terminals, and border crossings. Both domestic and foreign legal and natural persons are subject to inspection supervision.

The Department for Public Roads, Cable Cars, and Ski Lifts Inspection Supervision includes eight (8) inspectors: seven (7) senior advisor-inspectors responsible for enforcing the Law on Public Roads, and one (1) senior inspector responsible for the application of the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts. Their activities primarily involve field inspections of public roads, technical inspection stations, cable car installations, and ski lifts.

Table 1. Quantitative Overview of Inspector Staff in the State Transport Inspectorate by Type, Age, and Title (as of 1 March 2025)

Age → Level – Position ↓	Road Traffic						Public Roads					Cable Cars and Ski Lifts					Inspectors (Total)							
	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	
B1 – General Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B2 – Chief Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B3 – Assistant Chief Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B4 – Senior Inspector		1				1						0						0	0	0	1	0	0	0
V1 – Advisor Inspector	0	0	4	4	4	12	0	1	2	2	2	7	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	6	7	6	6
V2 – Independent Inspector			1			1						0						0	0	0	0	1	0	0
V3 – Assistant Inspector			1	1		2						0						0	0	0	0	1	1	0
V4 – Junior Inspector	1	2	1			4						0						0	1	2	1	0	0	0
Total	1	3	7	5	4	20	0	1	2	2	2	7	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	4	9	8	6	6

Source: Ministry of Transport, **Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate**, pp. 2–3.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>

(Accessed on 12 March 2025.)

2.3. Segmented Responsibilities

The competencies and authorizations of the various profiles of state inspectors within the State Transport Inspectorate derive from the provisions of the Law on Road Transport, the Law on the Transport of Dangerous Goods in Road and Rail Traffic, the Law on the Working Time of Mobile Workers in Road Transport and Recording Devices in Road Transport, the Law on Public Roads, the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts, and the Law on the Prohibition and Prevention of Performing Unregistered Activities, as well as from multilateral agreements and international treaties ratified by the Republic of North Macedonia.

In the segment of passenger and goods transport in domestic and international road traffic, state road traffic inspectors conduct supervision over a broad range of areas, including³¹:

- fulfillment of the conditions for obtaining licenses for inter-municipal and international passenger and goods transport;
- compliance with specific technical and operational requirements for vehicles used in different types of transport;
- implementation of agreements on joint inter-municipal line passenger transport concluded between one or more municipalities;
- passenger transport in inter-municipal road traffic;
- goods transport in domestic road traffic;
- supervision of legal entities, sole proprietors, and individuals engaged in international transport with regard to their obligations for verification and retention of copies of international transport permits;
- passenger and goods transport in international road traffic;
- special line passenger transport conducted between two or more municipalities or exclusively within a single municipality;
- inter-municipal taxi passenger transport; and
- bus stations and bus stops.

In contrast, state road inspectors (as distinct from road traffic inspectors) exercise responsibilities prescribed under the Law on Public Roads, which include the authority:

- to inspect and supervise the maintenance and protection of public roads and road facilities;
- to halt works carried out contrary to the provisions of the Law on Public Roads relating to the protection of public roads and road facilities and to order the *отстранување* (removal) of identified deficiencies;
- to order the remediation of deficiencies on public roads that endanger traffic safety or the stability of the road and road facilities;
- to suspend works carried out on or near public roads that may compromise road integrity or traffic safety;
- to exclude from traffic vehicles transported without a permit for extraordinary transport;

³¹ The specific competencies of state road traffic inspectors prescribed in the Law on the Transport of Dangerous Goods in Road and Rail Traffic and in the Law on Working Hours of Mobile Workers in Road Traffic and Recording Devices in Road Traffic are not the subject of this paper, but are of exceptional importance for the topic that is the subject of scientific observation.

- to order the demolition of facilities or parts thereof constructed within the road area or protective belt;
- to take measures to secure public roads and, where necessary, to temporarily prohibit traffic for certain categories of vehicles which, due to their technical characteristics, may damage the public road or, due to road conditions, may endanger traffic safety;
- to prohibit traffic on newly constructed or reconstructed public roads, their sections, or facilities thereon if they are placed into use without the required operating permit;
- to control whether temporary traffic regimes comply with approved traffic projects;
- to prohibit the use of parking areas or access roads on public roads if constructed without a permit or in contradiction to the issued permit;
- to supervise and control toll collection;
- to supervise and control the collection of fees for the use of public roads by motor and trailer vehicles, as well as fees for technical assistance on roads;
- to undertake other measures and actions within their competence under the Law on Public Roads; and
- to conduct inspection supervision in accordance with the provisions of the Law on the Prohibition and Prevention of Performing Unregistered Activities.

For the purposes of this paper, it should also be noted that the sole inspector for cable cars and ski lifts employed by the State Transport Inspectorate is responsible for supervising the condition of cable cars and ski lifts; overseeing the implementation of the provisions of the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts relating to operational conditions; monitoring compliance with technical regulations, norms, and standards during construction and maintenance; and supervising works carried out on these facilities or within their protective zones.

2.4. Brief Summary of Passenger and Goods Transport and Inspection Supervision

Passenger and freight transport, by years

Figure 3. Passenger and Freight Transport (2010–2023³²)

Source: State Statistical Office

Web link:

https://makstat.stat.gov.mk/PXWeb/pxweb/en/MakStat/MakStat_Transport_PatenTransport/560_Trans_MK_T39_ml.px/chart/chartViewLine/?rxid=46ee0f64-2992-4b45-a2d9-cb4e5f7ec5ef. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

³² Since 2014, due to methodological changes, data on road passenger transport refer only to national and international transport. Since 2018, transit and cabotage have been included.

Figure 4. Three-Year Summary³³ of Inspection Supervisions and Detected Irregularities by the State Transport Inspectorate (2022–2024)

Source: *Ministry of Transport, Analysis of Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervisions in the State Transport Inspectorate*, p.3.

Web link: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

3. CHALLENGES AND RISKS

The European Commission’s 2024 Report³⁴ on the Progress of the Republic of North Macedonia, published on 30 October 2024, contains a brief observation noting that the operational and technical capacities of the State Transport Inspectorate remain weak.

The identified challenges include an unfavorable quantitative and age structure of the inspector cadre; an extremely limited availability of highly trained non-inspector (administrative) staff to provide back-office or support services; a low volume of specialized theoretical and practical training; the loss of an independent budget account, particularly affecting the realization of capital investments; spatial and technical limitations in both the headquarters and regional offices; the absence of ISO standards and international certification for quality and process management; outdated stationary and mobile technical equipment; the lack of a central monitoring and data center with real-time analytics and data recovery systems; the non-implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) along

³³ The graphic chart displays data from all areas of inspection competence of the State Transport Inspectorate.

³⁴ https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/north-macedonia-report-2024_en. Accessed on 30 March 2025.

international road corridors; the absence of fully equipped road checkpoints for inspection purposes; insufficient safe parking spaces for heavy vehicles and buses during traffic stops; and an aging vehicle fleet. All of these factors impair traffic safety, monitoring, and the overall functionality of road traffic, and they undoubtedly have a negative impact on the scope and quality of the Inspectorate’s operational activities in the exercise of its powers.

For the purposes of this paper, particular attention is given to the issue of inspector mobility during field inspections through an analysis of indicators related to the quantity, age, and condition of the Inspectorate’s available vehicle fleet. This aspect will be further elaborated in Chapter 5, which addresses the implementation of a project aimed at modernizing the Inspectorate’s vehicle fleet with the support of grant funds from the European Union’s Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance 2021–2027 (IPA III).

Table 2³⁵. Age Structure and Condition of the Vehicle Fleet of the State Transport Inspectorate (as of March 1st, 2025)

Source: *Ministry of Transport, Analysis of Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervisions in the State Transport Inspectorate*, p.4.

Web link: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

No.	Vehicle model and type	Year of manufacture	Vehicle type, engine power (kW) and engine displacement (cm ³)
1.	Ford Fiesta	2001	passenger / 44 kW / 1.299 cm ³
2.	Ford Fiesta	2001	passenger / 44 kW / 1.299 cm ³
3.	Skoda Fabia	2000	passenger / 74 kW / 1.390 cm ³
4.	Volkswagen Golf 3 Caravan	1997	passenger / 66 kW / 1.896 cm ³
5.	Peugeot 306 Caravan	2000	passenger / 66 kW / 1.997 cm ³
6.	Seat Ibiza	1995	passenger / 44 kW / 1.391 cm ³
7.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
8.	Opel Corsa	1998	passenger / 44 kW / 1.686 cm ³
9.	Opel Corsa	1998	passenger / 44 kW / 1.686 cm ³
10.	Seat Ibiza	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.398 cm ³
11.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
12.	Skoda Felicia	1995	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
13.	Skoda Felicia	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
14.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
15.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
16.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
17.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
18.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
19.	Skoda Felicia	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
20.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
21.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
22.	Opel Astra	2001	passenger / 55 kW / 1.199 cm ³
23.	Volkswagen Caddy	2007	passenger / 51 kW / 1.997 cm ³
24.	Audi A3	1998	passenger / 66 kW / 1.896 cm ³

³⁵ The registration plates of the passenger motor vehicles are not shown in the table.

From the data presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that, of the total number of passenger motor vehicles available to the Inspectorate, the oldest date back to 1995. Specifically, seven (7) passenger motor vehicles were manufactured in 1995; seven (7) in 1996; one (1) in 1997; three (3) in 1998; two (2) in 2000; three (3) in 2001; and one (1) in 2007. In summary, out of a total of twenty-four (24) passenger motor vehicles, the average age of the Inspectorate's vehicle fleet, based on an analysis conducted as of 1 March 2025, is 27.6 years.

In addition to the shortcomings of the vehicle fleet, which negatively affect the mobility of inspectors in the field, it is important to emphasize the persistent risk to inspectors' personal safety when conducting inspections of supervised entities. These risks may take various forms, including verbal threats, endangerment of personal security, violations of physical and/or psychological integrity, and the forcible seizure and/or destruction of official and/or personal documents and objects.

4. CONCEPTUAL OUTLOOK TOWARD THE FUTURE AND THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A MODERN EUROPEAN INSPECTION SERVICE

The transport system is not a closed entity and transcends national borders, as it is mutually coherent and interconnected. Segments of the road network passing through the territory of the Republic of North Macedonia form part of the European transport corridors. Rapid technological development necessitates the advancement and implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), modeled on those in highly developed countries, which contribute to safer, more efficient, and more sustainable transport of passengers and goods. Such systems are essential for the development of a national transport network that meets European standards.

In this context, alongside investments in a modern and intelligent road network, efforts must also be directed toward transforming the State Transport Inspectorate into a modern inspection service capable of adopting and exchanging best practices and experiences with its European counterparts in order to keep pace with the digital era. To this end, the Inspectorate, in cooperation with the EU Delegation in Skopje, prepared a Twinning Project application aimed at strengthening its administrative and technical capacities. On 22 February 2024, an international public call was published for the selection of a Twinning Partner, with a submission deadline of 6 May 2024. The selection process concluded successfully with the appointment of a Polish–Croatian consortium composed of experts from the Chief Inspectorate of Road Transport of the Republic of Poland and the Ministry of the Sea, Transport, and Infrastructure of the Republic of Croatia.

The project officially commenced in Skopje in November 2024 and has a duration of 24 months, with the possibility of a three-month extension. A grant in the amount of EUR 1.3 million was approved for the project through the European Union's Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance 2021–2027 (IPA III).

The general objective of the Twinning Project³⁶ is to enhance road transport safety in the Republic of North Macedonia and to achieve full alignment of national legislation with European Union standards in this area. The specific objectives focus on strengthening the operational capacities and administrative efficiency of the Inspectorate through the

³⁶ <https://javnaadministracija.mk/2025/01/29/mt-tvining-proekt-poddrshka-na-inspekciskite-sluzhbi-za-prevoz-na-patniczi-i-stoki/>. Accessed on 31 March 2025.

proper implementation of national and EU standards for inspection supervision of passenger and goods transport operators.

With regard to its contribution to the European integration process, the project aims to further harmonize national transport legislation with EU law and to strengthen the capacities of national authorities responsible for drafting and implementing transport legislation, including administrative, inspection, and other technical capacities.

A particularly significant aspect of the Twinning Project is the scope of cooperation, which includes approximately 50 expert missions involving 28 Polish and 14 Croatian experts. These missions represent a valuable opportunity for the exchange of know-how, capacity building, and the achievement of measurable results through the transfer of specialized technical knowledge and best practices.

5. CONCLUSION

The Ministry of Transport – State Transport Inspectorate represents one of the key pillars in the institutional framework for road traffic safety, and its functioning has a direct impact on the safety and security of passenger and goods transport. Through this professional paper, an effort has been made, within the limits of scientific observation, to present the role of the Inspectorate within the current institutional framework governing road traffic, emphasizing that this role must be complementary and coherent with that of other stakeholders in the sector.

Despite numerous objective and subjective challenges and risk factors affecting both the quality and quantity of its operational performance, the Inspectorate, although operating under significant strain, manages to fulfill its defined objectives using the available human and technical–technological resources. During the three-year period from 2022 to 2024, a total of 13,034 inspections were conducted. This corresponds to an average of 465.5 inspections per inspector over the three-year period, or an annual average of 155.16 inspections per inspector, which constitutes a respectable result under the given circumstances.

The Inspectorate largely succeeds in implementing planned regular inspections, achieving an implementation rate of 88.62% over the analyzed three-year period. Moreover, it exceeded the planned number of extraordinary inspections by 11.73%, while the overperformance rate for follow-up inspections reached 48.32%.

Additionally, during the same period, the number of detected irregularities exceeded projections by 71.47% (4,916 detected irregularities compared to 2,867 expected). The success rate in identifying specific and more complex irregularities will largely depend not only on the recruitment and continuous professional development of qualified staff but also on the modernization and technical upgrading of the Inspectorate through the introduction of advanced technological tools for timely detection. The subsequent processing of these irregularities, however, depends on the readiness and efficiency of judicial and misdemeanor bodies to ensure lawful, effective, and timely prosecution and sanctioning.

Finally, through the presentation of statistical and analytical indicators, this paper has reflected on the current state of road traffic while offering a theoretical conceptualization of the Inspectorate's role and future direction. With the implementation of ongoing projects in cooperation with the European Union, the State Transport Inspectorate is expected to strengthen its operational and technical capacities and to take a significant step toward becoming a modern inspection service aligned with contemporary demands and guided by the best practices of leading European inspection bodies in the transport sector.

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CORRUPTION IN CUSTOMS AS A CHALLENGE TO NATIONAL SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

Corruption within the Customs Administration represents a significant threat to the national security of the Republic of North Macedonia, as it undermines economic stability, facilitates illegal trade, and erodes public trust. This study aims to examine the roots and consequences of corruption within the Customs Administration in the Republic of North Macedonia, with a particular focus on its impact on national security.

Methods: The research employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, including analyses of official reports, surveys, expert interviews, and review of relevant literature. Additionally, a multidimensional approach based on the Balanced Scorecard and key performance indicators (KPIs) is applied to evaluate institutional effectiveness.

Results: The findings indicate that systemic issues such as low salaries, insufficient oversight, and political interference contribute significantly to corrupt practices. These factors directly undermine institutional credibility and economic security.

Discussion: Corruption in customs creates favorable conditions for organized crime, weakens economic security, and poses a direct threat to national security. The study recommends a range of measures, including institutional reforms, increased transparency, digitalization, ethical training for personnel, whistleblower protection, and the engagement of civil society, in order to reduce corruption and strengthen national resilience.

Keywords: corruption, customs, national security, Republic of North Macedonia, institutional reforms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Systemic corruption poses a direct threat to the functioning of key state institutions, weakening the rule of law and undermining the capacity of the state to deliver fair, transparent, and effective governance (Labović,2022). This threat is particularly severe when corruption is present in institutions responsible for law enforcement and the management of public resource.

One such critical institution is the Customs Administration, which plays a central role in regulating cross-border trade, protecting state borders, and collecting revenues for the national budget. Corruption within customs services can lead to serious consequences, including economic instability, the expansion of the shadow economy, a decline in public trust in institutions, and the facilitation of transnational crime (UNODC, 2022; Transparency International, 2023).

In the context of the Republic of North Macedonia, this issue is of particular significance. As a country with a strategic geographical location in the Balkans and a transit point for numerous international trade and migration routes, the effective and honest functioning of customs authorities is essential. However, multiple reports and studies indicate that corruption within the customs system remains a persistent problem, undermining the rule of law, deterring foreign investment, and fostering organized crime.

Beyond its economic implications, corruption in customs services also carries serious security dimensions. Through bribery, document manipulation, or the concealment of illegal activities, customs officials may knowingly or unknowingly contribute to the trafficking of drugs, weapons, people, and other illicit goods. Consequently, weaknesses within the customs system can be directly linked to broader issues of national and regional security.

The aim of this study is to investigate the occurrence of corruption within the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia by analyzing its scope, the factors driving it, and the consequences it produces, with a particular emphasis on its impact on national security. The research is based on data obtained from relevant institutions, policy analyses, academic literature, and primary sources, providing a comprehensive and objective insight into the problem and offering concrete, applicable recommendations for its mitigation.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Definition of Corruption

Corruption is one of the most complex and widespread phenomena in contemporary society, referring to the misuse of public or entrusted power for personal or group gain, contrary to the public interest and legal regulations (Transparency International, 2023). In both theory and practice, corruption is defined as a phenomenon encompassing various forms and manifestations, such as bribery, favoritism, abuse of official position, conflicts of interest, and misuse of information (Labovic, 2011).

In the context of the Customs Administration, corruption has a specific role and impact. As an institution responsible for monitoring and regulating import-export processes, customs authorities are particularly exposed to corrupt practices that can undermine their legitimacy and effectiveness. For instance, customs officials may accept bribes to allow illegal imports or exports of goods, manipulate documents, or favour certain companies. Such practices result in direct economic damage to the state, as well as a weakening of the rule of law and legal certainty.

Moreover, corruption in customs has broader implications, as it affects economic stability, the competitiveness of domestic companies, and the international reputation of the state. At the same time, these corrupt practices create conditions conducive to organized crime, the trafficking of illegal goods, and even the financing of terrorist activities.

2.2 Corruption in the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia

National security is traditionally defined as a condition in which a state ensures the protection of its citizens, economic resources, and political institutions from threats that could disrupt social order, stability, and sovereignty (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime [UNODC], 2022). Contemporary threats to national security are no longer limited to conventional warfare or terrorist attacks but also include new forms of risk in which corruption and organized crime play a significant role.

Corruption in the customs administration of the Republic of North Macedonia represents a serious threat to national security for several reasons (CARM, 2015):

- **Weakening state control capacity:** When customs services are corrupt, illegal activities such as smuggling of weapons, drugs, counterfeit goods, and other illegal products may go undetected or be tacitly tolerated. This undermines the state's ability to control its borders and markets effectively.
- **Financing criminal groups and terrorism:** Corrupt channels facilitate the financing of organized crime and terrorist organizations, enabling them to sustain and expand their operations.
- **Undermining trust in institutions:** A widespread perception of corruption leads to a loss of public trust in government institutions and the judiciary, which may result in political instability and social unrest.
- **Creating an unfair competitive environment:** Companies that comply with the legal regulations are placed at a disadvantage compared to those that obtain privileges through corrupt practices.

According to reports from international organizations, corruption in customs represents one of the key risks to the security and economic development of the Republic of North Macedonia. Therefore, understanding this phenomenon and developing effective measures to combat it are essential for ensuring national security and long-term stability.

2.3 Institutional and Sociological Theories of Corruption

Corruption, as a social phenomenon, cannot be fully understood without analyzing the institutional and cultural factors that influence the behavior of individuals and organizations. Institutional theory, as proposed by Douglass North (1990), suggests that institutions –defined as formal and informal rules, laws, customs, and norms –shape the dynamics of social and economic relations. The quality and effectiveness of these institutions directly determine whether corruption is suppressed or allowed to flourish.

Klitgaard (1988), in his classical formulation of corruption, states:

“Corruption = Monopoly + Discretion – Transparency”

This formulation means that corruption thrives when officials have monopoly control over resources or services, possess discretionary decision-making power without sufficient oversight, and operate within a system lacking transparency and accountability. In customs services, where officials often exercise discretionary authority to approve or block the movement of goods, this combination creates conditions conducive to corrupt behavior. For individuals considering engagement in corrupt practices, the perceived cost includes both a moral component and the likelihood of punishment. Classical philosophical perspectives provide several guiding principles in this regard (Lukas & Rubel, 2004):

- Individuals should act consistently and in accordance with rational judgement.
- One should strive to maintain respect as a human being within society.
- Agreements with citizens should be honored in order to prevent social disorder, even in times of conflict.

A combination of high discretionary power – resulting in substantial potential gains from corruption – and insufficient accountability is widely regarded as one of the most common structural causes of corruption (Pei, 2009).

2.4 The Importance of Institutional Reforms

Effective efforts to combat corruption in customs require systemic institutional reforms, which include the following elements (Labović, 2022):

1. Systemic Rule of Law

- Establishing a systemic rule of law is a fundamental prerequisite for the development of the Republic of North Macedonia.
- The implementation of a comprehensive and unified system would accelerate economic growth, raise awareness among politicians and citizens, and significantly improve the Republic of North Macedonia's ranking on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI).

2. Deep Structural Reforms

- Structural reforms are necessary within key systems and their subsystems to order to ensure qualitative, sustainable, and practically implementable changes.

3. Development of Public Awareness and a Critical Mass

- Citizens and experts, through engagement and public discussion, can create a critical mass capable of exerting pressure on political actors to pursue genuine reforms.
- Without informed and active citizens and experts, reforms cannot be implemented effectively or sustainably.

4. Expected Effects of Implementation

- Establishment of a functional and effective state.
- Significant improvement in the rule of law.
- Accelerated economic and societal development within a period of four to five years.

These reforms not only reduce opportunities for corruption but also strengthen public and business trust in the customs administration, which is essential for national security and economic development.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To conduct a comprehensive analysis of corruption in the customs administration as a challenge to national security in the Republic of North Macedonia, this study employs a multidimensional research approach. This approach enables a systematic and in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, overcoming the limitations of traditional one-dimensional methods that focus solely on financial indicators or basic statistical data.

3.1 Approach and Methodology

The research is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, aiming to provide a detailed and comprehensive analysis of corrupt practices, their consequences, and the effectiveness of measures implemented to combat them.

- **Qualitative approach:** This includes the analysis of relevant academic literature, official documents, strategic frameworks, and reports from national and international institutions (e.g., Transparency International, UNODC, and the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia). In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted with security experts, customs officials, and representatives of NGOs engaged in anti-corruption initiatives.

- **Quantitative approach:** This involved the analysis of data on reported cases of corruption in the customs administration from 2019 to 2024, obtained from publicly available sources and institutional databases. This analysis covers statistical indicators such as the number of reported cases, their regional distribution, and the types of corrupt activities identified.

3.2 Multidimensional Approach – Balanced Scorecard

To overcome the limitations of traditional performance measurement based exclusively on financial results, this study applies a multidimensional approach grounded in the **Balanced Scorecard model** developed by Robert S. Kaplan and David P. Norton (1992).

This model translates the strategic objectives of the customs administration into specific organizational performance indicators, which are subsequently monitored, measured, and adjusted.

The Balanced Scorecard encompasses four key perspectives:

- **Financial perspective:** Analysis of financial losses resulting from corrupt practices.
- **Customer perspective:** Assessment of satisfaction among the business community and citizens with customs operations.
- **Internal processes:** Evaluation of the efficiency and transparency of customs procedures.
- **Learning and growth:** Assessment of institutional capacities and the ethical awareness of customs officials.

3.3 System Analysis and Indicator Weighting

The primary methodological tool used in this study is **system analysis**, which enables the identification of principles for constructing a list of **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** for the customs service in North Macedonia.

To determine the **relative importance** of each KPI (its weight), the **Weight of Metric** method is applied. The metric weight indicates the significance of a specific KPI in relation to other indicators within the hierarchical measurement system and is expressed as a **percentage share**. The cumulative value of all indicators equals **100%**.

Through the application of this methodology, targeted management and improvement of areas with the greatest impact on **combating corruption** and **strengthening national security** are made possible.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Reported Cases of Corruption in the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia (2019–2024)

Data up to September 2024

Year	Reported cases	Percentage change (%)
2019	120	-
2020	135	+12.5%
2021	110	-18.5%
2022	140	+27.3%
2023	130	-7.1%
2024	125	-3.8%

Source: State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption of the Republic of North Macedonia, 2019–2024

Analysis of Table 1: The table illustrates fluctuations in the number of reported cases of corruption within the Customs Administration of the Republic of North Macedonia during the period 2019–2024. The most significant increase was recorded in 2022, with a 27.3% rise compared to the previous year. This increase may indicate either improved efficiency in reporting mechanisms or an actual rise in corrupt activities. In contrast, the last two years show a slight decline in reported cases, which may be attributed to the initial implementation of anti-corruption measures.

Table 2: Main Causes of Corruption in the Customs Administration According to an Employee Survey (2023)

Cause	Percentage of responses
Low salaries	45%
Insufficient training	30%
Lack of transparency	60%
Political pressures	25%
Weak control mechanisms	55%

Source: Research conducted by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of North Macedonia, 2023

Analysis of Table 2: The survey shows that most customs officers identify lack of transparency (60%) and weak control mechanisms (55%) as the primary challenges enabling corruption. Poor working conditions, particularly low salaries (45%) and insufficient training (30%), were cited as additional factors increasing the system’s vulnerability to corrupt influences.

From the data, it can be observed that reported cases of corruption in the customs administration show an overall upward trend with periodic fluctuations. The largest increase was recorded in 2019, coinciding with intensified control and anti-corruption measures by state institutions.

The growth in recent years may reflect improved awareness and reporting efficiency, but it may also indicate a deepening of corrupt practices, which poses a serious risk to national security.

Analysis 2: The Impact of Corruption in Customs on the National Security of the Republic of North Macedonia

Corruption in the customs administration is not only a legal or economic problem but also a serious challenge to national security. This phenomenon facilitates illegal activities such as smuggling of goods, trade in prohibited products, and the financing of organized crime, all of which directly threaten state stability.

One major consequence is the weakening of trust in state institutions. Citizens and businesses exposed to corrupt practices lose faith in the system, which results in reduced cooperation with competent authorities and diminished support for reforms. Additionally, corruption undermines economic security by increasing the shadow economy and reducing revenue from customs duties. This diminishes budgetary resources available for critical security and social programs, further elevating the risk of crime and social unrest. Data from oversight bodies and interviews with experts indicate that effectively reducing corruption in customs requires a systemic approach, including enhanced oversight, greater

transparency, and the education of customs officers on ethical standards and professional conduct.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND MEASURES TO STRENGTHEN SECURITY THROUGH ANTI-CORRUPTION PRACTICES IN CUSTOMS

- **Enhanced transparency and accountability**
One of the key measures is the introduction of systems that ensure full transparency in customs procedures. This can be achieved through the digitalization of processes, which reduces direct human intervention and the potential for corruption. Implementing systems that record and monitor all transactions and decisions allows for easier detection of irregularities and accountability of officers.
- **Training and education of customs officers**
Regular training on ethics, legislation, and the identification of corrupt practices is necessary to enhance awareness and professional capacity among customs employees. Through such training, officers will be better prepared to resist, report and prevent corrupt influences.
- **Collaboration with civil society and the media**
Active involvement of non-governmental organizations and the media in monitoring and investigating corruption creates additional pressure on authorities to comply with laws and ethical norms. The public must be informed and provided with mechanisms to report corrupt practices safely and anonymously.
- **Introduction of protection mechanisms for whistleblowers**
Protecting individuals who report corruption is crucial for the effective fight against corrupt practices. Legal and psychological protection, as well as guarantees of anonymity, are essential for encouraging whistleblowers without the fear of retaliation.
- **Institutional reforms and strengthened control**
Reforms in the institutional structure of customs, including the independence of anti-corruption bodies and the strengthening of internal controls, will allow for more effective detection, investigation and sanctioning of corruption.

6. CONCLUSION

Corruption in the customs administration represents a serious challenge to the national security of the Republic of North Macedonia. As an institution on the front line of protecting state borders and regulating imports and exports, customs plays a pivotal role in preventing criminal activities and safeguarding the economic sovereignty of the state. However, the presence of corrupt practices weakens this role and opens the door to illegal operations that threaten the economic system, security, and integrity of state institutions. Research indicates that corruption in customs undermines public trust in institutions, facilitates organized criminal networks, and reduces the effectiveness of efforts to combat crime and other illicit activities. Systemic weaknesses, lack of transparency, insufficient training, and weak control mechanisms create fertile ground for corruption.

From a national security perspective, this situation is alarming and requires urgent and comprehensive solutions. Implementing digital platforms and automated processes, enhancing the ethical capacity of officers through targeted training, and introducing

institutional reforms that enable independent oversight and whistleblower protection are key steps toward eradicating corruption.

Furthermore, involving civil society and the media as active partners in oversight and public accountability establishes a strong mechanism for preventing and sanctioning corrupt practices. Only through systemic, coordinated action by all relevant stakeholders can sustainably combat against corruption in the customs service be achieved, thereby strengthening the national security and institutional integrity of the Republic of North Macedonia.

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FROM SAFE HARBOUR TO SYSTEMIC ACCOUNTABILITY: PLATFORM RESPONSIBILITY AND CHILD PROTECTION ONLINE IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

The Internet offers vast opportunities, but it also poses significant risks for children. Societies must move beyond parental control and digital literacy initiatives toward systemic protection. This paper examines how the European Union's regulatory framework – particularly the Digital Services Act, the General Data Protection Regulation, and the Artificial Intelligence Act – can inform North Macedonia's approach to online child protection. Using qualitative and comparative legal methods, it analyses the alignment between European and national legislation and assesses institutional capacities. It further identifies structural gaps in coordination, accountability, and enforcement.

The paper observes that, while North Macedonia has made notable legal progress, practical implementation remains constrained by fragmented institutional mandates and weak inter-agency cooperation. It argues that sustainable progress requires systemic reforms grounded in hybrid governance, linking legal harmonisation, institutional capacity-building, and civic engagement, so that safety, privacy, and participation are recognized as interdependent rights within the country's evolving digital landscape.

Keywords: Digital rights; child protection; platform accountability; data protection; North Macedonia

1. INTRODUCTION

Official statistics confirm what is already a well-known: 97.1% of young people aged 15 to 24 in North Macedonia use the internet almost constantly (State Statistical Office, 2024). However, what statistics fail to capture is how this persistent online presence affects different aspects of young people's lives. As play, communication and social interaction increasingly shift from streets to screens, the risks traditionally associated with the offline world are now reproduced online. Algorithms, anonymity, and constant connectivity reinforce these dangers.

Children face a broad spectrum of online harms, ranging from exposure to violent, pornographic, or hateful content to grooming, cyberbullying, and the non-consensual sharing of images.³⁷ Technological developments have also generated more subtle forms of harm,

³⁷ UNICEF Office of Research – Innocenti. (2024). *Children's exposure to hate messages and violent images online*. Florence: UNICEF Office of Research – Innocenti.

particularly with the rise of artificial intelligence. Algorithmic systems shape children’s views, beliefs, and behavior, while easily accessible applications enable the creation and dissemination of deepfake content. As a result, the line between reality and fabrication becomes blurred, while manipulation, humiliation, and gender-based violence are becoming widespread.³⁸

At both global and EU levels, there is a growing shift away from the traditional paradigm that views digital platforms as neutral intermediaries. Major scandals – including the Cambridge Analytica case³⁹, large-scale election misinformation, and the widespread dissemination of child sexual abuse material – have contributed to a transition from mere liability for user-generated content toward models of shared responsibility.

By contrast, North Macedonia largely remains within the so-called “safe harbor” era for global digital platforms. Major social media companies have no formal representatives in the country and are not subject to direct compliance under Macedonian law. Consequently, the capacity to effectively prevent and address cases of online abuse remains limited. The *Public Room* case is a fitting example.⁴⁰ In this large-scale instance of intimate image abuse, thousands of survivors – predominantly women and girls – were left without effective access to justice, while most perpetrators escaped accountability.

North Macedonia is currently on a path towards EU accession, a process in which legal harmonization plays a central role. This paper therefore analyzes both EU and Macedonian legal frameworks and assesses how harmonization can contribute to the creation of a safer digital environment for children. However, as this paper argues, digital safety is a more complex question and cannot be achieved solely through legislative reform. For this reason, the analysis goes beyond the Digital Services Act (DSA, Regulation (EU) 2022/2065), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679), and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act, Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) – the EU’s key legislative instruments in this field – and seeks to outline practical recommendations for building a child-centered digital ecosystem in North Macedonia.

<https://www.unicef.org/innocenti/media/2621/file/UNICEF-Children-Exposure-Hate-Violence-Online.pdf>

³⁸ European Parliament. (2025). *Children and deepfakes*. European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS).

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/775855/EPRS_BRI\(2025\)775855_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2025/775855/EPRS_BRI(2025)775855_EN.pdf)

³⁹ The Cambridge Analytica scandal involved the unlawful harvesting of Facebook data from tens of millions of users without consent, which was subsequently used for psychological profiling and micro-targeted political advertising –revealing major failures in platform data governance and user protection.

See

also:

Information Commissioner’s Office. (2018). *Investigation into the use of data analytics in political campaigns*.

<https://ico.org.uk/media2/migrated/2260271/investigation-into-the-use-of-data-analytics-in-political-campaigns-final-20181105.pdf>

⁴⁰ Petkovska, N., & Leshoska, V. (2021). *За кого интернетот е безбедно место? Родово-засновано насилство во онлајн просторот* [For whom is the internet a safe place? Gender-based violence in the online space]. National Network to End Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence. <https://glasprotivnasilstvo.org.mk/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Za-kogo-internetot-e-bezbedno-mesto-finalno.-docx.pdf>

2. THE EU FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN

2.1 DIGITAL SERVICES ACT

The Digital Services Act (DSA, Regulation (EU) 2022/2065) represents a significant milestone in European law, redefining how responsibility is structured in the digital world. It marks a departure from the paradigm in which online safety depends solely on individual awareness or parental control, introducing instead the principle that protection must be embedded within the very systems that shape our digital interaction.

The DSA introduces the concept of systemic accountability through a layered system of obligations that scale according to a platform's size and influence. All services that hosts content are required to provide simple mechanisms for reporting and removing illegal material and to act transparently with regard to content moderation decisions. Platforms with the greatest influence – those capable of shaping what millions of people see each day – carry far greater responsibilities.

These Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) and Very Large Online Search Engines (VLOSEs) must regularly conduct risk assessments how their design, algorithms, and recommender systems affect users' rights and well-being (Art. 34 DSA; Recital 84). For the first time in EU law, these entities are legally obliged to assess the specific risks their services pose to children, including exposure to harmful or age-inappropriate content, manipulative or addictive design features, and the emotional or psychological effects of constant visibility, social comparison, and algorithmic amplification (Art. 34(1)(b-c) DSA; Recital 89).

The DSA further prohibits targeted advertising based on the profiling of minors, thereby ensuring that children are not subjected to personalized commercial influence or behavioural targeting (Art. 28(2) DSA). In addition, the Regulation calls for age-appropriate design and enhanced safety measures that protect young users while enabling their meaningful participation online. Platforms are required to adopt proportionate and effective risk-mitigation measures tailored to the needs of children (Art. 35 DSA; Recital 71).

Transparency and oversight also constitute two important aspects of the DSA. Platforms must publish detailed reports, share data with independent researchers, and submit to external audits of their risk-assessment and mitigation practices. A newly established European Board for Digital Services ensures that these obligations are enforced.

What distinguished the Digital Services Act is its redefinition of what accountability means in the digital sphere by framing online safety as a prerequisite for meaningful participation in the digital public sphere.

2.2 GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR)

While the DSA redefines the responsibilities of online platforms, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679) remains the moral and legal cornerstone of the European Union's digital rights framework. The GDPR transformed data protection from a predominantly technical concern into a matter of human dignity, recognising that the collection and dissemination of personal data affects how individuals exercise autonomy, freedom, and identity in the digital environment. For children, these safeguards are foundational to their right to grow, learn, and participate safely online.

The GDPR is the first comprehensive EU legal instrument to recognise children as a distinct category of data subjects entitled to special protection (Recital 38 GDPR). It does so by acknowledging that children may not fully understand the long-term consequences of their digital activities, even though their data – from photos and educational apps to browsing histories and online preferences – may follow them throughout their lives. To address these

risks, the GDPR established a minimum age for digital consent (set between thirteen and sixteen, depending on the Member State) and requires that privacy notices be presented in clear and age-appropriate language (Art. 8 (1); Recital 38 GDPR).

The Regulation also introduces the right to erasure, often called the “right to be forgotten,” enabling individuals to request the deletion of personal data collected during their childhood (Recital 65-66 GDPR). Equally important is the GDPR’s restriction on profiling and targeted advertising that exploits children’s behaviour or emotional patterns (Article 22 GDPR).

Although the GDPR primarily focuses on data processing rather than platform architecture, its principles of fairness, transparency, and accountability complement the systemic model introduced by the DSA. While the DSA governs how platforms must manage risk, the GDPR safeguards the personal integrity of the user operating within those systems. Taken together, these instruments establish a coherent framework in which privacy, safety, and participation are understood as interdependent rights – each essential to protecting children in the digital environment.

2.3 THE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT (AI ACT)

The Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act, Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) complements the DSA and the GDPR by addressing how algorithms themselves shape risk. It represents the first comprehensive attempt worldwide to regulate artificial intelligence systems according to the level of risk they pose to safety and fundamental rights.

The AI Act classifies AI systems along a spectrum ranging from minimal to unacceptable risk. AI practices that manipulate or exploit the vulnerabilities of children are explicitly prohibited. Systems considered high-risk – such as those used in education, recruitment, or law-enforcement contexts – must undergo rigorous conformity assessments, transparency checks, and continuous human oversight (Article 6 (2); ANNEX III AI Act). These requirements are designed to ensure that decisions influencing a child’s opportunities or digital experiences are explainable and fair (Recital 48 AI Act).

The AI Act also establishes transparency obligations applicable to all AI applications that interact with the public. Users must be informed when they are engaging with an AI system or when content is artificially generated including deepfakes and other forms of synthetic media. This provision has clear implications for the protection of children against deception, manipulation, or emotional distress caused by artificial content that blurs the line between authentic and fabricated experiences (Article 50 AI Act).

In many respects, the AI Act closes a conceptual gap left by earlier regulations. While the GDPR governs personal data processing and the DSA regulates platform responsibilities, the AI Act addresses the technologies that drive those systems. Together, they form a triad of accountability: the GDPR ensures lawful data use, the DSA enforces responsible platform design and operation, and the AI Act introduces ethical and technical safeguards for the algorithms at their core.

2.4 OTHER SUPPORTING DIRECTIVES

A set of complementary directives further completes the European Union’s framework for protecting children in the digital environment.

The Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD, Directive 2010/13/EU, as amended by Directive 2018/1808), was the first EU legislative act to classify video-sharing platforms as active organisers of online audiovisual content. It requires platforms to adopt appropriate measures to protect children from content that may impair their physical, mental,

or moral development. Such measures include age-verification tools, parental controls, content-classification systems, and user-reporting mechanisms. These obligations established an early form of shared responsibility among regulators, industry actors, and parents – a logic that later evolved into the systemic accountability framework introduced by the Digital Services Act.

Directive 2011/93/EU remains the criminal-law backbone of child protection within the EU. On 6 February 2024, the European Commission submitted a proposal to recast the Directive in order to ensure that “*all forms of child sexual abuse and exploitation, including those enabled or facilitated by technological developments*” are criminalised. The proposed revision explicitly addresses online solicitation, live-streaming of child sexual abuse, and the operation of online infrastructures facilitating such offences.⁴¹

Privacy and security in electronic communications are governed by the ePrivacy Directive (Directive 2002/58/EC), which guarantees the confidentiality of communications. As this framework does not, in itself, permit the systematic detection of child sexual abuse material (CSAM), a temporary derogation adopted in 2021 (Regulation (EU) 2021/1232) allows service providers to continue identifying and reporting CSAM under strict safeguards. This derogation applies until a permanent legal basis is established through the forthcoming ePrivacy Regulation. This delicate balance reflects a broader EU principle: privacy and child protection are not competing values but mutually reinforcing rights.

Finally, Directive (EU) 2024/1385 on combating violence against women and domestic violence marks a milestone in the recognition of digital gender-based violence. For the first time, EU law explicitly criminalises non-consensual sharing of intimate material, cyberstalking, and online harassment – phenomena with profound implications for children and adolescents, particularly girls. Its adoption in 2024 represents an important step toward closing the gap between online and offline protection.

2.5 CROSS-CUTTING MECHANISMS AND PRINCIPLES

The EU’s approach treats the online environment as a shared public space in which rights and responsibilities are intertwined, and children’s well-being becomes a collective duty. Across the DSA, the GDPR, the AI Act, and related directives runs a common thread: protection, participation, and dignity belong together. Children cannot be safe if they are silenced, nor can they participate meaningfully if their privacy and emotional security are not respected. These three principles reinforce one another, forming the moral foundation of Europe’s digital policy.

Transparency sits at the core of this system. It means making visible how digital power operates – who decides what we see, believe, or share. Platforms must open the “black box” of algorithms and explain the choices that shape our information spaces. As Kaushal et al. (2024) note, the DSA brings “automated transparency” into law, allowing both regulators and the public to observe how moderation and recommendation systems function – an essential condition for democratic oversight in algorithmic societies. For children, this openness exposes the forces that shape their curiosity and self-image, giving adults the opportunity to intervene before harm becomes invisible or normalised.

⁴¹ European Parliament. (2025). *Report on the proposal for a directive on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child sexual abuse material and replacing Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA (recast)*. A9-0000/2025. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-10-2025-0097_EN.html

The second pillar – prevention and risk mitigation – signals the EU’s shift from reaction to anticipation. Platforms are now required to identify and reduce risks before they cause harm, whether these involve illegal content, manipulative design, or psychological distress. This approach recognises that technology is never neutral: every interface and every algorithmic choice carries moral and emotional consequences. By embedding responsibility into design, the EU reframes online safety as foresight rather than repair.

A child-centred perspective runs throughout the entire framework. Each instrument – from the DSA to the Directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence – acknowledges children as rights-holders and participants in digital life. This perspective reframes safety not as protection from the world, but as the freedom to engage with it safely. When protection and participation work together, children gain the confidence to explore, learn, and belong.

Finally, the EU model depends on shared responsibility. Laws alone cannot create a safe internet; they must be complemented by education, awareness, and cooperation. The Better Internet for Kids (BIK+) Strategy embodies this principle, linking governments, educators, civil society, and the technology sector into a single community of care. As Sobko and Merkou (2025) observe, this multi-stakeholder approach “bridges the gap between legal obligations and everyday practice,” transforming compliance into collective action.

Together, these principles mark a quiet but profound cultural shift. Europe is building not only a system of regulation but a vision of the digital world as a space in which safety, empathy, and accountability coexist – where protecting children is inseparable from protecting what is human online.

3.THE NATIONAL CONTEXT – NORTH MACEDONIA’S LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL LANDSCAPE

3.1 LEGISLATIVE AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

North Macedonia’s framework for online safety and child protection has developed gradually, mirroring the country’s broader digital transformation and European integration trajectory. The legal architecture consists of several relevant laws and bylaws that collectively shape the national approach to digital rights, privacy, media regulation, and child protection.

The Law on Personal Data Protection (LPDP, 2020) establishes a child-centred framework aligned with Article 8 of the GDPR. It sets the age of digital consent at fourteen, mandates parental authorisation for younger users, and requires that all privacy communications be presented in child-friendly language. The law also guarantees the right to erasure and restricts the processing of minors’ data for commercial or profiling purposes. The Agency for Personal Data Protection (APDP) oversees implementation, monitors compliance, and conducts awareness-raising activities aimed at strengthening data ethics and digital literacy across institutions, schools, and the private sector.

The Law on Audio and Audiovisual Media Services (LAAMS, 2013/2024) complements this framework by incorporating European standards for media accountability and the protection of minors. It regulates video-sharing platforms, prohibits covert advertising, and requires clear labelling of commercial communications. In addition, in 2025 these obligations were extended to influencers and other content creators, recognising them as media actors subject to transparency and registration requirements (Rulebook on

Individual Providers of On-Demand Audiovisual Media Services, 2025). In parallel, the Rulebook on the Protection of Minors introduces detailed obligations for both legal and individual providers of audiovisual content to safeguard children from harmful

material. It prohibits child pornography and excessive violence, establishes age-based classification systems, defines time-of-day restrictions for broadcast content, and requires visual and acoustic warnings. The Rulebook further obliges on-demand audiovisual media service providers to implement technical access-control and age-verification tools to prevent minors from accessing harmful content.

The Criminal Code criminalises several technology-facilitated forms of child sexual abuse and exploitation, including offences related to child sexual abuse material (Art. 193-a), the online solicitation or grooming of a child for sexual purposes (Art. 193-b), and child trafficking for the purpose of sexual exploitation, which also encompasses online forms of abuse (Art. 418-g). The Minister of Justice has publicly announced that forthcoming amendments will seek to align domestic legislation with EU standards on sexual abuse and gender-based violence, including provisions addressing image-based abuse and deepfake technologies (MIA, 2024).⁴²

At the institutional level, several bodies contribute to implementation. The Agency for Personal Data Protection (APDP) acts as the data protection authority; the Cybercrime and Digital Forensics Sector within the Ministry of Interior investigates online offences; and the Agency for Audio and Audiovisual Media Services (AAVMS) oversees compliance with media standards and the protection of minors in broadcasting and on-demand services. In 2025, the Government of North Macedonia established the National Centre for a Safer Internet as the single national contact and coordination point for reporting, awareness-raising, and capacity building related to children’s use of digital technologies. In parallel, the National Council for Digital Transformation and Cybersecurity was created as a high-level coordinating body responsible for policies and activities related to digitalisation, online safety, and cyber resilience (Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, 2025a; 2025b).

3.2 STRUCTURAL GAPS AND POLICY LIMITATIONS

While North Macedonia has made significant strides toward aligning its legislation with the European framework, the country’s system of digital protection remains transitional – more reflective of formal compliance than of the systemic accountability envisioned by the EU. Legal provisions exist, yet the structures that give them practical effect are still maturing.

One key challenge lies in the absence of an integrated model of coordination and risk management. Responsibilities for children’s online safety are distributed across multiple agencies – the APDP for data protection, the AAVMS for media oversight, the Cybercrime Unit for investigation, and various ministries responsible for education and social policy – but there is no central mechanism to ensure coherence or shared accountability. As a result, institutional cooperation depends largely on personal initiative rather than structured protocols. While the National Centre for a Safer Internet represents an important step toward institutionalized inter-agency cooperation, its effectiveness will depend on clearly defined mandates, sustainable funding, and systematic collaboration among all relevant actors.

A second gap concerns jurisdiction and enforcement. The current regulatory scope extends only to entities established within North Macedonia, leaving global platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, and Meta outside direct national oversight. This structural limitation

⁴² Macedonian Information Agency. (2024). *Филков: Секој потрошен денар во судството мора да биде оправдан со резултати – побрзи постапки, поголема доверба и поквалитетни судски одлуки*. MIA. <https://mia.mk/story/ФИЛКОВ>

means that national regulators can monitor local actors – including influencers and domestic media providers – but cannot require compliance, data transparency, or risk assessments from the platforms where children spend most of their digital lives. Similarly, cooperation between law enforcement authorities and major social media companies remains limited.⁴³In this respect, the country remains dependent on external mechanisms – notably the EU’s Digital Services Act and European-level codes of conduct –without the capacity to transpose their systemic duties into effective domestic enforcement.

Institutional capacity represents another critical constraint. Regulatory bodies operate with limited budgets, small teams, and insufficient technological tools for algorithmic or behavioural risk analysis⁴⁴. Training in areas such as AI governance, data ethics, and child-centred digital design remains sporadic, limiting the depth of domestic expertise. Within the justice system, awareness of the psychological and procedural needs of child survivors of online abuse is gradually improving; however, specialisation remains uneven and case management continues to be slow⁴⁵.The Agency for Personal Data Protection (APDP) continues to operate with limited independence, staff, and resources, constraining its ability to fulfill its mandate effectively (European Commission, 2024; 2025). At the policy level, fragmentation persists. Strategies related to digitalisation, gender equality, and child rights acknowledge online risks but do so in peripheral manner, without measurable objectives or cross-sectoral alignment. The result is a framework that fulfils formal harmonization requirements but lacks the connective tissue – shared indicators, prevention models, and evaluation mechanisms – that would enable it to function as a living ecosystem of protection.

Taken together, these gaps reveal not resistance to progress, but the need for a conceptual shift: from reactive oversight toward proactive, risk-based governance. Aligning with the EU model requires more than legislative harmonisation; it demands adoption of the cultural logic behind European digital regulation – a view of online safety grounded in foresight, design, and collective accountability rather than post-hoc regulation.

3.3 PATHWAYS FOR ALIGNMENT AND RESILIENCE

Bridging this transitional stage requires a shift from compliance to culture – embedding the principles of transparency, prevention, and participation into national institutions and policies. The EU’s systemic approach offers both a template and a mirror: it illustrates what mature digital governance can achieve while highlighting areas where national practice must evolve.

⁴³ Stevanović, A., Ristevski, O., & Skara, G. (2021). *Cyberbullying, stalking and online harassment in North Macedonia and Serbia*. WEASA. <https://www.weasa.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Research-on-cyber-stalking-in-North-Macedonia-and-Serbia.pdf>

⁴⁴Both the 2024 and 2025 European Commission Progress Reports highlight severe limitations in the institutional capacity of the Personal Data Protection Agency (PDPA), noting its lack of budgetary independence, insufficient financial and human resources, inability to fulfil core supervisory tasks, and weakened consultation and governance mechanisms – conditions that directly undermine effective data protection oversight in North Macedonia. (European Commission, North Macedonia Report 2024; North Macedonia Report 2025)

⁴⁵As noted by the European Commission, access to justice, legal representation and capacity-building for public officials working with child victims remain insufficient, indicating persistent gaps in specialisation and systemic weaknesses in handling cases involving children.(European Commission, North Macedonia 2024 Progress Report; North Macedonia 2025 Progress Report).

Building on recently established coordination mechanisms – including the National Council for Digital Transformation and Cybersecurity and the National Centre for a Safer Internet – North Macedonia should aim to strengthen horizontal cooperation and ensure that these bodies operate within a unified framework of accountability and child protection. The establishment of a National Digital Safety Council could further institutionalise multi-stakeholder collaboration by linking government oversight with civil-society expertise and educational outreach. Acting as a national node of accountability, such a body could coordinate prevention strategies, data collection, and rapid response to online harms, in line with the EU’s principle of “shared responsibility.”

Capacity-building remains equally essential. Targeted training in areas such as algorithmic transparency, digital evidence, and child-centred communication could help bridge the expertise gap among judges, prosecutors, educators, and social workers. Partnerships with European institutions and agencies –including Europol, ENISA, and the European Board for Digital Services – would facilitate knowledge exchange, joint investigations, and access to emerging standards of digital risk assessment.

The Western Balkans face similar challenges in digital governance. Regional cooperation –through mechanisms such as the Regional Cooperation Council, the South Eastern Europe Law Enforcement Centre (SELEC), or bilateral agreements – could enhance cross-border information exchange and promote common standards for online child protection. Coordinated regional advocacy could also strengthen visibility and influence of smaller states in dialogues with major online platforms, ensuring that their specific needs are represented in global governance discussions.

Developing a national framework for systemic risk management, inspired by the DSA’s model of graduated responsibility, would further reinforce accountability. Such a framework could require major online intermediaries operating within the Macedonian market to conduct child-impact assessments and submit transparency reports to national regulators. Even if implemented as a voluntary or co-regulatory mechanism, this approach would demonstrate the country’s commitment to shared accountability and alignment with future EU membership obligations.

Civil society should remain a cornerstone of this transformation. Local organisations often act as first responders to digital harm, bridging gaps between families, schools, and public institutions. Institutionalising their role through stable funding mechanisms and formal cooperation agreements would strengthen sustainability and ensure continuity beyond short-term project cycles.

Ultimately, building resilience requires reframing digital safety as a positive right – not merely the absence of harm, but the ability of children to participate, learn, and express themselves within safe and empowering digital environments. Embedding this perspective across education, media policy, and judicial practice would mark the transition from fragmented protection towards a cohesive national system grounded in the principles of European digital citizenship.

4. CONCLUSION

North Macedonia's experience reveals the complexity of translating global digital governance principles into a small-state context with limited institutional resources. The European Union's evolving framework – built around transparency, systemic risk management, and protection of child rights – has reshaped how accountability in digital environments is understood. For candidate countries, this shift represents both an obligation and an opportunity: aligning with EU standards requires the development of institutions capable of enforcing those standards, not merely the formal adoption of legislative language. The analysis demonstrates that, while North Macedonia has achieved substantial formal convergence with the EU framework, its practical capacity to protect children online remains uneven. Fragmented institutional responsibilities, weak inter-agency coordination, and the absence of clear accountability mechanisms create gaps between legal ambition and effective enforcement. Global platforms continue to operate beyond national regulatory oversight, while domestic institutions rely on reactive, case-based interventions rather than systemic prevention strategies.

Further progress depends on institutional learning and cooperation. Strengthening the independence and expertise of regulators, integrating child protection into digitalisation policies, and formalising cross-sectoral coordination mechanisms could transform existing efforts into a coherent system. Equally essential is the engagement of civil society organizations, educators, and children themselves, whose participation anchors these reforms in lived experience and fosters social trust.

Viewed in this light, digital child protection becomes a critical lens through which broader governance capacity is tested. The effectiveness with which a society safeguards its most vulnerable members online reflects its understanding of rights, accountability, and the responsibilities attached to power in a networked world.

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